

*“Living is a career, do you know
what I mean?”*

Young-Onset Dementia and Women’s Career Development

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I Abstract

This thesis explores how living with young-onset dementia impacts women's career development. Dementia is a growing global concern, often associated with older age, though the number of people being diagnosed with the condition at a younger age is increasing. Being diagnosed when younger often presents additional career and life-stage related challenges and concerns. Career in this study refers to paid work and other roles and activities that are important to individuals, so is defined as life and work. People living with young-onset dementia have careers that are composed of paid employment, voluntary activities (such as dementia advocacy and campaign work) and personal roles (such as within the family). Recognising that people living with young-onset dementia are not homogenous, and that more gendered perspectives within both dementia and career-related research are needed, this study has focused on women's experiences.

Twelve women living with young-onset dementia participated in this study through online interviews. Objectives for the research included exploration of the impact of dementia on career life roles and stages, enablers and disablers of career roles and the meaning of participants' chosen objects to career identities. Object elicitation was therefore used in an innovative way to begin interviews and explore career. Findings were generated using reflexive thematic analysis, including innovative creative approaches to analysis and understanding the data through art and crochet. This research has evidenced that women living with young-onset dementia have careers that include change and challenge, evolving feelings and needs. Themes included how careers continue but are not continuous, and connections with peers and a community of others who offer support enable positive career continuance. The roots of career formed before developing dementia can facilitate new positive branches of career after diagnosis. This study offers a needed and unique contribution to our knowledge of gendered experiences of *life and work* when living with young-onset dementia.

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IV Positionality Statement

This positionality statement has been written to support the reflexive process. It was first drafted before data collection commenced and then reviewed during data analysis. Guidance from Chiu (2023) inspired this statement.

My name is Rachel Allen and (at the time of thesis submission) I am 43 years old. I completed a Masters Degree in Disability Studies via distance learning, graduating in 2010. I started the Masters after discovering the Centre for Disability Studies at the University of Leeds when researching the dissertation project for my Foundation Degree in Business and Financial Administration (FDBPA), which I completed in 2008. Both the FDBPA and Masters were completed whilst I was working part-time for a local authority in London.

I worked part-time because when I was 17 and starting the second year of my A-Levels, I became ill with ME. Whilst medical recognition and understanding of this condition has improved since my diagnosis, particularly recently with concerns arising from long-Covid, the legacy of having a disbelieved neurological condition from my youth has affected the way I think and understand the world and those living in it, as well as myself. Completing the Masters supported my development of an identity as a disabled person and commitment to the social model of disability. I recognise that my life experiences, such as academic opportunities, time since symptom onset and my faith have afforded me the privilege of negotiating a positive disabled identity. I used to be reluctant to disclose the diagnosis of ME because of the insensitive reactions from others, as I've grown older I feel more secure in myself and less reactive to other's opinions about the diagnosis. When younger I occasionally used a wheelchair and often used a walking stick, and now I rarely need these, but I'm aware that there is no external sign of impairment. There is also no way to biologically evidence the experience of ME. My life has been so profoundly impacted by what cannot be seen, so as a researcher this has a strong influence on my epistemology and understanding of reality. I feel living with an invisible illness has enabled me to develop a sensitivity to identities and experiences different to my own, to distrust appearances, and fuelled a strong motivation to learn, discover and research.

I do not identify with any particular social class because defining this is complex. My Father was a police officer. I grew up in a house provided by the police in a quiet cul-de-sac, in a middle class neighbourhood in south-west London. Homes in this neighbourhood are now worth well over £1

million. When I was 19, I moved out of the family home into a council flat by myself. I continue to live alone and now rent a studio flat in Glasgow. When I was 30, I moved to Cumbria. I was made redundant from my local authority job and took this opportunity to relocate nearer my maternal Grandma. I then relocated to Glasgow after starting the PhD.

This is my first experience of being a full-time student since my A-Levels. Since then, I have had periods where I could not work due to fatigue and was reliant on state benefits. I found the benefits system cruel and difficult. Being able to work meant a restoration of dignity, of an identity not dictated by brown envelopes, of a freedom from accountability to assessments that measured nothing about who I was. As a working person, I could claim success. I could define myself more positively. I could unentangle myself from the constant stress of eligibility, applications, appeals and the worries that if I managed to cook a meal or ache less I would be arrested for benefit fraud. Since my first job at 16 years old I have worked in retail, banking (briefly!), local government, the charity sector and education. I have always sought jobs that in some way help people.

Before starting the PhD, I was working four part-time jobs and received (and needed) Working Tax Credit. Though I stopped receiving this when I started the PhD, a brown C5 envelope through the door still makes my heart lurch. Many of my career decisions have been decided by my health, for example retraining as a Teaching Assistant so I could work more locally. While I have often not been in healthy financial circumstances, I recognise that I have been able to avoid debt or severe hardship through the financial sense I developed and education I received when I was younger. I have been able to understand and negotiate support systems, such as social housing, enabling me to maintain a home when this may otherwise not have been possible. I was profoundly affected by my experience of claiming benefits. One of the most rewarding jobs I've had was as a benefits advisor, where I felt I could use my experiences to support others. Bringing positive out of negative is important to me.

I also recognise that my Christian faith has been pivotal to my experiences, and provided a source of hope when circumstances were dire. However, this also is complex. When younger, I enjoyed church and had many social connections there. As I have grown older, I have felt alienated from church not only because it isn't designed for someone with ME, but as a single older woman it can also be a very lonely experience. Christian ideas about illness, such as prayers for healing, are confusing and difficult to negotiate in the context of a life that has spent more years sick than well.

I celebrate all the complexities and contradictions that have made me who I am and continue to do so. I am chronically ill, but look well. I am not employed, but able to live comfortably. I am a Christian, but don't usually go to church. I have a small biological family and a wide, beautifully diverse, extended family of choice. I recognise privilege in my whiteness, Britishness, relative

affluence and identifying with my biological gender. I am privileged to have had the resources to overcome challenging circumstances both from within and through others offering their love and support.

In the context of this PhD research, my journey of illness disrupting and influencing my career motivates me to explore this connection beyond my own experience. My Grandma died in 2014, in her 80's, from dementia. Many memories I have of her, things I learned about and from her, I would not have if her dementia had developed earlier. Since starting this PhD, I have learned a lot about dementia; a lot that would have helped me be a better Granddaughter when she was distressed and anxious. I recognise what I'd describe as the 'spikey privilege' that so many years of illness has given me; the time to adjust, negotiate identities and struggle to a positive place. Young-onset dementia offers no such privilege. Those with young-onset dementia have a limited period from symptom onset and diagnosis to progression and death. I'm motivated, through this research, to learn how we can ensure maximum quality of life and enable women to continue having the careers they want to for as long as possible.

1. Background

1.1 Introduction

By 2030, the World Health Organisation projects that 78 million people worldwide will be living with dementia, and this is predicted to rise to 139 million by 2050 (World Health Organisation, 2021).

There are approximately 90,000 people living with dementia in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2023) and it is a primary cause of death for women in Scotland (Alzheimer Scotland, 2023).

Dementia is often associated with older age, but those living with young-onset dementia develop the condition before they are 65 years old; an age where many will be working, have financial commitments and caring responsibilities. Working, finances and caring are all important facets of career; and how career is understood generally has been evolving as retirement age and job instability have increased, along with wider social change (such as expectations around parenthood).

The aim of this *Background* chapter is to introduce this thesis, the focus of which is women living with young-onset dementia and their career development. The preceding *Positionality Statement* introduced myself as the researcher, and in the following sections further context for the research will be provided; beginning with *Dementia* before an overview of the legal and policy context of the research and discussion of career theory. I introduce my qualitative approach, reflect on my interest in the topic and articulate the study aim and objectives. An overview of the thesis now follows.

1.1.1 Thesis Overview

This thesis will be structured as follows: The *Literature Review* follows this *Background* chapter. The *Methodology* chapter then discusses the theoretical foundation for the study before detail about the data collection method and how data from interviews were analysed is included in *Methods*. The *Findings* chapter presents the learning generated from the data. The *Discussion* chapter evaluates how findings have addressed the research aim and connect to existing literature. The research aim and objectives were developed following an integrative literature review, exploring research related to what people living with young-onset dementia do. This helped to inform an understanding of how young-onset dementia impacts different elements and aspects of career.

1.1.2 Research Aims and Objectives

The research aim for this study is to *explore how women living with young-onset dementia experience life roles in the context of career.*

The research objectives are to:

- Explore how a diagnosis of young-onset dementia impacts life role identities and life stages for women
- Identify enablers and disablers of career role continuance for women living with young-onset dementia
- Explore the meaning of artefacts to career and career identities for women living with young-onset dementia.

As an exploratory study, a qualitative research approach is appropriate. Reflexive thematic analysis (RTA), developed by Braun and Clarke (2022a), is used as an underpinning theoretical framework for this study, alongside theoretical perspectives related to career, disability and gender. The method of data gathering utilised here are semi-structured online interviews using object elicitation.

1.2 Dementia

Dementia is a clinical syndrome to describe neurodegenerative illnesses which affect brain and bodily health. Alzheimer's disease is the most common (Chertkow, 2022); however there are multiple types of dementia (over 200), and other forms include frontotemporal dementia (FTD), vascular dementia, dementia with lewy bodies and mixed dementia (Dementia UK, 2022a). Wendy Mitchell, a person living with dementia until her death in 2024 and dementia advocate, stated that "everyone is an individual, so when you meet one person with dementia, you've met only one person with dementia" (Age UK, 2019, p. Unpaged); highlighting that the ways dementia can affect individuals varies widely. Symptoms can negatively impact memory, thought processing and undertaking everyday activities (World Health Organisation, 2023) and also include "confusion, problems with understanding, difficulties with speech, problems with decision-making [and] changes in behaviour" (Dementia UK, 2022a, p. 7). Memory loss is first on the UK National Health Service (NHS)'s list of problems caused by dementia symptoms; the list also includes difficulty with mental agility, language, judgement, mood, ability to move and manage daily tasks (NHS, 2023, p. Unpaged).

Providing exact numbers related to dementia prevalence is problematic, for example because not everyone living with dementia will have a formal diagnosis, but millions of people across the world develop dementia each year (World Health Organisation, 2023). Access to obtaining a diagnosis is not universal. For example, residents in Scotland can access free medical care via the NHS but may live in a rural area, which makes traveling to a hospital difficult. Access to diagnosis in other countries may be cost prohibitive, limited due to availability of diagnostic professionals and equipment, or not accessible due to dementia-related stigma.

Dementia is a stigmatised condition (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018; Scott, 2022; Swaffer, 2014). Discrimination and disadvantage can occur not only because of the condition, but because of what others think about the condition. Areas of dementia-related stigma include fears about incapacity and death, with perceptions being informed by advanced and end stages of the condition and of dementia being seen as “a diagnosis without hope” (Pritchard and Bartlett, 2024, p. 1). It is thought of as a condition of old age and not of concern to younger people, and therefore most dementia-related services focus on those who are older (Carter, Oyebode and Koopmans, 2018). Wider social perceptions and stigma influence understanding of oneself, for example undermining personal resources (Ritchie *et al.*, 2020) and experiencing ‘self-stigma’ (Wolverson, Clarke and Moniz-Cook, 2016). Research has an important role in addressing stigma through “developing a better understanding” of those who are stigmatised (Wiersma, 2011, p. 204). Kitwood and Bredin (1992) and Kitwood (1997) have highlighted the importance of negating stigma by focusing on the personhood of the individual with dementia; and this has been extended to include different ways of conceptualising dementia, such as through feminism (Sandberg, 2023), and understanding personhood through the lens of citizenship (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2007; Sandberg, 2023), which emphasises the rights and agency someone living with dementia has.

Dementia is a progressive and terminal condition. There is no cure for dementia. However, in 2024 two new modifiable risk factors for dementia were identified (vision loss and high LDL cholesterol) (Livingston *et al.*, 2024), adding to the 12 factors published in 2020 (Livingston *et al.*, 2020). Understanding of dementia is therefore constantly deepening, because research doesn't stop and is ongoing (Hartnell, 2024). This is leading to advancements in how dementia is managed, treated and possibly cured in the future. For example, through new medications (Hartnell, 2024) and technology. Alongside biological and pharmaceutical advances, it is important that stigma around dementia is reduced so that those living with dementia can enjoy the maximum quality of life possible after diagnosis. This includes continuing their careers, for example through paid work, for as long as they want and need to. With life expectancies in countries like the UK increasing, more people are going

to be living with dementia for longer. There is growing recognition that involving people living with dementia in research is important for reducing stigma and developing evidence-based policy and service provision (Cridland *et al.*, 2016a). Through development of in-depth understanding of dementia experiences, society can evolve to support those who develop dementia, and reduce the fear and isolation that can accompany the diagnosis.

1.2.1 Young-Onset Dementia

While dementia is often thought of as a condition related to older age, young-onset dementia refers to dementia that develops before the age of 65 years (Dementia UK, 2022). In 2016 it was described as a recent term, having replaced others such as pre-senile dementia (Rossor *et al.*, 2010; Draper and Withall, 2016) and early-onset dementia (Draper and Withall, 2016). Where early-onset dementia is still used, it must be distinguished from the early stages of dementia, and an alternative term is working-age dementia (Alzheimer's Society, 2018). The age criteria of 65 years is more “psychosocial than neurobiological” (Draper and Withall, 2016, p. 780), and developed as a criteria because of sociological rather than biological or neurological reasons, because 65 years was the expected age of retirement (Rossor *et al.*, 2010; Alzheimer Scotland, 2025). There are indications that the age of 65 as a criteria is generally accepted globally, for example the World Health Organisation define young-onset dementia using the age of 65 years (World Health Organisation, 2023), (further examples include Ikeuchi *et al.* (2020) from Japan; Novek and Menec (2023) from Canada; and Smeets *et al.* (2024) from The Netherlands, who specify 65 years in relation to young-onset dementia). However, this may be changing as age-related boundaries of employment and retirement become increasingly blurred and retirement ages globally are predicted to increase (World Economic Forum, 2023). For example, Li *et al.* (2024) defined dementia in younger people as below 70 years. It is also important to recognise that those under the age of 65 living with dementia are not a homogenous group. For example, those of a younger age are more likely to have dementia caused by genetic or metabolic factors (Rossor *et al.*, 2010), and be at a different career stage to those nearer retirement age.

1.2.1.1 Diagnosis

Young-onset dementia is a growing global concern, with “a 128% increase in new cases since 1990” (Li *et al.*, 2024, p. 1). In Scotland, it is estimated that about 3,000 people are living with young-onset dementia (NHS Health Scotland, 2013); though the actual number is likely to be greater than this due to the way diagnoses are recorded by the NHS (Carter *et al.*, 2022). Carter *et al.* (2022) estimated that 7.5% of people living with dementia in England were diagnosed before they were 65 years old.

Those with young-onset dementia often experience lengthy waits for a diagnosis (Scottish Government, 2023), exacerbated by age-related factors such as atypical presentation (Draper and Withall, 2016) and the need to be referred for diagnosis to specialists (Chiari *et al.*, 2022); with an average of four years estimated from symptom onset to diagnosis (Dementia UK, 2025; van Vliet *et al.*, 2013). This is especially so for women because of medical assumptions about women's bodies (Wiersma, Harvey and Caffery, 2022). Recognition and awareness of young-onset dementia is therefore important not only for clinicians, who are able to trigger the diagnostic process, but also for those who may have symptoms at a younger age to be aware of the possibility of dementia.

Young-onset dementia is not only a clinical diagnosis or description of symptoms, but part of identity and life experience, and therefore how (and how well) it is understood matters. Alzheimer's Disease is the most common type of young-onset dementia (Draper and Withall, 2016). Those living with young-onset dementia often experience more rapid progression than those with later onset (Draper and Withall, 2016; Mayrhofer *et al.*, 2021; Olivieri, Sarazin and Lagarde, 2022). Symptoms of young-onset dementia are not limited to cognition or memory loss but can also include depression, behaviour changes and personality changes (Draper and Withall, 2016); and behaviour and personality changes often occur earlier in younger-onset (Mayrhofer *et al.*, 2021). Societal appreciation of the needs of those with young-onset dementia is recent in comparison to those with later onset (Olivieri, Sarazin and Lagarde, 2022). Support and services for those with dementia are often not specific to those diagnosed at a younger age (Novek and Menec, 2023; Rabanal *et al.*, 2018), though younger adults need services and channels of support that are designed to meet their needs (Stamou *et al.*, 2024),

1.2.1.2 Employment

People with young-onset dementia are often still in employment (Kilty *et al.*, 2023; Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018), have family caring responsibilities (Draper and Withall, 2016) and financial commitments (Draper and Withall, 2016; Kilty *et al.*, 2023; Pison-Young *et al.*, 2011). The impact of a diagnosis during this life stage and loss of employment (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018) can necessitate the need for financial support and guidance (Kilty *et al.*, 2023), and result in barriers to wider social participation (Andrew, Phillipson and Sheridan, 2019; Karjalainen *et al.*, 2022). However, research has shown that timely diagnosis and person-centred support can improve the experiences of people with young-onset dementia, for example by supporting them to continue in employment post-diagnosis (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018). As a neurodegenerative condition, young-onset dementia is not static and as the condition progresses the impact on multiple areas of life also progresses. As life expectancy for those with young-onset dementia can be "remarkably short"

(Rhodius-Meester *et al.*, 2019, p. 727), it is imperative that diagnosis facilitates appropriate support and understanding to enhance quality of life.

1.2.2 Gendered Experience of Dementia

"Women are disproportionately affected by dementia, both directly and indirectly" (World Health Organisation, 2023). Directly, because more women than men are diagnosed with dementia; and indirectly through factors such as caring responsibilities. The early symptoms of dementia can present differently in men and women (Alzheimer's Research UK, 2022). Whilst it is not currently known why more women have dementia than men, evidence has begun to suggest a link between hormonal changes during menopause and cognitive function (Alzheimer's Research UK, 2022; Ferretti, 2023). Approximately two thirds of people living with dementia in the UK are women (Alzheimer's Research UK, 2022), and research specific to young-onset dementia found that women "bore a higher burden of dementia globally, and gender differences are still widening" (Li *et al.*, 2024, p. 1). Women with young-onset dementia decline faster than men (Ferretti, 2023).

These differences relating to sex (the biological characteristics of male and female) extend also to gender (the ways sex roles are socially constructed both externally in society and internally as part of our identities¹). The social construction of gender can often mean women are more vulnerable compared with men and age can exacerbate this (Bamford and Walker, 2012). Older women who are working have intersecting potential disadvantages and this intersectionality is worthy of further exploration (Bimrose, McMahon and Watson, 2013). Women who develop young-onset dementia are likely to be in their 50's and 60's, at an age where they may not be considered elderly but are 'older'. At an older age, they have a diagnosis that is *young-onset*. Women with young-onset dementia therefore have an intersection of disadvantage, where one aspect of their identity may disadvantage them but two or more may combine to exacerbate that disadvantage. Women may also experience disadvantage due to other aspects of their identity, such as ethnicity or sexual orientation, multiplying this intersection. While intersection has been described as "triple jeopardy" (Bamford and Walker, 2012, p. 121), it could also be experienced as multiple assets (Krekula, 2007).

Research has begun to highlight the influence of gender in the context of dementia (examples include: Tolhurst, Weicht and Runacres (2022) and Wiersma, Harvey and Caffery (2022)) but has not yet explored how young-onset dementia and gender relate to career. Workplaces and other spaces, such as home and the local community, are arenas where career is lived and experienced and where

¹ It should not be assumed that someone identifies as the same gender as their sex. This thesis uses she/her in reference to females. This does not imply an assumption that all females identify as she/her.

gender identities are enacted. Therefore, career has the potential to yield valuable insights about how gender impacts living with young-onset dementia. This increased understanding can be utilised to ensure that services for those diagnosed with young-onset dementia are appropriate for and address women's needs.

1.3 Legal and Policy Context

1.3.1 Dementia Policy in Scotland

In Scotland, everyone diagnosed with dementia is entitled to a year of post-diagnostic support, often through a link worker. This support has been a key policy in Scotland for approximately ten years (Scottish Government, 2023), though "less than half of those who are entitled to post diagnostic support receive it" (Scottish Government, 2023, p. 40). Dementia has been a health priority for the Scottish Government since 2007 (Scottish Government, 2013) and national dementia strategies have been published in 2010, 2013, 2017 and most recently in 2023. The 2013 strategy acknowledged that those with young-onset dementia have different needs, for example post-diagnostic support that is age-appropriate (Scottish Government, 2013). The 2023 strategy expanded on this, identifying the complex impact that dementia at a younger age can have on family, employment and financial circumstances (Scottish Government, 2023). Whilst the delivery plan for the 2023 strategy highlights the dementia workforce as a thematic priority (Scottish Government, 2024), career guidance, which could address needs that those with young-onset dementia have, has not been considered as part of this workforce.

The strategies have developed to recognise the need to be inclusive of individual needs and diversity, for example the 2017 strategy commits to implement recommendations related to those who have "protected characteristics" (Scottish Government, 2017, p. 23). Sex, disability, and age are all protected characteristics, because negative assumptions about these characteristics result in discrimination (both direct and indirect). Whilst the 2023 strategy acknowledges that women find gendered assumptions related to care can result "in the loss of their own identity, careers and financial security" (Scottish Government, 2023, p. 18), the impact for women when receiving a diagnosis on identity, career and finances also needs to be acknowledged and better understood. To date, none of the dementia strategies have included specific actions to meet the needs of those with young-onset dementia. Neither the key deliverables nor the thematic priorities of the current dementia strategy delivery plan specifically address the needs of those with young-onset dementia or the needs of women (Scottish Government, 2024).

1.3.2 Career Policy in Scotland

Scotland also has a national careers strategy, *Moving Forward*, published in 2020 (Scottish Government, 2020). Whilst the strategy does make a general commitment to equality and diversity, referring to disability and gender pay gap action plans, and acknowledges the ‘adult workforce’ as a target group; neither women’s needs nor the needs of disabled workers are specifically highlighted as a priority. Therefore, in Scotland, in respect of both dementia and careers strategies, the needs and experiences of women living with young-onset dementia are being neglected. There is a policy gap where the needs of those living with young-onset dementia, and especially the needs of women living with young-onset dementia, are not currently addressed.

1.3.3 The Equality Act

The UK Equality Act 2010 offers protection from discrimination related to protected characteristics. However, the legislation is limited by being civil rather than criminal. It is the responsibility of the person discriminated against to assert and realise their rights under the law, which may be much more difficult when “access to the law is very tightly constrained and there are many obstacles” (DEEP, 2016, p. 23)², compounded through the impact of cognitive impairment. There is also a lack of understanding that dementia is a disability, and therefore that those living with dementia are disabled people and have ensuing rights under the Equality Act (Egdell *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, those with dementia may not identify as disabled people (Shakespeare, Zeilig and Mittler, 2019). Alzheimer Europe published a discussion paper titled *Dementia as a Disability?*, to address potential implications of connecting dementia and disability (Alzheimer Europe, 2017) because understanding dementia as a disability was in relatively early development (Alzheimer Europe, 2017), with a lack of clarity and confidence about the rights of people living with dementia and asserting these (DEEP, 2016).

One right disabled people have under the Equality Act is to have their impairment accommodated through reasonable adjustments. The experience of impairment arising from dementia is not “a relatively stable entity” but, like many other chronic and progressive conditions, fluctuates from day to day (Bury, 1982, p. 168). Therefore, deciding what is reasonable and what adjustments are required isn’t stable or static but an ongoing process, requiring commitment and insight that may be more difficult for those living with dementia due to the nature of their impairment. Employers may also find identifying and implementing adjustments difficult for employees with dementia, because

² DEEP is an acronym for the UK Dementia Engagement and Empowerment Project

of a lack of expectation that employees will be working while living with dementia, or a lack of understanding about why support is needed pre-diagnosis (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018). Egdell *et al.* (2021) asserted that “the continuing potential of employees living with dementia and their legal rights are not consistently recognised” (Egdell *et al.*, 2021, p. 134), and through a survey and interviews with employers found that generally dementia was not a priority for them (Egdell *et al.*, 2021).

It is therefore important that policies arising from legislation go beyond upholding the law, but also broaden the scope and rights of those living with dementia. The Equality Act does not only apply to employment, but other aspects of life relevant to career such as access to transport, healthcare and voluntary opportunities. Indeed, career includes many facets of life, some but not all of which are related to employment. It is important to explore what career means and what it includes in order to understand the impact young-onset dementia has, and the following section will now discuss this.

1.4 Career

1.4.1 Defining Career

There is not a singular, universal, definition of career. In everyday language, career is usually considered synonymous with paid employment (Barnes, Bassot and Chant, 2010). There are differences in general and academic definitions and understanding of what career means (Bårdsdatter Bakke and Hooley, 2022). Whilst paid employment is often part of career, it is not the whole. Understanding career is subjective (Alexander, 2022) and therefore difficult to define. Each individual has their own idea and vision of what career means (Inkson, 2004). While the field of career development is broadening, research has traditionally focused on younger people leaving formal education and starting paid work rather than the ‘adult workforce’. If career is understood to start when paid work starts, then it can also be understood to end when paid work ends. Those living with young-onset dementia who are employed must then adjust to the diagnosis, impact of impairment and the loss (whether that be through changes in employment or the ending of employment) of career. It is therefore important that in this study career is defined broadly and inclusive of diverse experiences, including but not exclusively related to paid work. *Life and work* defines career in this study because it communicates an emphasis on life (positioned before work) along with the importance of work (whether paid or unpaid).

Women living with young-onset dementia do not often fit stereotypical and stigmatised versions of dementia; and younger women living with dementia who are working, caring and actively

participating as part of their communities do not fit stereotypical ideas about career. Career guidance and development has evolved as a research discipline from 1909, when Frank Parson's *Choosing a Vocation* was published. Career development theory has developed largely from a male perspective (Patton and McMahon, 2006b) and from a western context, particularly the USA (Leung, 2008). A further significant limitation of career theory, particularly in the context of this study, is the lack of inclusion of and attention to gendered and disabled experiences of career. Therefore, an overview of theoretical perspectives of career follows, including a focus on gender and disability.

1.4.2 Career Development Theory

1.4.2.1 Overview of Theoretical Perspectives

There are many theoretical perspectives on career (Robertson, 2019). There is “extensive theoretical diversity” (Lauder and Neary, 2020, p. 479), with over 80 theories listed on the *Career MARCR*³ website and over 400 models in use in careers counselling (Reid, 2016). Theoretical perspectives about career generally align with three “major schools of thought... person-environment correspondence theories, developmental and self-concept theories, and career decision-making and social learning theories” (Juntunen, Motl and Rozzi, 2019, p. 45). Leung (2008)'s *big five career theories* are established perspectives within each school of thought. The ‘big five’ are the theory of work adjustment (TWA) and vocational personalities in the work environment, aligned with person-environment correspondence; social cognitive career theory (SCCT), aligned with career decision making and social learning; and two self-concept theories, Gottfredson (1981) and Super (1980) (Juntunen, Motl and Rozzi, 2019; Leung, 2008).

TWA was developed by Dawis and Lofquist, who proposed that careers develop continually in cycles of satisfaction and dissatisfaction (Leung, 2008). For careers to be satisfying, personal needs and the work environment must correspond and fit together (Leung, 2008; Juntunen, Motl and Rozzi, 2019). Holland's theory of *vocational personalities in the work environment* similarly explores how “vocational interest is an expression of one's personality” (Leung, 2008, p. 118) and how satisfaction at work is stronger if personality is congruent with the environment (Holland, 1996). SCCT focuses on the interaction of three processes: self-efficacy, outcome expectations and personal goals (Leung, 2008). SCCT also focuses on younger age or “emerging adulthood” (Juntunen, Motl and Rozzi, 2019, p. 60), due to the proposition that opportunities for career change are more likely at a younger rather than older age (Lent, Brown and Hackett, 1994). As this study is focused on the experiences of

³ <https://marcr.net/marcr-for-career-professionals/career-theory/career-theories-and-theorists/> (Developed by Marc Truyens and accessed 21/09/2025)

women living with young-onset dementia, a theoretical approach that emphasises the importance of personality is problematic because of the complex impact diagnosis can have on the sense and presentation of self. Focus on environment is also problematic because, as discussed further in the *Literature Review*, employees with dementia can lose their jobs after being diagnosed and therefore environmental factors are of less significance.

Gottfredson (1981)'s *theory of circumscription and compromise* focuses on the importance of sex-role socialisation. For Gottfredson, the development of self-concept occurs through four stages in childhood and adolescence (Gottfredson, 1981), and this has particular impact on women as they eliminate and limit their career possibilities based on early socialisation (Leung, 2008). While useful to consider how gendered socialisation influences career experiences, application of the *theory of circumscription and compromise* (Gottfredson, 1981) in the context of older age and disability is limited due to the focus on younger age.

1.4.2.2 Life-Span, Life-Space Approach

Donald Super developed the Life-Career Rainbow as part of his *life-span, life-space approach to career development* (Super, 1980). Super's work since the 1950's "was the first... to address women's career development in any serious way" (Osipow and Fitzgerald, 1996, p. 251). It is accessible not only for academics and career guidance professionals but also to those not familiar with career theory. Unlike the gender-focused approaches from Astin (1984) and Farmer (1985) his approach is well known, and understands self-concept as something that evolves through life roles (Leung, 2008). It has been used in other research about the experiences of those with identities under-represented in career theory. For example, House (2004) used the *life-span, life-space approach* to explore older lesbian's experiences of career barriers related to their sexual orientation. Barclay, Stoltz and Chung (2011) integrated *life-span, life-space* with the transtheoretical model and applied this to career counselling for midlife career changers. Hunt and Rhodes (2021) explored how critical race theory could be combined with *life-span, life-space* to expand understanding of the career decisions of black students.

The life space is understood to include multiple roles over the life span. Super (1980) identified nine roles: child, student, leisurite, citizen, worker, spouse, homemaker, parent and pensioner. Individuals 'play' these roles in four 'theatres': the home, community, school and workplace (Super, 1980). Together these blend, as colours do in a rainbow, to form a career that has different and distinct roles and phases. Super (1980) recognised the importance of time and emotions with these roles, and how the connections between roles, environment and life stages combine to compose career. While age is not definitive, the approach recognises that age does influence career and

transitions within career (for example, retiring and becoming a pensioner) and does not focus solely on youth or middle age.

The *life-span, life-space approach*, particularly the Life-Career Rainbow, is therefore appropriate in the context of this study, exploring the career experiences of women living with young-onset dementia. It offers an approach that is inclusive of different elements of career, flexible in how these elements may be understood, and able to accommodate gendered and disabled experiences inclusively.

The Life-Career Rainbow

“Any job and any occupation, at any age, may prove to be an open door, a hurdle, or a dead end... Development takes place in many contexts, and it may be facilitated or guided in each of these” (Super, 1990, p. 243; 254)

Super’s approach to career recognises that careers develop in various contexts, and that paid roles and jobs can be ‘open doors’ or ‘dead ends’. This perspective is appropriate because the focus of this study is on the lives of women living with young-onset dementia, and dementia can also be a means of opening doors (for example, becoming a dementia advocate) or experiencing the end of particular elements of career (for example, loss of paid work).

Super first proposed the Life-Career Rainbow in 1976 (Super, 1980) and continued to develop his *life-span, life-space approach* until 1990 (Super, 1990). The Life-Career Rainbow, copied from the original 1980 text, is included below:

FIG. 1. The Life-Career Rainbow: Nine life roles in schematic life space.

Figure 1: The Life-Career Rainbow⁴

This approach emphasises how we identify with different roles throughout our lives (depicted as arcs within the rainbow), and experience different life stages (shown on the edge of the rainbow). The Life-Career Rainbow incorporates the span of life and the spaces we live in to offer an understanding of career (Super, 1990). The personal determinants (internal) and the situational determinants (external) influence the rainbow. Disability could be considered both a personal determinant (as part of biography) or a situational one (such as adjustments to employment) but is not explicitly articulated in the rainbow. The Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) is therefore used as a basis for conceptualising career in this study; as a way of understanding *life and work* through different roles and stages, with external and internal elements influencing how career develops. This was useful, for example, when developing the participant information sheet (Appendix Six) and other communication about the study because a focus on life roles and stages enabled an inclusive approach not solely focused on paid employment.

Limitations of the Life-Career Rainbow

Limitations of the Life-Career Rainbow are recognised. Though flexible, it is dated and therefore not as applicable to modern careers as some other approaches (Truyens, 2019). When it was published

⁴ Reprinted from A Life-Span, Life-Space Approach to Career Development; Journal of Career Development, Vol 16, Super (Donald), Pages 282-298, Copyright (1980), with permission from Elsevier.

the Life-Career Rainbow, with its definitive arc of ages and linear distinctions between roles, reflected a labour system and career patterns that were more predictable and consecutive. What may previously have been 'maintenance' of career between the ages of 45-64 is now often more cyclical throughout adult life, a development that Super acknowledged when he reflected on 'minicycles' within career and the difference between maturity related to age and career maturity (Super, 1990). Furthermore, shape of the rainbow and language used, depicting a downward trajectory of 'decline', does not positively reflect how careers continue beyond paid work and retirement. It is therefore adopted flexibly alongside the other theoretical approaches relating to gender and disability that now follow.

1.4.2.3 Career and Gender

Theoretical perspectives related to women's career development originated in the 1980's and include Astin (1984), Gottfredson (1981), Farmer (1985); and more recently Mainiero and Sullivan (2005) and Mainiero and Gibson (2017). Astin placed "considerable emphasis on the changing structure of opportunity" (Astin, 1984, p. 117) and social context, such as marriage no longer being the means through which a woman could have her need for survival met. Women's careers have a relational dynamic (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005); therefore their needs differ at different stages of their careers because personal factors remain a powerful influence (Farmer, 1985). For women, career cannot be separated from context (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005).

Women's careers are often different, and develop differently from men's (Mainiero and Gibson, 2017). The opportunities available to women differ, as do expectations of their career trajectories (Astin, 1984), and this "has been assumed because of women's role as childbearers" (Super, 1990, p. 234). Research exploring gender as a focus of career rather than an aside is needed (Mainiero and Gibson, 2017). Understanding and defining what makes a 'working life' for women is far from straightforward, because such understanding is "built in large measure on the old male breadwinner model" (Loretto, Vickerstaff and White, 2009, p. 8). Caring continues to be understood as more natural for women than men (Savitch, Abbott and Parker, 2015), and this has particular relevance in the context of young-onset dementia when women may need to be cared for as their condition progresses. The 'gender pay gap' persists, where women earn less than men and more women than men work part time (Hug, 2021; UK Parliament, 2024), and "invisible labour", such as organisation of family life, is "largely undertaken by women" (Frizzell, 2023, p. 208). In the film *Barbie* (2023), actress America Ferrara delivers a now infamous monologue that starts with the line "it is literally impossible to be a woman..." and goes on to describe the conflicts and contradictions of a woman's

career in contemporary western context, including the impossible expectation that “you have to never get old”⁵.

Feminist Approaches

Feminist approaches inform understanding of both career and dementia in this study. Feminism is in essence critical of the traditional dominance of the voices of “white, western, middle-class, heterosexual men” (England, 1994, p. 81). Understandings of gender, and therefore womanhood, are multiple and constructed (Greene and Griffiths, 2003); and socially, culturally and biologically influenced. The lack of inclusion of women, especially disabled women, within career theory is particularly striking and I identified a gap in knowledge where further insight into gendered experiences of career, and living with dementia, is needed.

Feminism has been described as ‘untidy’ (Greene and Griffiths, 2003) because it is a perspective that can be used in research as a specific or overt epistemology or, as in this study, as part of a collective approach. Feminism has formed from the historical and political need for gender equality, and in a research context this means that “absolute knowledge claims” (Nagy Hesse-Biber and Leavy, 2011, p. 23) are inappropriate; what is absolute or true for one group (such as men) is not necessarily true for others (such as women). Essentially, feminist approaches aim to make a better world for women and highlight the value of their knowledge and experiences (Nagy Hesse-Biber and Leavy, 2011), and this study aligns with this aim.

It is important that feminist research is inclusive of “variations of being a woman” (Gillberg and Jones, 2019, p. 206). For example, women who are not white, western, middle class or heterosexual; and women who are disabled. This study is focused on the experience of young-onset dementia, and this is not a neutral or objective condition. For example, healthcare in the UK has been developed from a patriarchal model. This has been inherently biased against women, for example historically understanding women’s illnesses as psychological or emotional rather than physical (Gillberg and Jones, 2019). An implicit male bias in dementia research continues, with a call for dementia policy and research to be ‘gender transformative’ (Weidner, Barbarino and Lynch, 2021). It can also be argued that “dementia has rarely been the centre of feminist attention” (Sandberg, 2023, p. 202), though the visibility of women with dementia in some contexts is encouraging. Examples include Wendy Mitchell, who authored three best-selling books about her dementia experience, and the novel (and subsequent film) *Still Alice* by Lisa Genova, depicting the main character Alice’s

⁵ Text versions of the monologue are available online, for example from Cosmopolitan magazine here: <https://www.cosmopolitan.com/entertainment/movies/a44675941/barbie-america-ferrera-monologue/> [access date 23/10/2024]

experience of young-onset dementia and the impact of this on her career and identity roles reliant on high levels of cognition (Alanbagi, 2025).

Feminist standpoint epistemology focuses on how through the sharing women's lives contributes to the goal of achieving social change and reduced oppression (Brooks, 2011). One helpful aspect of this perspective is how women, as the oppressed rather than oppressor, have developed understanding both of their own perspective and that of those who are dominant (Brooks, 2011; Gillberg and Jones, 2019). Just as women's identities are varied and diverse (Brooks, 2011), this intersectional perspective is important for dementia-related research, because those with a diagnosis do not simply identify as person living with dementia, or as a woman, or as any other singular aspect of who they are (Alzheimer Europe, 2017).

The material-discursive feminist approach (Garland-Thomson, 2011) focuses on how language and the material environment combine to construct reality. One important aspect of a material-orientated approach is the concept of fitting or misfitting in different ways (Garland-Thomson, 2011), such as living in a disabled body in an environment that varies in accessibility. A woman living with young-onset dementia may therefore 'misfit' with services designed for those of an older age, with employer's expectations about capability, and with family member's understanding of needs.

1.4.2.4 Career and Disability

As with gender, disability is not about biological difference but is socially constructed. Current understanding of disability and what this means have origin in men's experiences (such as social changes following wounded soldiers returning from World War II), evidencing that gender and disability are not distinct entities (Thomas, 1999, p. 28). Connection between dementia and disability is not straightforward, for example because dementia has not always been understood as a form of disability and not all people living with dementia identify as being disabled (Alzheimer Europe, 2017). This dementia and disability disconnect has been described as "planets spinning on different axes" (Shakespeare, Zeilig and Mittler, 2019, p. 1075).

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities (UNCRPD) is an international treaty that is relevant for those living with dementia (Alzheimer Europe, 2017). The UNCRPD is an example of how rights arising from disability can promote greater inclusivity and be a basis for positive change (Alzheimer Europe, 2017). In the UK, The Equality Act (2010) defines disability as "a physical or mental impairment that has a 'substantial' and 'long-term' negative effect on your ability to do normal daily activities" (Gov.uk, Undated, p. Unpaged). Dementia is therefore a condition where symptoms may meet the legal definition of disability (depending on how symptoms impact an

individual). However, a barrier people with dementia have in realising their rights often arises from the necessity for an individual to identify as having dementia or being disabled (Alzheimer Europe, 2017). In the context of employment, employers may find it difficult to understand when an employee with a progressive condition such as dementia meets the threshold for protection under the Equality Act, particularly if they do not yet have a diagnosis (Egdell, Stavert and McGregor, 2018). This is exacerbated by employers not always putting legislation into practice and a lack of successful discrimination claims and resultant case law (Ritchie *et al.*, 2020). So, whilst one way of defining disability, the legal definition is not the only or optimal understanding of disability available.

The Social Model of Disability

Bury (1982) described illness as 'biographical disruption' because the onset of symptoms and diagnosis is often unexpected and results in fundamental life changes in multiple ways, from day-to-day practicalities to future dreams and plans. The neurological and clinical understanding of dementia is not the only understanding, because "illness is not simply a biological matter, it is a social one" (Burr, 2019, p. 126). How we understand young-onset dementia is not simply a medical diagnosis, because our medical beliefs are situated in a cultural context that helps us make sense of the bodies we live in (Burr, 2019). The medical model of disability focuses on the biology of illness and what a person can't do because of their symptoms. In the UK, our medical and legal systems (including the legal definition of disability previously described) have developed from the medical model approach.

The biopsychosocial model emphasises the interaction and intersection of physical, mental and emotional health and human functioning (Hathcoat, Meixner and Nicholas, 2019). The social model of disability makes a distinction between impairment and disability, with impairment arising from physical differences (such as muscular pain) but disablement from the society and environment (such as stairs).

The social model understands disability as "a situation, caused by social conditions" (UPIAS and Disability Alliance, 1976, p. 3). Rather than focusing on an individual's capacity or capability the focus instead is on wider social (often ableist) assumptions, because it is society that causes disability rather than impairment (UPIAS and Disability Alliance, 1976) and therefore disability not a negative part of an individual's identity. Thomas (1999, p. 3) defined disability as "a form of social oppression involving the social imposition of restrictions of activity on people with impairments and the socially engendered undermining of their psychological or emotional well-being". This definition highlights how cultural and social understandings of disability, and how such understandings are enacted, impairs people. This study adopts the social model understanding of disability, and the language

used reflects this understanding. The social model continues to have “transformatory potential” (Thomas, 1999, p. 15) because it is established as a challenger to the medical model, and therefore underpins this study as a way of not only understanding disability but as a form of challenge to the dominant rhetoric and conceptualisation of dementia.

1.5 Background Summary

We need to better understand how the complexities of women’s careers connect with the complexities of being a woman with young-onset dementia, because current policies related to living with dementia do not differentiate between the needs of men and those of women. We need to understand if such differentiation is necessary, and ensure scarce resources are targeted where they can be most effective and meet the needs of all people living with young-onset dementia. Currently, often support and services for those with dementia are not specific to those diagnosed at a younger age (Novek and Menec, 2023; Rabanal *et al.*, 2018) or to women. It is also important that more is known about the diversity and complexity of women’s experiences beyond a comparison with men’s experiences. Those living with dementia are not homogenous, neither are all women who are living with young-onset dementia. This study will offer an original contribution to knowledge by building on research related to dementia and employment, dementia and identity, and gendered experiences of dementia to explore how women living with young-onset dementia experience life roles in the context of career.

In comparison to societal understanding of late-onset dementia, interest and focus on the experience of young-onset dementia is more recent (Olivieri, Sarazin and Lagarde, 2022). Younger adults need services and channels of support that are informed and designed around their needs (Stamou *et al.*, 2024), and research matters for informing design of such services. Research has begun to explore the experiences of those living with young-onset dementia, as the *Literature Review* details further. What hasn’t been explored explicitly is the experience of young-onset dementia in the context of career. Although more women have young-onset dementia than men, gender-related expectations and stigma also impact on services and channels of support (Bamford and Walker, 2012). We need to understand what women with young-onset dementia need to be able to promote and meet those needs. The following *Literature Review* discusses how paid employment, non-paid work and activities and disruption to the lifecycle are key areas related to career when living with young-onset dementia.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This *Literature Review* seeks to address the question *What do people living with young-onset dementia do in the context of career?* To begin, detail of the process of searching and refining the papers for inclusion in this review is described.

2.2 Literature Search and Appraisal

Reviews of literature can utilise various approaches and types of review, for example Grant and Booth (2009) described fourteen review types. The purpose of this review is to contextualise the literature relevant to what people do in the context of career; rather than aiming to identify a knowledge gap the focus is on identifying and analysing what is known relevant to the research area (Braun and Clarke, 2022a). Therefore an integrative review, “the broadest type of research review” (Whittemore and Knafl, 2005, p. 547), was adopted because this facilitated inclusion of a range of literature within an overall qualitative methodological framework, and creative synthesis of existing knowledge with related learning and fresh perspectives and ideas (Torraco, 2016a; Torraco, 2016b). Integrative reviews are well suited to an emerging topic in the literature, such as career and young-onset dementia (Torraco, 2005). An initial search was undertaken in early 2022 and a full search completed with the support of an academic librarian in December 2023 (this was updated in January 2025 and new literature incorporated into the *Discussion* chapter).

The steps in the literature review process reflected those described by Whittemore and Knafl (2005): After drafting the purpose of the review boundaries for the search were specified (as detailed in the *Search Strategy* section below). The search was then undertaken and papers further evaluated and analysed in accordance with inclusion and exclusion criteria, then presented as synthesis of ideas related to the main themes identified through the evaluation and analysis process: *Paid Employment, Non-Paid Work and Activities* and *Disruption to the Lifecycle*. Detail of the search strategy now follows.

2.2.1 Search Strategy

To identify papers for inclusion in the review, advice was sought from an academic librarian and a search strategy was drafted. Databases were identified as those appropriate for research relating to young-onset dementia and career and accessible to me through the university library. As dementia and career is an emerging area of research a range of databases were required to ensure that any relevant literature was included in the search, with a focus on the social sciences:

- Ebsco (including: Health Source, Medline, APA PsycArticles, Psychology and Behavioural Sciences Collection and SocINDEX): Enabled searches across multiple databases, including journals such as Dementia.
- Emerald Insight: Database including journals related to health and social care.
- Henry Stewart Journals (Ingenta Connect): Database focused on vocational journals supporting employment and career development.
- Science Direct: Database focused on medical-related books and journals.
- Taylor & Francis Online: Database for journal articles published through Taylor & Francis and Routledge.
- Web of Science: Database enabled multiple citation searching across academic disciplines.
- Wiley Online Library: Database including eBooks and journals related to social science and humanities.

These databases were searched using the following terms:

- Young onset dementia OR younger onset dementia OR early onset dementia
- Young onset Alzheimer's OR younger onset Alzheimer's OR early onset Alzheimer's

The 'OR' was used as a Boolean operator because preferred terms for young-onset dementia differ between contexts. 'Early onset' is the historically used phrasing for dementia that occurs before the age of 65 years old. Young-onset is the term preferred by people living with young-onset dementia and the term used by the Alzheimer's Society. Alzheimer's is a common type of dementia and was therefore included as a search term so as not to miss any papers that directly referred to Alzheimer's rather than dementia.

'AND' terms were then searched in turn:

- Career
- Work OR employment OR self-employment OR job OR occupation OR vocation

Synonyms for 'work' were included to ensure results reflected terms that described how someone earns money or formally spends their time between leaving full time education and retirement.

- Volunteering OR voluntary OR advocacy OR gig economy OR part time

These terms were included to capture alternatives to paid work that may form part of someone's career, other than in the context of earning money.

- Social media OR activities OR hobbies OR craft

Recognising that career for people with young onset dementia may encompass other informal activities, inclusion of these additional terms ensured inclusion of literature about such activities.

Careful consideration was given to the search terms used, because understanding of career as *life and work* could potentially include many multiples and variances of search terms to identify papers relevant to different aspects of career. Taking the example of 'social media', using more specific terms such as 'Facebook', 'LinkedIn' or 'Twitter' may have yielded more results but it would not have been possible to search for all possible forms of social media (for example, because platforms change names frequently and usage popularity can vary within short timescales). It was therefore decided that literature focused on social media and those with young-onset dementia would likely use social media as part of the title or abstract rather than solely reference a specific platform by name. General terms were therefore used to ensure a practical balance between volume, scope and relevance of results.

Similarly, young-onset dementia can be referred to in various ways in the literature, for example by specific diagnosis rather than the more general 'dementia' term. However, given the focus for the review within the social sciences, the decision was made to use the term 'young-onset dementia' and variances, with 'young-onset Alzheimer's' and variances (as the most common form of young-onset dementia) as a secondary term. This may have excluded relevant literature focused on a rarer type of dementias, but this is unlikely given that reference to young-onset dementia would be expected in abstracts, which were included in searches. Other terms such as 'sport' or 'family' may have yielded further results relevant to the literature review question. However, to ensure that results were manageable terms were excluded that could generate multiple irrelevant results (such as literature focused on sports injuries and young-onset dementia).

An initial search was undertaken early in 2022 and 11 papers were identified through this. As the study progressed I reflected on the process and how I could have better organised the search, and sought further guidance from the academic librarian, resulting in a repeated search in December 2023. A total of 548 papers were identified from the search in December 2023. Of these, 108 were

excluded as duplication, 170 excluded as not young-onset focused, 78 excluded as care focused, and 132 excluded from filter terms (qualitative studies, written in English, with non-medical/neurological focus); with 19 included. An issue with the Taylor & Francis search was identified, and after seeking further support from the university library this specific search was repeated and an additional five papers added (totalling 24). A further additional paper (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018) was added as a database indexing issue prevented this from appearing in searches (totalling 25). These 25 papers were added to the original 11 (totalling 36). This process is depicted in the following PRISMA⁶ diagram:

⁶ Source: Page MJ, et al. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. This work is licensed under CC BY 4.0. The template has been adapted to reflect the integrative nature of the review, such as use of the term 'papers' rather than 'reports'.

Figure 2: PRISMA Diagram

2.2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Due to the definition of career as *life and work* a broad inclusion criterion was used in this review. This needed to be balanced with practical considerations to ensure a range of the most relevant literature was included. It was therefore decided to limit the search within 10 years (after 2012) because modern context was an important consideration given the focus on career. For example, rapid technological changes have created prospects in the last decade (such as the earning potential of social media influencing) and the financial context of many households has changed significantly in that time due to factors such as the ‘financial crash’, ‘cost of living crisis’ and the pandemic. Previous literature reviews on aligned topics, for example Ritchie *et al.* (2015), evidenced the lack of research in this area prior to 2012. Exceptions were made for papers published prior to this but considered of seminal importance. These were Ohman, Nygard and Borell (2001), Kinney, Kart and

Reddecliff (2011) and Pison-Young *et al.* (2011). Ohman, Nygard and Borell (2001) was the first study to specifically explore young-onset dementia and vocation or employment. Explicitly cited in 8 of the literature review papers, it continues to have influence. Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff (2011) was considered seminal because it reported on a workplace programme, a specific intervention connecting those with young-onset dementia to a career-orientated activity and group. Robertson, Evans and Horsnell (2013) and Robertson and Evans (2015) make reference to Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff (2011)'s evaluation in their own evaluations. Pison-Young *et al.* (2011) was one of the first studies in the UK to identify the loss of employment as being significant to those with young-onset dementia. It is possible that other papers with continuing importance and relevance older than 2012 were excluded from the review, however none were identified when reviewing references of the included papers.

The decision was made to focus on qualitative papers. As an exploratory study, it was important that this review yield insights to address the review question of *what people living with young-onset dementia do in the context of career*. This included exploration of why and how those living with young-onset dementia undertake roles and activities that are part of their careers, to support understanding of what enablers and barriers they may experience. When searching databases it was not possible to specify qualitative or quantitative approaches, so quantitative papers were included in search results and screened. Papers with a quantitative focus tended to be those from biomedical science, focused on drug interventions or symptomology, which were not the focus of this review. No quantitative papers were identified as exceptions to the inclusion criteria during screening, however some papers with a mixed approach were included in this review when the findings and focus addressed the review question. An example of such a paper was Gerritzen, McDermott and Orrell (2023), which used both qualitative and quantitative methods to explore online peer support for those with young-onset dementia.

The focus in this review is on experiences related to having dementia at a younger age. However, participant composition in the literature was often of an age range that included those with both younger and older onset. For example, Bartlett (2014, p. 1296) stated that the participants "were aged 53 to 74 years". Broders and Wiersma (2020) discussed how it had been necessary to take a flexible approach to participant age; one of their participants experienced symptoms before the age of 65 but wasn't diagnosed until after this age, and five of their participants had been diagnosed with young-onset dementia but had now aged beyond 65 years. Nygard *et al.* (2023)'s inclusion criteria included to have been in employment within the previous six months and aged 50-75 years old, reflecting that age and retirement are not as clearly connected as they have been in the past. Scott *et al.* (2023) stated that all ten participants were living with young-onset dementia, but were

aged between 50-74 years old. A flexible approach was therefore taken to participant age in this review, to ensure that relevant literature was not excluded if not all (or most) participants were aged under 65 years. If people with young-onset dementia participated, then the paper was eligible for inclusion.

The inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review are summarised in the following table:

Inclusion	Exclusion
Published since 2012 (within the last 10 years)	Published before 2012 (exceptions were made for three papers due to seminal importance)
Qualitative methodology	Quantitative methodology
Participants living with young-onset dementia	Participants not living with young-onset dementia
Written in English	Written in a language other than English

Table 1: Literature Search Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

While papers did reflect a range of countries (Australia, Canada, Denmark, Finland, France, Ireland, Japan, the Netherlands, Norway, the USA and the UK) a limitation of the review was that papers needed to be written in English. While this may have excluded research from other countries and cultures, it was a necessary limitation because I am fluent in English but not any other language. The majority of papers utilised a form of interview as the method of data collection, though some did use focus groups and other methods, such as photovoice. Most papers included participants with different types of dementia, or did not specify the dementia diagnosis participants had.

2.2.3 Critical Appraisal

In order to critically appraise the literature, several critical appraisal tools were reviewed and the CASP (Critical Appraisal Skills Programme) qualitative checklist (CASP, 2018) was selected. This tool was considered accessible and straightforward, and enabled critical appraisal of the literature appropriate for the qualitative paradigm, within which there is debate about how (and if) literature should be appraised (Dixon-Woods *et al.*, 2004). A CASP checklist was completed for each paper included in the review. The CASP checklist prompts reflection on 10 questions within three categories: Are the results valid? What are the results? Will the results help locally? (CASP, 2018). As no papers were to be excluded based on quality, a basic scoring system of zero for no, two for yes

and one for partially yes or unable to tell was devised (20 was the maximum score). Totals for each paper ranged from five to 18. The average score was 15. Scores were compared and discussed with my lead supervisor initially, to ensure appropriate evaluation and assessment of papers was in place as I continued the appraisal process. A table detailing the author, title, date, journal and CASP scores for all papers included in this review can be found in Appendix One.

2.3 What Do People Living with Young-Onset Dementia Do in the Context of Career?

This chapter now continues with the literature review, organised through three perspectives addressing the literature review question: *What do people living with young-onset dementia do in the context of career?* This can be summarised as roles that are both paid and unpaid, personal (such as family roles) and roles that relate to activities that are important or enjoyable, such as advocacy activities. The three themes of the literature review were developed following the reading and analysis of the literature through a lens of understanding career as *life and work: Paid Employment, Non-Paid Work and Activities, and Disruption to the Lifecycle*.

2.3.1 Paid Employment

2.3.1.1 Importance of Work

Whilst work can refer to paid employment and other forms of work such as volunteer roles, this section focuses on work that is paid. Those living with dementia are likely to find it increasingly difficult to navigate an unstable world of work not designed for their needs, as flexibility and adaptability become increasingly necessary and lifelong jobs no longer exist (Jones, 2024). However, work roles were found to be “integral” to the stories of people living with young-onset dementia (Chaplin and Davidson, 2014, p. 149), and important not only because of needs related to finances but needs related to identity (Rabanal *et al.*, 2018) and socialisation (Chaplin and Davidson, 2014) too. Continuing paid employment after a diagnosis can challenge stereotypical expectations about the lives and capabilities of those living with dementia (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018). Working in paid roles was therefore an important aspect of *what people living with young-onset dementia do*.

As both pension ages and the cost of living have risen, increasing numbers of people will need to work for longer and therefore develop dementia during their working life (Ritchie *et al.*, 2015).

However, the connection between work and well-being was complex. Working presented challenges but positive experiences contributed to well-being. However, well-being was also reduced by negative aspects of work such as a lack of support in the workplace (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018). Three important aspects of being an employee with young-onset dementia were symptoms at work, support at work, and leaving work.

2.3.1.2 Symptoms at Work

Several papers described how symptoms were first experienced or noticed within the context of employment (Evans, 2019; Johannessen *et al.*, 2018; Ohman, Nygard and Borell, 2001; Roach and Drummond, 2014), evidencing an important connection between dementia and work.

Understanding of dementia symptoms varied in the literature, for example the participant in Robinson, Giorgi and Ekman (2012, p. 224)'s research described "feelings of incongruity" between what she was experiencing and the external messages she was trying to interpret and understand. Given the impact of dementia on cognition, it can be difficult for those living with the condition to understand and articulate their symptoms. Employees are required to interact with colleagues, perform their work tasks and adhere to workplace norms, and symptoms can present challenges with fulfilling these requirements. They are not only experiencing and seeking to make sense of their symptoms within, but also 'without' (Robinson, Giorgi and Ekman, 2012), and the workplace is an area where congruence between internal and external perspectives matters.

Evans (2019) used a qualitative life-course paradigm in his Australian study with ten participants living with dementia, exploring the experience of dementia and employment from the time of initial symptom onset to leaving work (both of which were found to be difficult to define). The participants experienced problems emerging at work and negative experiences of leaving work (Evans, 2019). Evans (2019) used a similar approach to that of Nygard *et al.* (2023) and Ritchie, Tolson and Danson (2018). Evans (2019) used an 'insider/ outsider' perspective, participants offered an 'insider' perspective whilst their spouses offered an 'outsider' perspective. Approaches using multiple perspectives suggested that the 'insider' perspective required additional input to be fully understood, which may not be possible for those living with dementia to absorb. This has particular relevance for employment, where understanding feedback, instructions or advice is often important.

Along with memory difficulties, symptom experience included "tiredness, increased sensitivity in stressful situations, difficulty in reading and writing, and in concentrating and initiating tasks" (Ohman, Nygard and Borell, 2001, pp. 37-38), "feeling irritated, anxious, or fatigued" (Issakainen *et al.*, 2023, p. 8), and "loss of ability across many domains" (van Vliet *et al.*, 2017, p. 1889). Everyday

tasks often required more effort (Wawrziczny *et al.*, 2016). Issakainen *et al.* (2023) described the difficulties and challenges at work, the distress these difficulties caused, and the negative impact on participants' dignity. The inconsistency (Ritchie *et al.*, 2015), nature (Ohman, Nygard and Borell, 2001) and unpredictability (Ashworth, 2020) of symptoms were difficult to navigate at work.

Working with Dementia

Ohman, Nygard and Borell (2001)'s research continues to have influence as it was the first to specifically explore employment issues in the context of dementia. They interviewed employees with dementia and representatives from their workplaces. Ritchie, Tolson and Danson (2018) undertook a similar case study approach, interviewing employees with dementia, representatives from their workplace and a relative. Employees with dementia only wanted to continue working if they could do so competently (Ohman, Nygard and Borell, 2001), and continuing to work was felt to be helping manage symptoms (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018). However, differing perspectives of competence were presented from the participants and their workplace respondents. The workplace respondents reported that they, and participants' teams and colleagues, were wanting and willing to offer support. It was also found that colleagues felt irritation, conflict and guilt (Ohman, Nygard and Borell, 2001) and line managers and colleagues were impacted emotionally through their efforts to support their colleague with dementia (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018). Ritchie, Tolson and Danson (2018) found that employers had good intentions, but a lack of knowledge about how to translate this into employment policy and practice. A distinction between competence and contribution was therefore suggested and was complex; perspectives of the person with dementia about their contribution at work and competence in their role may not be shared by their colleagues and managers.

Diagnosis and Work

Ritchie, Tolson and Danson (2018) highlighted how delays in diagnosis of dementia had a negative impact on employment. The longer diagnosis took, the higher the likelihood that the employee had needed to leave employment or take sick leave (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018). Diagnosis was important so that the relationship between work performance and dementia could be understood. Symptoms of dementia such as memory loss or confusion could be attributed to a lack of focus, laziness or lack of ability rather than as part of the experience of cognitive impairment. Broders and Wiersma (2020) found that the lengthy diagnosis process was distressing, and for the women they interviewed symptoms were often attributed to the menopause or mental health conditions. Nygard *et al.* (2023, p. 9) also described the negative impact of lengthy diagnosis for their participants, with one of their female participants experiencing a "negative spiral with devastating consequences

lasting well after work had ended". By contrast, another female participant received her diagnosis earlier, before her symptoms negatively impacted her work, and this enabled a focus on how she could continue working (Nygard *et al.*, 2023). Diagnosis is therefore important in respect of employment, but the timeliness of diagnosis is also important. It was aptly described as a "a double-edged trigger" (Nygard *et al.*, 2023, p. 9) because diagnosis triggered very different consequences, both positive and negative. Kilty *et al.* (2023) interviewed 10 people living with young-onset dementia, and 12 spouses and children, to better understand the impact of developing young-onset dementia while working on the family. The issue of timely diagnosis was discussed because not having a diagnosis can be a barrier to accessing support such as referrals to occupational health, as well as understanding from others at work (Kilty *et al.*, 2023).

Workplace culture is significant here. Workplaces need to be an environment where vulnerability in whatever form is not uncomfortable or unsafe, and older workers in particular are enabled and supported (Evans, 2019; Centre for Ageing Better, 2021b). If the workplace doesn't feel like a safe space due to the potential for negativity and conflict to occur at work (Evans, 2019), employees with young-onset dementia won't know or understand how disclosing their diagnosis will help or hinder their continuing employment. Experiences with managers and colleagues could be negative and emotionally traumatic (Ikeuchi *et al.*, 2020), but also positive through sensitive and patient responses to challenges (Karjalainen *et al.*, 2022). When responses from others were positive, this helped those with young-onset dementia to accept the diagnosis (Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac, 2014).

2.3.1.3 Support at Work

Adjustments

People living with dementia do continue in paid employment. However the comparative rarity of dementia made it challenging for employers to be supportive, particularly when formal diagnosis was often lengthy (Nygard *et al.*, 2023) or not available at the time when employees required support (Kilty *et al.*, 2023). Whilst diagnosis is not required to be considered a disabled person under the law, a diagnosis can often make a person's legal status as a disabled person clearer, and this is important for realising legal rights. The Equality Act (2010) stipulates that employers need to make 'reasonable adjustments' to ensure disabled employees can undertake their work. The UNCRPD (United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities) specifies that "reasonable accommodation is provided to persons with disabilities in the workplace" (United Nations, 2006, pp. Article 27, (1)i). Such adjustments were discussed by Ikeuchi *et al.* (2020), Karjalainen *et al.* (2022),

Kilty *et al.* (2023) Nygard *et al.* (2023), Ohman, Nygard and Borell (2001) and Ritchie, Tolson and Danson (2018).

Even with a diagnosis, understanding the possibilities for adjustments and rehabilitation was problematic (Ohman, Nygard and Borell, 2001). The legal definition of adjustments is contextual, dependent on what is deemed 'reasonable' in individual circumstances, and larger employers may have greater flexibility and resources to facilitate adjustments (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018). Ikeuchi *et al.* (2020) defined adjustments as a form of support utilising an employee's capabilities and motivation to maintain work tasks and social participation. Helpful adjustments for those with dementia included workplace accessibility, flexible hours and being able to work remotely (Karjalainen *et al.*, 2022).

Karjalainen *et al.* (2022)'s research discussed the complex nature of adjustments, for example the loss of income from reduced hours and how technology can be an enabler but also a barrier to continued employment. Marashi *et al.* (2021) specifically explored the use of technology at work. Seven participants with young-onset dementia (and two caregivers) were interviewed about the features of technology that positively and negatively impacted usability. An insight gained from this research is that everyday technology was not designed for people living with dementia, yet familiarity of such design is a critical feature of usability (Marashi *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, employees with dementia may need technology to be adapted to make it more accessible, but introducing unfamiliar interfaces or software may reduce usability. Technology, an increasingly integral part of many work roles, can therefore be situated between the proverbial rock and hard place, between enablement and disablement.

Chaplin and Davidson (2014)'s research was amongst the first to explore young-onset dementia and paid work in the UK. None of their five participants, four men and one woman, were offered reasonable adjustments. However, two of the five were continuing their employment on a 'semi-retired' basis and Chaplin and Davidson (2014, p. 158) suggested that this may have been possible due to the greater "locus of control" those two participants had in their employment. It was concerning to note that the status level of employment may therefore be an important factor, particularly as discrimination, oppression and injustice do not occur by accident (Hooley, Sultana and Thomsen, 2021). Chaplin and Davidson (2014, p. 159)'s striking conclusion was that if their findings were reflective of wider practice then "support for workers who have a dementia is, at best, poor and at worst unlawful".

Adjustments that were unhelpful were reported in the literature. Examples included managers and colleagues observing an employee with dementia covertly (Chaplin and Davidson, 2014) and too much support being provided, undermining autonomy (Ikeuchi *et al.*, 2020). It was suggested that employees with young-onset dementia should be involved in addressing their own work needs (Issakainen *et al.*, 2023), benefitting both the employee and employer (Chaplin and Davidson, 2014). Better investigation when work performance changed or declined might have helped identify dementia earlier (Evans, 2019), which links to the importance of employers proactively supporting employees (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018), rather than relying on a diagnosis before considering adjustments.

Workplace Perceptions

Whilst diagnosis was important to offer understanding of symptoms and access to adjustments, the negative influence of stereotypes impacted the expectations of employers and colleagues (Nygard *et al.*, 2023). Using the UNCRPD and data from Canada, Finland and Sweden, Karjalainen *et al.* (2022) aimed to discover what kinds of workplaces and adjustments were helpful to those working and living with dementia. Along with technology, their findings highlighted the importance of the workplace environment, including the wider work community and colleagues. Nygard *et al.* (2023)'s research from Sweden noted that a country's legislation and implementation of the UNCRPD would greatly affect those who develop dementia while in employment. In their longitudinal case study research, Nygard *et al.* (2023) interviewed five participants living with dementia and those they invited to participate as significant others. The longitudinal approach enabled the changing feelings and insights of participants to be recorded. One participant, initially happy with how her employer treated her, later developed a more negative perspective as she considered how the employer's stereotypical view of dementia had escalated her departure from work (Nygard *et al.*, 2023).

Gradual decline of cognitive function can result in a lack of definition as to when an employee needs support or realises they need support, especially because the onset of symptoms is usually not definitive (Evans, 2019). It may not be possible to simplify existing tasks for employees with dementia or for new tasks to be learned effectively (Ohman, Nygard and Borell, 2001). Opportunities for adjustments, particularly within the realms of 'reasonable' and the interpretations of this in different contexts, are limited not only by the nature of young-onset dementia but the low expectations of employers about an employee's continued employment (Evans, 2019) and consideration of their future employment (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018).

The employee with young-onset dementia could be perceived as a “poor worker” and this had impact on colleague dynamics (Evans, 2019, p. 268). Co-workers were reported as having negative reactions to colleagues with dementia (Evans, 2019), and diminished capacity was observed (Ohman, Nygard and Borell, 2001). The progress of dementia, with problems at work becoming more visible over time, increased a tension between understanding and trusting oneself (Ohman, Nygard and Borell, 2001) and disclosing and explaining to others. There was suggestion of workplaces being potentially hostile, such as when symptoms of dementia were “interpreted as signs of laziness, incompetence or alcoholism”.

Ikeuchi *et al.* (2020) asserted to be the first to explore young-onset dementia and employment in Japan. While some further detail about the Japanese context would have been beneficial to better understand the findings (for example, the role of co-ordinators within prefectures and networks), they emphasised the critical role of support for those with young-onset dementia; it was not only needed but needed appropriately because excessive support resulted in feelings of helplessness (Ikeuchi *et al.*, 2020).

Ritchie *et al.* (2015) identified that those with dementia need support in employment but there was a lack of awareness and knowledge from employers about appropriate support (Ritchie *et al.*, 2015), and it can be stressful for colleagues to provide ongoing support to employees with dementia (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018). Difficulties emerged managing changing working relationships (Evans, 2019); such as stress and emotional impact when supporting a colleague with dementia (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018). Responses and communication from colleagues was important (Issakainen *et al.*, 2023) as was the need to be treated “the same” (Ashworth, 2020, p. 1655). This highlights the need to support not only employee with dementia but their team and colleagues too.

2.3.1.4 Leaving Work

Sick Leave and Reduced Socialisation

Continuing to work was important for continued social inclusion. Johannessen *et al.* (2018)’s longitudinal research focused on the experiences of those living alone with young-onset dementia. Through interviews with 10 participants they found that loss of employment exacerbated social isolation. The nine participants who were working during the diagnosis process were all “proposed a full or part-time sick leave or retirement” and this started “social retraction” (Johannessen *et al.*, 2018, p. 4). This reduction in social contact, perpetuated by dementia symptoms such as not being able to engage in small talk, related to disruption to social norms. Having a supportive network was important (Nygard *et al.*, 2023), but relationships with others were more difficult and exhausting to

maintain when not at work. One participant from Nygard *et al.* (2023)'s research continued working despite recommended sick leave because she felt the benefits of the social community were greater than the challenges of continuing to work.

Sick leave was a step towards leaving employment rather than a facilitator of adjusted work. Broders and Wiersma (2020); Chaplin and Davidson (2014); Ohman, Nygard and Borell (2001); Nygard *et al.* (2023); Ritchie, Tolson and Danson (2018), discussed how sick leave was often necessary for participants before diagnosis could be obtained and precipitated leaving employment. When taking sick leave, many employees were not entitled to full pay or only entitled for a limited time, and this could exacerbate financial pressures when adjusting to diagnosis. Pleasure from work, for example through meaningful activity or social interaction, also stopped during sick leave. Sick leave may therefore be helpful for alleviating the stress and challenges experienced at work, but it does not support continued employment, which many employees living with dementia need and want.

Employment Ends

Employers didn't have previous experience of supporting employees with dementia, and in several cases felt that early retirement was preferable to continued working whilst the employee with dementia felt they could continue (Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018). Support was needed for continuing employment or transitioning to other roles after employment ended (Ikeuchi *et al.*, 2020). Ritchie, Tolson and Danson (2018) asserted that support for the transition of leaving work is as important as support whilst at work. People living with dementia benefit from ongoing support to continue their careers, including after paid work ends.

For some, leaving work was experienced as a relief (Evans, 2019); a "being let off" (Ohman, Nygard and Borell, 2001, p. 39). For others, stopping work was not a choice and they would rather have been enabled to continue working through reasonable adjustments or additional support (Kilty *et al.*, 2023). Leaving was a painful loss (Rabanal *et al.*, 2018), stressful (Roach and Drummond, 2014; Evans, 2019), and disappointing (Evans, 2019); made all the more difficult by lack of opportunities to say goodbye to colleagues (Chaplin and Davidson, 2014) or "have a 'proper retirement'" (Ashworth, 2020, p. 1656). Evans (2019) found only one of their 10 participants with young-onset dementia left their workplace with recognition and celebration. They described how some participants experienced disappointment and frustration after leaving paid work due to their lack of opportunity to actively and meaningfully engage. Some felt abandoned by their employer (Chaplin and Davidson, 2014), and found losing their job resulted in loss of confidence (Ikeuchi *et al.*, 2020). Being forced to

stop work was experienced as a significant loss both in respect of finances and identity (Rabanal *et al.*, 2018).

Robertson and Evans (2015, p. 2332) and Evans (2019, p. 264) theorised a “double insult” to identity when loss of employment intersected with diagnosis of dementia. Their choice of words is apt given the devastating nature of the diagnosis compounded by further loss when needing to leave work, either because of symptoms or through (not necessarily the employee’s) choice. Issakainen *et al.* (2023) undertook research with 12 participants living with dementia in Finland using focus groups with a combined social, psychological and legal approach. They drew “on the concept of relational autonomy to explore how working-age people living [with] dementia seek to influence their lives” (Issakainen *et al.*, 2023, p. 1). The importance of the psychosocial conditions of work and the disabling nature of inflexible work structures were highlighted. Losing employment resulted in losing daily routines and social contacts (Issakainen *et al.*, 2023). The participants were diagnosed with young-onset dementia while still working and were retired at the time of the focus groups, so offered a post-employment perspective. The participants in Pison-Young *et al.* (2011)’s research were not working full time when they were diagnosed. Whilst they found that employment was not a particular concern for their participants; being busy, enjoyment and being active were important (Pison-Young *et al.*, 2011). In contrast, Ashworth (2020)’s research also included participants who were no longer in employment. She found that even though no longer working, occupational status continued to influence plans for the future and participants’ sense of self.

Financial Impact

Leaving work had financial and practical implications for people living with young-onset dementia. Issakainen *et al.* (2023); Kilty *et al.* (2023); Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff (2011); Ritchie *et al.* (2015); and Robertson and Evans (2015) all addressed the financial impact of an early exit from work. The lack of appropriate guidance and counselling, including financial guidance, after diagnosis was noted (Issakainen *et al.*, 2023). Busted, Nielsen and Birkelund (2020) and Kilty *et al.* (2023) highlighted the financial consequences of stopping work for the wider family. No longer financially contributing to the household was experienced as a burden for those with young-onset dementia (Busted, Nielsen and Birkelund, 2020). As well as reduced earnings, additional costs due to living with dementia and the stress of navigating support systems and financial concerns were difficult (Kilty *et al.*, 2023). An example of this is additional transport expenses when the person living with dementia can no longer drive (Scott *et al.*, 2023). The stressful and difficult process of proving an invisible impairment to obtain financial support such as welfare benefits was described (Broders and Wiersma, 2020), with

potential for families to be left needing to cope with significant financial insecurity (Nygard *et al.*, 2023).

2.3.2 Non-paid Work and Activities

2.3.2.1 Work programmes

Several papers focused on work programmes (voluntary work schemes designed for those living with dementia) for people with young-onset dementia. Three papers in the review (Robertson, Evans and Horsnell, 2013; Robertson and Evans, 2015; Evans, Robertson and Candy, 2016) originated from a workplace programme in Australia called *Side By Side*. Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff (2011) reported on *GOOTH*, a programme based at a local zoo.

Those with young-onset dementia participating in *Side By Side* experienced a “positive impact on well-being, most apparent in the areas of self-esteem, self-worth and confidence” (Robertson and Evans, 2015, p. 2335). *Side by Side* was “initiated to assess the feasibility of supported workplace engagement for people with young-onset dementia” (Robertson, Evans and Horsnell, 2013, p. 666). For one day per week, participants undertook work at a hardware store and were assigned a workplace ‘buddy’ to support them. Benefits to participants included socialising with others with dementia and being able to make a contribution they felt was meaningful (Robertson, Evans and Horsnell, 2013). Robertson and Evans (2015) used deductive content analysis to analyse data within a framework of four positive outcomes that had been nominated by participants in the programme: improved well-being, worthwhile activities, contributing to society, and socialising. Photography, through photovoice, was included in the *Side by Side* project at a later stage and detailed in Evans, Robertson and Candy (2016).

Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff (2011) evaluated a workplace programme based at a zoo in the USA. The Get Out Of The House (*GOOTH*) programme initially involved ten male participants, who were transported to the zoo by limousine and undertook two hours of work at the zoo before lunch and an afternoon ‘experience’, such as behind the scenes tours (Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff, 2011). They interviewed six participants and held a focus group with their wives. As in *Side by Side*, the participants in *GOOTH* also benefited from the opportunity to socialise and bond with other men who had dementia (Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff, 2011). Efforts to introduce women to *GOOTH* were not successful because the group was initially formed with men, so it was difficult to alter this established dynamic (Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff, 2011). As both programmes highlighted the benefits of socialisation and being able to undertake activities with meaning or purpose for

participants, it could be argued that it was the opportunity provided, rather than the structure of the programmes, that facilitated the benefits.

Workplace programmes and activities were found to be important for engagement with the world and provided important opportunities to socialise with others living with young-onset dementia. Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff (2011) described the social aspects of work as providing 'normalcy'. Normalcy is about maintaining "the state of being typical, usual or expected"⁷. The *GOOTH* programme provided normalcy for the men participating, men who because of dementia had needed to give up many of the activities they had previously enjoyed (Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff, 2011). It can be important for those living with dementia to present a normality to the world (Robinson, Giorgi and Ekman, 2012) and workplace programmes may be a way of doing so. However, this is complex because dementia may not feel normal to those living with the diagnosis. A participant in Busted, Nielsen and Birkelund (2020, p. 4)'s research said: "I want to live as normal as possible. I don't want to see others with dementia". Therefore, 'seeing' others with dementia may undermine normalcy due to internalised negative stigma associated with dementia, but *GOOTH* is an example of how socialising with others with dementia can be positive and help maintain normalcy.

Another key benefit claimed from the workplace programmes was the opportunity to make a positive contribution in a work context (Robertson, Evans and Horsnell, 2013). People living with young-onset dementia have often lost their jobs but not the willingness and ability to contribute through work, and workplace programmes were designed to facilitate continued professional contributions. There are limited alternatives to use professional skills at a life stage where working is a principal means of "social status, self-esteem and self-worth" (Robertson, Evans and Horsnell, 2013, p. 667), especially because services for those with dementia are often designed for older people. Alternative ways to make a positive contribution included being with family (Ohman, Nygard and Borell, 2001), hobbies (Pipon-Young *et al.*, 2011), campaigning (Bartlett, 2014), advocacy (Broders and Wiersma, 2020), online peer support (Gerritzen, McDermott and Orrell, 2023), housekeeping and gardening (Ohman, Nygard and Borell, 2001; van Vliet *et al.*, 2017) and social media (Craig and Strivens, 2016; Talbot *et al.*, 2020a; Talbot *et al.*, 2021). However, the distinction with the work programmes was the structure they offered, the opportunity to meet and socialise with other younger people with dementia, and use professional skills. Limitations of the work programmes included the relatively small number of participants that could be accommodated (Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff, 2011), and insecure funding (Robertson, Evans and Horsnell, 2013).

⁷ From Oxford Languages via Google

2.3.2.2 Online Links

Chaplin and Davidson (2014) suggested that hobbies as an activity were part of adjusting to retirement or unemployment and a conduit for future positivity. After leaving or reducing paid work all five participants in Chaplin and Davidson (2014, p. 156)'s research had resumed old hobbies or started new ones. Issakainen *et al.* (2023) highlighted that when work ends, so do the daily routines and the social context it provides. Those with dementia maintaining a sense of strength after diagnosis were those engaged in activities, who had peer support from others with a diagnosis and who had "a sense of purpose" (Wiersma, Harvey and Caffery, 2022, p. 11). Work enables wider societal contribution (Evans, 2019) and socialisation, as the workplace is often a distinct and important social group. Social media provides an interesting opportunity for people with young-onset dementia to find ways of renegotiating career through virtual spaces, and have perhaps utilised such spaces to meet needs that work no longer does; because of the resulting decline of social networks (Robertson and Evans, 2015) and experiences of isolation and loneliness (Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac, 2014; van Vliet *et al.*, 2017).

Social media refers to virtual spaces where users publish content that this is publicly available. Social media offered the potential for wider social networks (Talbot *et al.*, 2021), and was used by people with young-onset dementia for campaigning, advocacy, information gaining and sharing, to connect with others and share support (Craig and Strivens, 2016; Talbot *et al.*, 2020a). Kohl *et al.* (2024a)'s mixed methods study explored social media use in the context of dementia, specifically comparing the use of social media between older (above the age of 65 years) and younger people with dementia. They found that younger people with dementia used social media more frequently than older people, and used more forms of social media (except LinkedIn) (Kohl *et al.*, 2024a). Younger people's use of social media was advocacy focused, whereas for older people use was more about the dementia journey (Kohl *et al.*, 2024a). Kohl *et al.* (2024a)'s research involved a survey and semi structured interviews. Of the 143 survey responses, 88 were male and 54 female, 66 were non-users of social media and only 27 were under the age of 65. A further limitation was participant data did not distinguish between older people with dementia and those who are now older but developed dementia at a younger age. However, this research indicated the potential for social media to be a forum of advocacy, raising awareness and challenging stereotypical views about dementia (Kohl *et al.*, 2024a).

Twitter⁸ and Facebook™

Talbot *et al.* (2020a) and Talbot *et al.* (2021) focused on the use of Twitter by people with dementia. Of the 30 users that Talbot *et al.* (2020a, p. 969) identified, 17 were male and 12 female, with 1 unknown; leading them to highlight the male majority. Talbot *et al.* (2021) later interviewed 11 younger people with dementia (eight men and three women) and used thematic analysis to better understand motivations for using Twitter and associated challenges. The four themes generated from the data all related to identity and they found that Twitter provided a community and space for social connections (Talbot *et al.*, 2021). Using Twitter was a form of meaningful activity and supported maintenance of a positive identity, contributing to self-worth in a similar way to work (Talbot *et al.*, 2021). As younger generations age, an increasing number of people diagnosed with young-onset dementia will be 'tech savvy' and therefore social media is likely to become part of the experience of living with the disease (Talbot *et al.*, 2020a).

Social media has potential to be a space where those living with young-onset dementia can be respected as experts by lived experience (Craig and Strivens, 2016). Facebook™ was a popular social media platform (Kohl *et al.*, 2024a), though Craig and Strivens (2016)'s paper was the only one to focus on Facebook™ use. However, significant quality issues were identified with Craig and Strivens (2016)'s paper as it was based on the authors' experiences as creators and facilitators of a young-onset dementia support group page and took the form of an article rather than research. The page was considered a forum of engagement and a network where people with young-onset dementia could share their voices (Craig and Strivens, 2016).

Meeting Online

Following the pandemic, when restrictions on leaving home and meeting others were enforced, online platforms were commonly used to connect with others. Gerritzen, McDermott and Orrell (2023) collected data during the pandemic, using a mixed-methods survey to explore what platforms were used for online peer support, why they were used (or not used) and how positive benefits could be maximised. Their research indicates that online peer support was of particular importance after receiving a diagnosis. It helped reduce isolation and provided a safe space where those with a diagnosis could connect with others who understood them (Gerritzen, McDermott and Orrell, 2023). Respondents to their survey shared about experiences using platforms such as Twitter and Facebook™, as well as meeting platforms such as Zoom. The variety of platforms was considered a

⁸ Twitter became known as X in 2023. However, as it is still commonly referred to and known as Twitter and the related research took place before the rebranding, the platform is referred to as Twitter in this thesis.

positive aspect of online support, because different needs could be accommodated. Most of the survey respondents were signposted to sources of online support by dementia organisations, which contrasted with negative and unempathetic experiences with healthcare staff during diagnosis and post-diagnosis (Gerritzen, McDermott and Orrell, 2023). A limitation of this survey was a small sample size of 69 respondents, of which 47 were 'non-users' of online peer support.

While Gerritzen, McDermott and Orrell (2023, p. 2390) found that online support was a "lifeline", having a facilitator to support meetings and ensure a safe space was important. van Vliet *et al.* (2017) also found that participants needed to feel safe and part of this was receiving understanding and acceptance from others. van Vliet *et al.* (2017) referred to two requirements for remaining active, having support externally and feeling secure. Scott *et al.* (2023) discussed the importance of being understood by others in their research focused on driving cessation. They described interviews as highly emotional and acknowledged that whilst there were opportunities to talk about their experiences, there were far fewer opportunities to share such experiences (Scott *et al.*, 2023). Being active both online and offline may therefore both need to include others who have young-onset dementia, and being supported to engage in ways that feel safe.

2.3.2.3 Social Connections with Others

Both external support and feeling secure were suggested to be necessary requirements for staying active (van Vliet *et al.*, 2017). Activities related to leisure or recreation were key for those with young-onset dementia, enabling them to continue feeling useful. This was especially important in the early stages of dementia (van Vliet *et al.*, 2017). People with young-onset dementia value having a sense of usefulness (van Vliet *et al.*, 2017; Rabanal *et al.*, 2018). Though van Vliet *et al.* (2017) did not define usefulness, their theme *Staying Engaged* describes the importance of social involvement (including being useful to others) and being busy with activities that have a function or purpose (including activities such as sport or leisure for the purpose of enjoyment) (van Vliet *et al.*, 2017). Their findings suggested that needing a sense of usefulness may decrease over time, while needing pleasure from activities may increase.

Rabanal *et al.* (2018) highlighted the positive attitudes of their participants and how they linked keeping active to maintenance of well-being. van Vliet *et al.* (2017) reported that their participants with young-onset dementia felt being engaged in daily life was important but the caregivers spoke of passivity and apathy towards engagement. The authors suggested this may be due to participants not being aware or having insight into their dementia (van Vliet *et al.*, 2017), but this could also perhaps be attributed to the influence of the focus group guide or those living with dementia

desiring to please caregivers. The views of those living with dementia are not necessarily the same as those supporting them or providing care. Tilki *et al.* (2023) focused on sport and exercise for those living with young-onset dementia and they also reported that those with dementia were initially somewhat reluctant to participate but then all (except one) did. This may suggest the importance of doing activities together rather than individually, or may perhaps reflect weariness following “endless” encouragement and discussion (Tilki *et al.*, 2023, p. 130). Tilki *et al.* (2023) was the only paper identified that focused on sport or exercise, so was included in this review despite limitations identified through quality appraisal. Such limitations included possible author conflicts of interest and a lack of appraisal or feedback from those living with young-onset dementia. The authors emphasised the importance of peer support (Tilki *et al.*, 2023). The project duration was one year, and in that time social connections were made and maintained, and those with young-onset dementia seemed less stressed and more positive (Tilki *et al.*, 2023). van Vliet *et al.* (2017) and Tilki *et al.* (2023) contrast in focus and context but both suggest that one complexity in supporting those with young-onset dementia is a balance between encouragement and coercion.

Meeting Others with Young-Onset Dementia

Connection with other people also living with young-onset dementia was important for feeling powerful and developing a positive and affirming outlook (Ikeuchi *et al.*, 2020). Goffman (1963) wrote that being with others with the same condition (he phrased this as ‘stigma’) facilitates the sharing of learning and self-concept, as people sharing a diagnosis will share similar “moral careers” as they go through comparable experiences and adjustments (Goffman, 1963, p. 45). Shared diagnosis was not always experienced positively, for example Robertson and Evans (2015) had to review use of accommodation space for younger people with dementia during *Side by Side* because the older users were a source of discomfort. There was a sense of confrontation between the need to connect with others experiencing young-onset dementia and the need to avoid those at a more advanced or later stage, because the future disease trajectory evoked fear and distress. This was evident when a participant had to withdraw from the *Side by Side* programme due to their cognitive decline, distressing the other participants because they were confronted with their own future (Robertson and Evans, 2015). So, while connection with others living with young-onset dementia was important, there was also a potential threat in these connections due to the unknowns about differing and comparable rates of decline in cognition.

The role of support groups was somewhat varied in the literature. It was argued that they were helpful for forming new social identities (Pipon-Young *et al.*, 2011) and such groups enabled members to be their authentic selves (Issakainen *et al.*, 2023). However, the needs of those with

young-onset dementia were often neglected in support groups, unless they were designed specifically for those with young-onset dementia, when they were an important mechanism of support (Rabanal *et al.*, 2018). Such groups also needed to support differing gendered needs rather than have dementia dominate (Wiersma, Harvey and Caffery, 2022).

Managing Negativity

The exhaustion and demanding nature of activities was emphasised by Robinson, Giorgi and Ekman (2012). Their Swedish study was undertaken over three years with one female participant. Their longitudinal and phenomenological study aimed to offer insights from an individual experience as it evolved over time (Robinson, Giorgi and Ekman, 2012). Managing daily activities for their participant seemed part of a complex struggle between the criticism she felt from others, the responsibility or accountability for her dementia that resulted from this, and the need to protect herself (initially from others' criticism and then later to preserve her identity). Daily activities included cooking and other household chores, and being able to successfully undertake such activities connected with her self-image of being both cognitively and practically capable (Robinson, Giorgi and Ekman, 2012). A strength of this study was the capturing of the participant's feelings about her diagnosis over a three-year period, however other women may have differing feelings or experiences. Adjustment was found to be an internal journey, and activities could be understood as an external structure that protected those inner processes, a form of survival mechanism.

There was a need to contend with external negative perceptions of dementia (Pipon-Young *et al.*, 2011) and stigma (Issakainen *et al.*, 2023). These could manifest as accusations or disapproval (Robinson, Giorgi and Ekman, 2012), which could then confuse and compound internalised stigma and perceptions of dementia. Trolling and exposure to "dementia doubters" online was highlighted by Talbot *et al.* (2021, p. 2552). They also found that dementia diagnoses were questioned through Twitter and experiences of being ignored or neglected were discouraging (Talbot *et al.*, 2021). Offline also, the struggle to defy external expectations of the diagnosis, whilst also conforming so that "illness credentials" were not questioned, was highlighted by Bartlett (2014, p. 1299). Negative and limiting assumptions about a person based on their having a diagnosis of young-onset dementia undermined personhood and it was important to challenge such public perceptions of dementia (Talbot *et al.*, 2021). The participant in Robinson, Giorgi and Ekman (2012, p. 226)'s research needed to "protect her self-image in order to keep it intact". Support is therefore needed for those with young-onset dementia not only in respect of facilitating and structuring activities, but in supporting positive identity and self-image.

2.3.2.4 Advocacy and Research Involvement

An important form of non-paid work that people living with young-onset dementia were engaged in was advocacy and research involvement. Participants in Broders and Wiersma (2020)'s research were selected from a wider study with 21 participants, of whom eight had a young-onset diagnosis. Five of those with a young-onset diagnosis were women involved in advocacy and Broders and Wiersma (2020) focused on their experiences. Advocacy provided purpose for these women (Broders and Wiersma, 2020). Bartlett (2014) noted that gender may be important in the context of advocacy, because two of her female participants noted discontent about potentially being used or their contributions being tokenistic.

Bartlett (2014) suggested that campaigning activities were perhaps a defiance of dementia, enabling affirmation for identity through making a contribution that was like work (but wasn't). Her research aimed to expand understanding of the relationship between psychology, emotions and disability (Bartlett, 2014) by examining the experiences of people with dementia who also campaigned for social change using the lens of citizenship. The research highlighted how aspects of dementia such as cognitive capacity, exhaustion and public stereotypes can limit an individual's ability to undertake activities (Bartlett, 2014). Her two-year study included interviews, focus groups, diary keeping and observation of participants. A balanced perspective of the positive and negative aspects of campaigning activities were presented (Bartlett, 2014). Campaigning as an activity involves both the psychological (internal) and social (external) self. Internal costs of external success include the worsening of dementia symptoms, often not seen or appreciated by others (Bartlett, 2014).

The psycho-emotional cost of campaign work, particularly in respect of constant conflict with what others' expected of someone with dementia, was highlighted (Bartlett, 2014). Even though the process of undertaking activities was often debilitating, without such activities people with young-onset dementia may experience an absence of meaning or purpose. It has been suggested that volunteering activities may need to be adapted for those with dementia (Roach and Drummond, 2014) and Bartlett (2014, p. 1301) argued that development of rules was needed around the "cranial bias" within campaign work, to better enable those living with dementia to undertake such activities (which were often cognitively loaded). The resourcefulness of individuals and how well they managed their conditions were often relatively simple strategies (Rabanal *et al.*, 2018).

2.3.3 Disruption to the Lifecycle

Connected with the review question of *what people living with young-onset dementia do in the context of career*, alongside paid employment and non-paid work and activities, *disruption to the lifecycle* was also significant. The literature highlighted how having dementia is disruptive to age-related expectations (Johannessen *et al.*, 2018). More research is needed about adjustment within the lifecycle for those with young-onset dementia (Pipon-Young *et al.*, 2011), because being younger with dementia is “disruptive to multiple life trajectories” or roles (Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff, 2011, p. 362) and expectations for the years ahead (Robertson, Evans and Horsnell, 2013; Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac, 2014). Diagnosis could be understood as a “sledgehammer” (Rabanal *et al.*, 2018, p. 3), with the effect of breaking both the lived reality and future expectations for career. Whereas those without dementia may be maintaining career (Super, 1980), or preparing for retirement, those living with dementia in their 50’s and 60’s have no ‘arc’ of expectation to follow. Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac (2014) identified disruption of the lifecycle as a key theme, providing context for their other themes of identity, social orientation and agency (Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac, 2014, p. 456). None of their participants were in paid employment when interviewed, which perhaps suggests that continuing paid employment may help to lessen disruption to the lifecycle, as that branch of career can continue.

An area of concern noted by Pipon-Young *et al.* (2011) was age when diagnosed, because those diagnosed in their 60’s may not define themselves as young and therefore not identify with a *young-onset* diagnosis (Pipon-Young *et al.*, 2011) or indeed feel *too young* (Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac, 2014). Those with young-onset dementia may be in comparatively good physical health, yet aware their cognitive capacity is deteriorating (Rabanal *et al.*, 2018). The stigma of dementia being a disease of the elderly (Johannessen *et al.*, 2018) and being connected with older age (Nygard *et al.*, 2023) was disruptive to sense of identity and the lifecycle as expectations adjusted to those of an older age. Super (1980) connected age with roles and life stages, with ‘decline’ after the age of 65 (or retirement life stage). Dementia being constructed within ‘old age’, and a stage of life stigmatised as one of decline, has resulted in the neglect of wider impacts of the disease, such as on family and community relationships (Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff, 2011).

Those with a young-onset diagnosis distinguished themselves from those with later onset dementia (Rabanal *et al.*, 2018), however Ashworth (2020) argued that there was less separation of identity between those with younger or later onset than previously suggested. While roles such as ‘citizen’ and ‘spouse’ continue into the ‘decline’ stage of life (Super, 1980), the shape of the rainbow being

on a downward trajectory suggests a continuation of career defined by deterioration. In the context of dementia, a progressive and terminal condition, this combination of decline and disruption to career could be interpreted as a negative and protracted end. However, the literature suggested that the disruption of dementia could have positive consequences for career; such as restarting or commencing hobbies (Chaplin and Davidson, 2014), keeping active (Rabanal *et al.*, 2018) and becoming involved in public life as an advocate (Bartlett, 2014).

Employment is often understood as part of youth or mid-life, whereas retirement and the possibility of dementia are for old age (Johannessen *et al.*, 2018). In addition to lifecycle connected with age, those with young-onset dementia were likely to have financial responsibilities commensurate with a pre-retirement life stage (Ritchie *et al.*, 2015) and find it difficult to manage finances due to dementia (Kilty *et al.*, 2023). They might also be caring for aging parents when diagnosed (Roach, Drummond and Keady, 2016). The Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) here offers a practical insight, as the role of 'homemaker' could be understood to be continuing in spite of the challenges of symptoms, restricted finances and impact on caring. Maintaining family relationships and the home, for example through housework, continues to be important to women after developing dementia (Wiersma, Harvey and Caffery, 2022). Considering the disruptive nature of dementia, and the stigma of decline associated with aging, an insight gained from this review is how continuation matters for career but not necessarily with all aspects or roles. This continuation could be of employment, or of family or homemaker roles, developing new identities or involvement in new activities; but the rainbow does not stop. As with actual rainbows, where a mythical pot of gold is promised if the end of the rainbow can be found, dementia does not mean the end because gold can still be found through one or multiple roles.

2.3.3.1 Planning Ahead

This review has found that future was important to people living with young-onset dementia, but planning for the future was complex due to the unpredictable nature of dementia progression. There was a connection between the future and fear. Such fears included future personality changes, getting lost, living arrangements and loneliness (Busted, Nielsen and Birkelund, 2020). The understanding of dementia as "an illness with 'no future'" subjected those living with dementia to "significant fear and stress" (Ashworth, 2020, p. 1647). The Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) ends with the 'decline' career stage, and whilst true that career does come to an end future is still an important consideration before (and also after) the age of 65. Plans for the retirement phase of life, for example, are an important aspect of career and after developing dementia there was an anticipation that such a previously-imagined future would be lost (Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac,

2014). Therefore the need arose to reconsider life expectations and adjust thinking about the future (Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac, 2014).

Envisaging a time when symptoms worsen (Ashworth, 2020) was fraught with practical and emotional costs. It was important that people living with young-onset dementia made the best of each day, adopting a day-at-a-time-approach (Busted, Nielsen and Birkelund, 2020). Busted, Nielsen and Birkelund (2020)'s research was undertaken with nine participants living with young-onset dementia in Denmark. Semi-structured interviews were analysed using thematic analysis, with 'fearing a humiliating future' one of three broad themes along with 'dementia causing loss of control over oneself' and 'becoming a burden to the family while the sense of self disappears' (Busted, Nielsen and Birkelund, 2020, p. 1). There was a relationship between control and the future, with lack of control leading to fear (Busted, Nielsen and Birkelund, 2020). The 'personal determinants' of the Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) may be especially important when living with young-onset dementia, because such determinants influence the response to fear, control and stress evoked by the diagnosis. Being able to maintain a positive attitude was found to be important for coping with the diagnosis but this isn't possible for everyone (Rabanal *et al.*, 2018).

Rabanal *et al.* (2018) undertook a study using interpretive phenomenological analysis (IPA) with 14 participants living with young-onset dementia in the UK, eight of whom were in paid employment at the time of interview. In contrast to Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac (2014) their participants were more orientated to the present than the future (Rabanal *et al.*, 2018). This is significant in the context of career, where future plans are often generally the focus of attention. Bimrose, McMahon and Watson (2013) noted how the context of life for older women could make career planning somewhat futile. This seemed to have additional significance for women with young-onset dementia due to the unpredictability of disease progression (Busted, Nielsen and Birkelund, 2020). Loss of work was described as particularly difficult for women because of the loss of something to do every day (Broders and Wiersma, 2020). This is a gendered aspect of experience that could be positive, as roles such as homemaker and parent could help alleviate the loss of work; or negative as reliance on such roles perpetuates gendered expectations that may not be right, desirable or possible for all women living with young-onset dementia.

2.3.3.2 Personal and Family Roles

Living out the roles depicted in the Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) and undertaking activities as part of these roles was also an important aspect of what people with dementia did in the context of career. As employment comes to an end with retirement, the Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) predicts that personal roles will become more prominent. For those living with dementia, this

transition of roles was not only related to aging but to diagnosis. Adjusting to living with dementia also meant adjustment of role responsibilities, and progression of the condition made it difficult to fulfil such responsibilities in different 'theatres' of career, including the home and place of work (Robertson, Evans and Horsnell, 2013). This suggests that not only do those living with young-onset dementia have a sudden career transition through diagnosis that others do not, but that ability to fulfil and enjoy personal roles is also undermined by dementia.

Roach and Drummond (2014) and Roach, Drummond and Keady (2016)'s aim was to better understand "family transition" in the context of young-onset dementia (Roach, Drummond and Keady, 2016, p. 26) and therefore responses from family interviews were analysed holistically. All participants with young-onset dementia were male, and women with young-onset dementia may have offered different perspectives on meaningful activity than the male participants. For example, care in the context of familial roles, and also in respect of care for appearances and the aging female body (Wiersma, Harvey and Caffery, 2022); and the connection between identity and appearance (such as clothing, hairstyle and make-up) intersecting with "dementia, age and gender" (Wiersma, Harvey and Caffery, 2022, p. 12). However, a key finding discussed by Roach, Drummond and Keady (2016) was that meaningful activity was a channel of continuity in the context of the family, enabling those with young-onset dementia to continue fulfilling roles they'd had before developing dementia. Wawrziczny *et al.* (2016) undertook a study using IPA, interviewing 16 couples where one partner had a diagnosis of 'probable' young-onset Alzheimer's Disease. Couples were interviewed together so that interactions between them and expressions of emotional exchange could be included in analysis. They described moments of avoidance and "moments of inevitable confrontation" (Wawrziczny *et al.*, 2016, p. 700) when symptoms could no longer be avoided.

Changing roles within the context of family were discussed by Pipon-Young *et al.* (2011), Roach, Drummond and Keady (2016) and van Vliet *et al.* (2017). Difficult transitions within changing relationships were described, and the anticipation of the transition when the person with dementia might no longer live at home (Roach, Drummond and Keady, 2016). Roach and Drummond (2014), Roach, Drummond and Keady (2016), Wawrziczny *et al.* (2016), Evans (2019), Ashworth (2020) and Scott *et al.* (2023) adopted a methodological approach that involved interviewing people living with dementia and their families (usually partners, with some adult children), demonstrating the importance of family to the experience of living with dementia. Though these papers utilised differing analytic approaches, a balance between before and after dementia seemed to emerge through the themes explored. There was a need to know (for example, confirmation of a diagnosis of dementia) and also a fear of knowing, given the incurable nature of dementia (Wawrziczny *et al.*,

2016); adjustment to the changing future while focusing on one day at a time (Ashworth, 2020); and ending work but needing to continue purposeful activity (Roach and Drummond, 2014). Such themes indicate that family roles both change and continue in the context of career. Work roles were connected with those in the family, facilitating a “biographical continuance” (Roach, Drummond and Keady, 2016, p. 31).

Dementia may therefore alter the shape of the Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) to reflect how living with a diagnosis can change career roles. A particular role that was relevant to family and career was that of driver. Ashworth (2020) highlighted the significance of losing a driving license, an important ability and aspect of independence. For one participant in Johannessen *et al.* (2018)’s research, no longer being able to drive meant life was emptier. Driving is ‘normal’ for many adults and contemporaries; it is a useful contribution, it can be enjoyable, it is often necessary, and it provides meaning through being able to help and assist others. Becoming a non-driver can therefore be of huge significance to people with young-onset dementia. Scott *et al.* (2023) focused on driving cessation. The loss of driving capacity discussed in interviews with ten participants was described as overwhelming. This could be understood as a form of grief because loss of driving was also a loss of an “individual’s independence, freedom, role, identity and social connectedness” (Scott *et al.*, 2023, p. 3). Their findings also highlighted the practical difficulties incurred through driving cessation, including challenging questions about when to stop, who should decide this, and how the decision process should be managed; and the need to ensure alternative provision and plans are in place (Scott *et al.*, 2023).

2.4 Literature Review Summary

This review has found that people living with young-onset dementia do continue their careers after diagnosis. This continuance takes the form of paid employment, voluntary activities and family and other personal roles. However, not only does dementia negatively impact each of these areas of career but many do not get the support they need and endure negative, stressful and difficult experiences. Such experiences compound the difficulties arising from dementia and are often avoidable through ensuring that employees can leave or retire positively and at the right time for them, have advice and guidance to address practical and financial concerns, and support that focuses on their contributions and needs rather than stigmatised assumptions.

A further area discussed in the literature through this review was how dementia is disruptive to the lifecycle. It has been argued that young-onset dementia shouldn’t be defined in terms of age, but in terms of life-stage (Pipon-Young *et al.*, 2011), because young-onset dementia in mid-life may force

one into a premature old age (Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac, 2014). The Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) conceptualises career through life stages as opposed to ages, and is therefore a helpful tool to support understanding that what people living with young-onset dementia do is related more to lifecycle than to age.

Career has not been explicitly explored for people living with dementia. This review has brought together a range of papers that have focused on different aspects of career for those living with young-onset dementia. Further understanding is needed to ensure career possibilities can be maximised, and policies and services seeking to support those with young-onset dementia can incorporate insights from a career perspective. The research aim for this study is therefore to ***explore how women living with young-onset dementia experience life roles in the context of career.***

The Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) has supported understanding of how the lifecycle, planning and the personal and family roles that are part of career can be impacted by young-onset dementia. The research objectives are therefore to:

- Explore how a diagnosis of young-onset dementia impacts life role identities and life stages for women
- Identify enablers and disablers of career role continuance for women living with young-onset dementia
- Explore the meaning of artefacts to career and career identities for women living with young-onset dementia.

What *people living with young-onset dementia do* from a gendered perspective was not prominent in the literature. This was somewhat surprising, particularly within the context of care and familial roles which are gender distinct (such as wife, mother, and sister), and when considering how the trajectory of women's lives is different to that of men (Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac, 2014).

Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac (2014) noted difficulty in recruiting women for their research and suggested this may indicate gender differences in coping with Alzheimer's Disease. Wiersma, Harvey and Caffery (2022) highlighted the need for more gender-specific dementia research and understanding of the entwined nature of gender and dementia, because gender and dementia cannot be separated. Therefore, this study will focus on women's experiences.

3. Methodology

3.1 Introduction

This *Methodology* chapter will detail the methodology upon which this research is based. I explore how reality, meaning and the researcher are understood before discussing the qualitative approach (reflexive thematic analysis); continuing with detail of the quality evaluation and ethical principles applicable to this study. As the chapter will detail, my role as a researcher is integral to the methodological approach of this study. I therefore introduce this chapter using the image of my walking stick as a means of communicating my understanding. As the *Methods* chapter will later discuss, as part of interviews with participants I asked them to bring an object to represent their career. To explain this aspect of the interview further, I created *Participant Object Instructions* (Appendix Two). I included three of my own objects in these instructions, of which the walking stick was one. I explained I had chosen it because “this walking stick is an object that represents my experience of chronic illness and how this has impacted my life”. I use it here as a way of representing the iterative process of developing the methodology for the study. I think visually through pictures and metaphor. Therefore, use of a picture reflects my process of understanding as a researcher, and as an object it reflects a part of my identity that has influenced the study.

Figure 3: Walking Stick

My walking stick (Figure 3, left) is an object I have had for many years but now rarely need to use. There are various ways that this object could be understood. It has a practical use, helping to relieve discomfort and providing support for staying upright when walking. Though called a ‘walking’ stick, it was also useful when needing to stand, for example in a queue. It has particular specifications, such as the shape of the handle and the length of the stick, and it folds. It also has emotional significance as I remember the reliance I had on it when I was younger, and the distress caused by other people staring and questioning why I was using a walking stick at my age. As ME is an invisible impairment, it

was usually the only external indicator or sign that I wasn't what I appeared to be; a healthy and happy young woman.

The walking stick is an example of how various theoretical perspectives contribute to knowledge. The various ways of understanding the walking stick that I describe are all true but are useful in different contexts. For example, to improve the design of the walking stick I might focus on the measurements. To understand how it was useful, I could ask questions. To gain insight into how I felt when I used it daily, I could review old diaries or photographs. All these perspectives are valid. However, the perspective and the methods used need to align with the desired objective. If I wanted to improve the design of the walking stick questions about using it may be helpful; but without the measurements, details of what it is made from, etc, the answers would be of limited use for my redesign.

Therefore, various perspectives are true but useful in different contexts and for different purposes. These perspectives, the philosophical underpinnings of the research, compose the ontological and epistemological foundations of the study. Braun and Clarke (2019a) refer to these theoretical foundations, and exploration and decisions about them within the research, as 'knowingness'. It is therefore important to articulate my knowingness and to clarify the context in which this study takes place, and how this study contributes to how young-onset dementia and career development for women is understood. Through the research process I have continued to develop my own knowingness and have learned, for example, that I am better able to understand my world through metaphor and imagery. This is how I have come understand ontology and epistemology, demonstrating my "engagement with research as a thought-out adventure" (Braun and Clarke, 2019a, p. 591).

The research aim for this study is to *explore how women living with young-onset dementia experience life roles in the context of career*. Exploration, "the investigation of unknown regions"⁹, is the focus for this study. The 'region' being explored is not a physical space or biological entity, but the region of experience. In the earlier *Background* chapter, theoretical perspectives related to the key concepts in this study (young-onset dementia, disability, career and gender) were explored. Just as there are multiple ways to explore and understand a walking stick, so there are multiple ways to explore experience. The methods used in this study have arisen from the most fitting philosophical underpinnings: interpretive constructionism. These philosophical underpinnings of this study will now be discussed further.

⁹ The Free Dictionary by Farlex

3.2 Philosophical Underpinnings

There are different ways to understand reality and to understand meaning. In a research context, these are referred to as ontology and epistemology. Combined, these form the philosophical underpinnings of a research study. To summarise my understanding of these I created a picture, informed by Moon and Blackman (2014) and Hathcoat, Meixner and Nicholas (2019) (the picture can be found in Appendix Three). This picture explored the ontological and epistemological possibilities for this study, using the example of how the understanding of a tree would differ from different philosophical viewpoints. I expand on meaning of the picture in the following paragraphs.

3.2.1 How is Reality Understood?

Whilst often presented as distinct entities, I understand methodological or philosophical perspectives to be more akin to points along a continuum (as depicted in the picture in Appendix Three). Whilst tables are often used to depict the different perspectives (for example Creswell (2003)), Moon and Blackman (2014) presented these in a form more like a continuum. Representing the perspectives as a continuum is helpful for ‘seeing’ how they are connected and linked. When exploring philosophical perspectives through drawing, I chose the example of a tree. For positivists, reality is something that is observable. A tree can be measured, observed, and tested. Regardless of who the researcher is, the reality of the tree is the same for everyone. For interpretivists, at the other end of the continuum, there is no singular reality but a myriad of experiences, perspectives and understandings that make a tree what it is for different individuals.

Critical realism, along the middle of the continuum, is as a ‘post-positivist’ ontology (Cruickshank, 2012). Reality is something we experience differently, and often ‘critically’. Understanding a tree using critical realism would focus on causality, structures and agency (Gorski, 2013; Fryer, 2022). The tree is real in a positivist sense (a reality that is shared by everyone) but this reality is also influenced by various structures, such as climate change impacting its health or the threat of deforestation. Post-positive perspectives, such as critical realism and social constructionism, often involve mixed methods approaches (Farrow *et al.*, 2020), using quantitative and qualitative data, because of the combination of positivism and interpretivism.

3.2.1.1 Interpretivism

Interpretivism, also known as relativism, understands that reality is relative to how the individual interprets it both internally and through influence of external factors, such as the society an individual lives in. Interpretivism “conceptualises reality as the product of human action and

interaction and does not subscribe to the notion of a singular reality that exists independent of human practices” (Braun and Clarke, 2022a, p. 174). Here the concept of bounded relativism is relevant, where those within a group can share a reality that those outside the group do not (Moon and Blackman, 2014). Mental reality is distinguished from physical reality. For example, the walking stick is physically meaningless because I do not use it, but mentally meaningful because of my past connection to it. Therefore, an interpretivist position doesn’t necessarily require outright rejection of reality in all forms. Reality can be relative to context, including a research context (Braun and Clarke, 2022a). Therefore, the interpretivist stance in this study recognises the neurological reality of a young-onset dementia diagnosis, but how this reality manifests and impacts *life and work* will be individual to each person diagnosed.

3.2.2 How is Meaning Understood?

Epistemology concerns how meaning is understood. Again, here perspectives are not distinct but related. The following table (Table 2, below) has adapted Moon and Blackman (2014)’s summary of how meaning is understood through objectivist, constructionist and subjectivist perspectives:

Epistemological perspective	How is meaning understood?
Objectivist	“Meaning exists within an object” (Moon and Blackman, 2014, p. 1169); the meaning or knowledge is independent of the subject
Constructionist	The subject creates (constructs) meaning by interacting with the object
Subjectivist	“Meaning exists within the subject” (Moon and Blackman, 2014, p. 1169); the subject gives meaning to the object

Table 2: Epistemological Perspectives

Subjectivists focus on the individual’s viewpoint. The same object will have different meanings for each individual based on their position and relationship to it. Meaning depends on past experiences, prior learning, culture, context, preferences and understanding. A tree, for example, may have negative meaning for someone who remembers falling off it and injuring herself, but as time passes this meaning may change as she enjoys its blossom in spring or shelters under it during a downpour of rain.

Dementia is not simply an objective reality; it is experienced subjectively. As subjectivity is often based on our experience, a diagnosis of dementia is not understood in the same way by everyone;

including everyone in the same country or of the same gender or at the same career stage. Whereas subjectivists focus is on how meaning is generated by individuals, for constructionists the focus is on social and cultural influences and how these interactions contribute to the construction of meaning (Hathcoat, Meixner and Nicholas, 2019). Meaning isn't a fixed position but continues to be constructed as new learning and experiences are gained. To return to the example of a tree, it is possible for an individual to have constructed meanings that are multiple and even contradictory; it can be liked because of the beauty of its blossom and hated because it blocks the light into a room. As with the walking stick, where I have constructed a meaning that is positive about my illness experience, I could also have constructed a meaning more focused on the negativity of having needed to use it, or a more neutral meaning related to its usefulness. This meaning has important implications, because if usefulness was the only meaning I had constructed for the walking stick, I would have discarded it when I no longer needed it. Therefore, meaning is a complex construction, where meaning for individuals is developed from multiple experiences, emotions and perspectives.

3.2.2.1 Constructionism

Constructionism has particular resonance with this study because young-onset dementia (as a chronic and life-limiting health condition), career (as *life and work*) and being a woman (culturally gendered as well as biological experiences); all have meanings that are constructed and continue to be constructed, for example through new experiences. An "individual's construction of reality is constructed 'from the inside out' through the individual's own thinking and processing" (Patton, 2008, p. 135). Meaning is about relationship; the relationship between the internal and external, the psychological and the social; and between what is made, or constructed, from the materials the individual has. This links to the different perspectives of identity within the context of young-onset dementia, such as the disappearing self (Busted, Nielsen and Birkelund, 2020) and loss of social roles (van Vliet *et al.*, 2017). For example, as a stigmatised condition the meaning of dementia may change before and after diagnosis. Having personal experience of the condition, meeting others living with dementia, and learning more about it can all contribute to the construction (and reconstruction) of what dementia means.

A constructionist epistemology posits that we make or construct meaning (Crotty, 1998) and focuses on how meaning is constructed "between the subject and object" (Moon and Blackman, 2014, p. 1169). The way we construct our meaning is often critical or intentional (Crotty, 1998), and because of this intentionality we are able to explain or articulate it. From a constructionist perspective, an object cannot be isolated from the experience of it (or the experience isolated from the object) (Crotty, 1998). Likewise, description of career experiences cannot be removed from the diagnosis of

young-onset dementia, or young-onset dementia removed from career. Added to this construction is the gendered experience of being a woman. Then with these, all the multiple and various learning, roles and life events that an individual has also experienced.

The constructionist approach “contends that the meaning of this world is culturally, socially, historically and politically situated” (Hathcoat, Meixner and Nicholas, 2019, p. 103). Therefore, constructionists understand language as a way of creating rather than reflecting reality (Braun and Clarke, 2022a). For example, given the prevailing stigma associated with dementia, Alzheimer’s Scotland suggests refraining from using language of ‘suffering’ when referring to people living with dementia (Alzheimer Scotland, 2024). The intention of this is to challenge the negative cultural meaning of dementia, to support the construction of a more positive understanding of the condition and those diagnosed with it. However, Alzheimer Scotland (2024) also recognise that some experiences and realities of dementia are situated in suffering. Meaning continues to be individually constructed even within shared realities, such as shared diagnosis.

Constructivism, Contextualism and Social Constructionism

It is appropriate here to note that terms relating to how reality and meaning are understood have been subject of extensive discussion, debate and refinement; leading to confusion and lack of clarity about what terms mean (Crotty, 1998; Fryer, 2022). For example, “the same term is often used in different ways or it may be completely ill-defined” (Hathcoat, Meixner and Nicholas, 2019, p. 101), and there is potential to combine positions or borrow from multiple perspectives (Guba and Lincoln, 2005) to further move debates forward. Constructionism therefore needs to be clarified in comparison to similar terms such as constructivism, contextualism and social constructionism.

Social constructionism is aligned with a realist ontology, and focuses on how meaning is made between people as they co-create reality together (Sommers-Flanagan, 2015). Contextualism emphasises the importance of context in how people construct reality (Braun and Clarke, 2022a) and is aligned with a critical realist ontology (Braun and Clarke, 2022a). Constructivism focuses on how shared understandings constitute reality (Kratochwill, 2008), so for example, “constructivists desire participants to take an increasingly active role” in data collection and dissemination (Guba and Lincoln, 2005, p. 202). These perspectives are therefore similar in recognising different elements that are part of how meaning is constructed, but constructionism is distinct in that the emphasis is on construction of meaning for the individual.

3.2.3 How is the Researcher Understood?

As well as differing understandings of what reality is and how meaning is constructed, the continuum of philosophical underpinnings also differ in how the researcher's role is positioned. A positivist ontology understands the researcher as independent of the subject of research, with the researcher's values excluded and their position one of 'disinterest' (Guba and Lincoln, 2005). An interpretivist ontology includes the researcher within the research and positions them as a 'resource' (Braun and Clarke, 2023). Replicability of findings is a positivist value (Braun and Clarke, 2024b), and "borrowing evaluation criteria from one paradigm of inquiry and applying them to another is problematic" (Koch and Harrington, 1998, p. 884). Within an interpretivist paradigm, the aim is not to reproduce or replicate findings, but rather to detail the methods used so that the readers of the research can fully understand what the researcher did and why they did it (Koch and Harrington, 1998). The individual qualities of the researcher add to the uniqueness of the research, and this adding of the researcher in the process is "inevitable" (Braun and Clarke, 2024b, p. 2).

As "knowledge cannot be separated from the knower" (Braun and Clarke, 2022a, p. 179), the researcher has strong influence on what becomes 'known' through the research process. For interpretivists, the researcher brings their own reality, experiences and understanding to the research. Their epistemological positioning "profoundly shapes the researcher's conceptualisation of the participant in data collection and analysis" (Carter & Little, 2007). It is not possible for the researcher to completely or fully understand the reality of others because these realities are multiple and complex. For example, I cannot remember all the times I used the walking stick and therefore cannot fully explain how it came to have the meaning it has. My mobility and level of pain are different now, and no longer needing it has influenced the meaning the stick has for me. So, whilst they cannot *know*, the researcher can seek to understand the reality of others through a process of interpretation or analysis. As the researcher, my aim is not to discover the 'truth' about participant experiences but read and analyse the data to generate meaning (Braun and Clarke, 2022a).

3.2.3.1 Me as a Researcher

Being aware of my 'constructed' self is part of clarity about my axiology and positioning as a researcher, locating myself in my work (England, 1994). Further detail focusing on my position as a researcher is included in this thesis in the *Positionality Statement* (IV). My researcher reflexivity has included consideration of "the diversity and complexity of one's own social location" (Nagy Hesse-Biber and Leavy, 2011, p. 39) and how my external and internal identities and understanding of

myself and the world have been shaped. As a researcher, I have also embraced how I think and connect with the world through the research process, for example through using creative and visual methods to support my analysis.

3.3 Methodological Approach

Having considered the interpretivist and constructionist paradigms adopted in this study, and how my role as the researcher is understood, I will now describe how these philosophical underpinnings translate into research practice (the methodological approach).

3.3.1 Qualitative or Quantitative?

Quantitative research is often aligned with realist and positivistic perspectives (Creswell, 2003), and qualitative with interpretative, constructionist and subjectivist perspectives. However, methodologies using either forms of data (or both) can align along the paradigmatic continuum (Crotty, 1998). Qualitative research, for example, can adopt a positivist epistemology; and sometimes not deliberately but through “positivism creep” (Braun and Clarke, 2022a, p. 188). This ‘creep’ occurs when traditional positivist values, such as the independence of the researcher in the research process, are unknowingly (or unthinkingly) adopted in qualitative research.

It is also possible, as with research that is neither positivist nor interpretivist (such as critical realist), to use both qualitative and quantitative data (known as mixed methods). For this interpretivist study, the approach is fully qualitative or ‘Big Q’ (Braun and Clarke, 2022c) because it fully embraces the interpretivist paradigm and associated qualitative research values, such as the importance of researcher subjectivity and the understanding of “meaning and knowledge as contextually situated, partial and provisional” (Braun and Clarke, 2022c). A key quality of qualitative research is “meaning and meaning-making”, and the interpretation of (rather than discovery) of findings (Braun and Clarke, 2019a, p. 591). This makes it appropriate for exploring participant experiences, which is the research aim of this study. A qualitative approach will enable participants to share their meanings and enable me as the researcher to make meaning through analysis of what they have shared with me.

3.3.1.1 What is Qualitative Research?

Qualitative research has historically been defined as being about words (Braun and Clarke, 2013). However, the field of qualitative research is developing and expanding in exciting ways, to include greater diversity of data forms. Such developments include how the data or words are collected (for

example Harrison and Ogden (2020) used a 'knit and natter' format for their focus groups), the inclusion of emotions within research (Reed and Towers, 2023) and also how the researcher reflects on their role and reflexively interprets data, for example Campbell, Dowlen and Fleetwood-Smith (2023) used diagrams, video stills and textile craft within their doctoral research.

Such developments support the interpretivist approach by expanding the possible routes of interpretation, rather than reliance on words. Non-text-based forms of data collection are one way that qualitative research is evolving to include voices that may be excluded by reliance on words. A future challenge for qualitative research is the continuing reliance on text-based forms of reporting and articulating interpretation and analysis of data, for example because of journal requirements. An example of how my interpretivist approach has been reflected throughout the research process was challenging the positivist and text-based format of a scientific poster. I created a scientific poster using crochet (a picture of the poster and further detail about this can be found in *Reflecting Through Crochet* in the *Methods* chapter). Such challenges also align with the feminist elements of this study, because innovation is a quality of feminist research (Brooks, 2011). This was also considered when planning data collection using object elicitation, because the traditional question and answer format of an interview isn't necessarily the best way to understand women's lives (Brooks, 2011).

3.3.2 Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) or Phenomenological Interpretative Analysis (IPA)?

Having clarified the philosophical underpinnings of the study and identified that a qualitative methodology was appropriate, specific forms of qualitative methodology were considered. Initially, I explored Robert Stake's (Stake, 1995; Stake, 2006; Stake, 2010) approach to case study. However, for the research to utilise case study there needed to be triangulation of data (Stake, 1995), and this would have meant compromise between the person with dementia's lived experience and other data sources. Ultimately, the decision not to adopt case study was reflective of the process of balancing dynamics between research objectives, questions and design to develop the best approach (Carter and Little, 2007).

An approach using thematic analysis would enable the utilisation of fitting aspects of case study (such as a focus on participants' reality), therefore RTA and IPA were both considered. Both these approaches are well suited to exploratory qualitative research and share similarities. For example, the steps of analysis in IPA such as familiarisation, experiential stages, clusters and themes (Smith and Fieldsend, 2021) are similar to those proposed in RTA. Like RTA, IPA also recognises the

importance of the researcher's role in "making sense" of participant data (Smith, 2004, p. 40). However, there are some key differences between IPA and RTA which made RTA the more fitting choice for this study. Braun and Clarke (2020b) have explained that the focus of analysis in IPA differs from RTA; in RTA themes are developed across cases but in RTA each case should be analysed in greater depth before developing themes across cases. IPA has a psychological focus, and lacks the flexibility that RTA offers to also consider "the social-cultural context" (Braun and Clarke, 2013, p. 183). The IPA analysis process has significant variants depending on the theoretical basis of the IPA being utilised (Neubauer, Witkop and Varpio, 2019), whereas in RTA the analysis process is clearly described (Braun and Clarke, 2022a).

3.3.2.1 What is Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA)?

RTA, developed by Braun and Clarke (2019a), is used in this study as the primary methodological approach. RTA enables and encourages a reflexive connection between the researcher and the data. This is advantageous in this study, where the phenomenon of career has multiple interpretations, and the experience of young-onset dementia is individual to participants but is also a shared diagnosis. Of the three thematic analysis approaches identified by Braun and Clarke (2023), RTA is the one most closely aligned with the qualitative research paradigm. While RTA alone may be 'methodish' (Braun and Clarke, 2022a) and not alone constitute a methodology (Braun and Clarke, 2022c), it can be used alongside other methodologies (Finlay, 2021). RTA studies benefit from less limited "interpretive power" (Braun and Clarke, 2022a, p. 261) by combining theoretical perspectives. Furthermore, career development theory is a small and developing area of interest, and "is often also informed by literature from wider fields" (Bolger, 2021, p. 12). Therefore, in this study I combine RTA with theory related to gender, career and disability (discussed in the *Background* chapter) to form an overall methodological approach to the study.

RTA is an approach developed from Virginia Braun and Victoria Clark's earlier work on thematic analysis. Their seminal paper, *Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology* (Braun and Clarke, 2006), has been cited over 185,000 times (Google Scholar, 2024). RTA was introduced in *Reflecting on Reflexive Thematic Analysis* (Braun and Clarke, 2019a) and continues to develop as an approach, for example RTA reporting guidelines (RTARG) were recently published (Braun and Clarke, 2024a; Braun and Clarke, 2024b). RTA, as with other forms of thematic analysis, is a method of analysing data to generate themes from initial familiarisation and coding of data. What distinguishes RTA is the need for the researcher to be a reflexive part of the research process (Braun and Clarke, 2022a).

Therefore, RTA is not only a method of analysis because of how the researcher is understood and positioned through the research process; from initial study conceptualisation to design, data

collection to analysis and dissemination. The researcher needs to be honest and authentic about their role in the research (Tracy, 2010). Who I am and what I bring to the data is integral to the RTA approach because who I am influences the process and reflexivity enables an understanding of how that influence manifests (Braun and Clarke, 2022a). RTA is also appropriate here because the reflexivity of the researcher challenges the traditional understanding of the researcher as expert, with associated assumptions about participants lives based on that expertise (Stone and Priestley, 1996).

3.3.3 RTA and Quality Evaluation

RTA, like qualitative approaches in general, have been criticised for being less rigorous or scientific than quantitative approaches. It has been argued that a focus on rigour, for example, is a remnant of positivist paradigms (Koch and Harrington, 1998). Some aspects of rigour, such as reproducibility of findings, are less fitting with an interpretative or qualitative approach, such as RTA (Braun and Clarke, 2024b). However, whilst such reproducibility is not the aim here, the *Methods* chapter does detail how the study was undertaken and data analysed in sufficient detail so that another researcher could undertake the same process. Flexibility can also be interpreted as not being sufficiently scientific or rigorous (Finlay, 2021; Larkin, Watts and Clifton, 2006). Different criteria for evaluating quality in qualitative research have been proposed. Yardley (2000, p. 219) has suggested four criteria: sensitivity to context, commitment and rigour, transparency and coherence, and impact and importance. Tracy (2010) proposed eight criteria to ensure that qualitative research was 'excellent'. More recently, Finlay (2021, p. 110) has suggested the four R's: "rigour, relevance, resonance and reflexivity". How the rigour or the quality of research is assessed within interpretive research necessitates an interpretive understanding that fits the interpretative paradigm. The 4 R's (Finlay, 2021) are an interpretative approach to quality assessment and flexible, so able to incorporate a range of interpretative approaches, and they enable a holistic overview of the research. Each of the 'R's in the context of this study will now be discussed and are then summarised (Table 3).

3.3.3.1 Rigour

Rigour can be defined as complete data collection (or gathering, in RTA) and analysis (Yardley, 2000) or complete and systematic analysis (Finlay, 2021). Koch and Harrington (1998) argued that by signposting the research product well, the reader will be able to navigate between the researcher and participant. Using participant quotations can evidence the depth of the analysis process (Finlay, 2021) and was also a method of promoting a "many voiced" analysis, ensuring that my reflexive

practices did not cross into self-indulgence (Koch and Harrington, 1998, p. 888). Member checking has been used as an aspect of rigour in qualitative study but this is problematic due to its positivistic roots and incompatibility with interpretative methodologies (Varpio *et al.*, 2017). In practice, member checking is also not straightforward, for example expecting participants to remember interviews from months previously or read many pages of transcript (Koch and Harrington, 1998). Given the research context of young-onset dementia, this requirement would be particularly onerous for participants and therefore raise ethical concerns.

Koch and Harrington (1998) have called for understanding of rigour to be widened, for example to include contexts such as the morality and politics of research as well as the researcher's engagement with the research product. By detailing my own positionality (my *Positionality Statement* can be found in IV), and the philosophical underpinnings of this study I have ensured a qualitative approach that is rigorous.

3.3.3.2 Relevance

In the context of this research related to young-onset dementia, I considered relevance when defining career as *life and work*. I understood from reviewing the literature that young-onset dementia often results in the loss of employment, so defining career in a way that prioritised employment would have been less relevant than a more flexible conceptualisation.

During phase two of my analysis, I met with a career guidance professional from Skills Development Scotland (SDS) to discuss my analytical thoughts so far and share some of the pictures created as part of the process. I chose to do this as a way of incorporating relevance into the analysis process, recognising the link between theory and practice in careers guidance (Lauder and Neary, 2020). Though career guidance is not my professional field, it is one with the potential to support women with young-onset dementia with their careers, so I sought input that would support the relevance of the research. Helpful feedback from this meeting was that using pictures and metaphor is encouraged when delivering career guidance to clients, so my approach was reflecting that of professional practice. Whilst my focus throughout the research was on relevance for those with young-onset dementia, discussing with a career guidance professional was a way I could ensure wider professional relevance to enhance the usefulness of the study.

3.3.3.3 Resonance

Resonance is essentially about ensuring the writing about the research is of a good standard (Finlay, 2021) and is presented in a relatable and accessible way. This is why the naming of themes is particularly important (Finlay, 2021); "a good theme name will be informative, concise and catchy"

(Braun and Clarke, 2022a, p. 111). Using participant quotations in the naming of themes can help explain what the theme is communicating in a way that is relatable and “immediate” (Braun and Clarke, 2022a, p. 112). Participant quotations were used for all subthemes in this study and supported the naming of major themes. A well written analysis is an analysis that is more likely to be read, and being read helps to ensure the research has impact and as wide a reach as possible.

3.3.3.4 Reflexivity

Reflexivity has been defined as:

- The “self-critical sympathetic introspection and the self-conscious analytical scrutiny of the self as researcher” (England, 1994, p. 82);
- The “researcher’s critical self-awareness” (Finlay, 2021, p. 107);
- “The critical gaze turned toward the self” (Koch and Harrington, 1998, p. 888);
- And the “striving to own, in the sense of acknowledging and taking responsibility for [my] perspectives” (Braun and Clarke, 2022b, p. 18)

It is a process through which the researcher is aware of how they ‘deal with’ the data (Koch and Harrington, 1998). The specifics of how to practice reflexivity can be unclear (Jamie and Rathbone, 2022), because individual researchers will find different channels and ways of reflexive practice effective. Detailing my channels and approaches to reflexive practice is therefore important to enable evaluation of the quality of work undertaken.

Rigour, Relevance, Resonance and Reflexivity Table

Table 3 (below) summarises the key practice points identified through the ‘4R’s’ to evaluate thematic analysis (Finlay, 2021):

4R’s	Definition	Key Points
Rigour	Research that is “believable or plausible” (Koch and Harrington, 1998, p. 882)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By utilising the steps outlined in the RTA process, several levels of analysis are undertaken and this supports a process that avoids findings that are superficial or lacking complexity (Yardley, 2000) • Member checking is not compatible with interpretative

		methodologies (Varpio <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
Relevance	The value of research is understood to be about how the research applies and contributes to the area of study (Finlay, 2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance has different interpretations, with a focus on added insight, usefulness and applicability to the research area (Finlay, 2021)
Resonance	The research is presented in ways that resonate with readers and provoke interest and engagement with what is written (Finlay, 2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings should reflect the depth of the analysis process undertaken and how themes are named, described and supported by participant quotations can evidence this (Finlay, 2021)
Reflexivity	How I understand myself as the researcher in relation to the research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflexivity is a process through which the researcher analyses, examines and breaks down their knowledge and understanding (Finlay, 2017)

Table 3: The 4R's

3.3.3.5 My Reflexivity as a Researcher

My own 'deconstruction' of knowledge (Finlay, 2021) was facilitated through writing (through a research journal and reflexive diary; suggested by Braun and Clarke (2022b) and Koch and Harrington (1998)) and creativity (crochet interview reflections, art journal, music playlist and additional creative outlets during analysis); alongside less tangible reflexive outlets such as walking breaks and internal conversations. These channels of reflexivity provided spaces to explore and question my position, understanding and approach throughout the research process. I decided that whilst some of my reflexive methods, such as those used in analysis, would be shared when and if appropriate, others needed to be private and not shared with my supervisor or others. This was important to ensure I could be honest, uncomfortable and process my reflections without concern that they would be judged or scrutinised. This was also a way of self-care during the research process, for example using my art journal as a way of calming my mind when I felt stressed.

A lack of reflexivity can result in a lack of rigour, because in RTA themes are "analytic entities produced by the researcher" and "aren't in data, waiting; they are instead developed through

analysis, and are generated at the intersection of the data and the researcher's positioning, skill and (considerable) interpretative labour" (Braun and Clarke, 2023, p. 300). The 'intersection' of the data and myself is where reflexivity matters. In the context of reflexivity, the personal is professional (England, 1994). Researchers influence every stage of a research project and therefore it is important to "be as reflective as possible" and mindful of the researcher's indirect impact throughout (Jamie and Rathbone, 2022, p. 16).

As part of my reflexive approach as a researcher, I have therefore considered how my own biography has influence within the context of insider-outsider status. The insider-outsider status is an aspect of the power dynamic between myself as the researcher and participants as the researched; it is not simplistic and should not be considered absolute (Mannay, 2010). For example, there is difference in power status in society between disabled people and non-disabled people (Stone and Priestley, 1996). It was therefore important to me to 'disclose' my experience of chronic illness to participants (which I did indirectly through the *Participant Object Instructions*, Appendix Two). Contextually, individual characteristics can offer position of privilege or of oppression (Young, 2014). Being aware of how as a researcher I have multiple insider and outsider positions (Braun and Clarke, 2013), and both privileged and oppressed status, is an especially important consideration in the context of this study because the participant group is one that can be considered as marginalised. Marginalised people "are those with a less powerful position in society" (England *et al.*, 2020, p. 255), and therefore may include those who are not in paid work and those who are living with young-onset dementia. I have been marginalised as an oppressed outsider to employment when I could not work and claimed benefits due to ill health, and then as a privileged outsider as a PhD student supported by stipend. I therefore seek not to position myself as expert in the researcher-researched relationship (Stone and Priestley, 1996), but acknowledge the imbalance of relationship with participants and the context of my privileges.

The emotional aspect of research is also important to consider in the context of reflexivity. *The Wounded Researcher* (Romanyshyn, 2010) relates to the humanness of researchers, and how our unconscious selves are an "invisible shadow" that influences our work (Romanyshyn, 2010, p. 279). Whilst reflexivity is a positive element of research, it is important that researcher reflexivity and approach does not dilute the voices of participants (Reed and Towers, 2023). The emotional impact of research on the researcher is a growing concern, as within dementia research the focus of emotional impact is often on the participant (Quinn *et al.*, 2024). All stages of research can have an emotional impact, this is not limited to data collection or analysis (Quinn *et al.*, 2024). Romanyshyn (2010, p. 285) has suggested that as wounded researchers, we are able to transform "a wound into a work". To be able to use emotions as positive aspects of reflexivity, rather than distractions or

hindrances to the research process, requires development of personal insight and ability to work through emotions, wounds and feelings to understand both the self and others (and the data) better. It is important not to avoid emotional responses, as not addressing these can lead to internalising and carrying the emotions beyond the specific research project (Reed and Towers, 2023), leading to becoming a researcher less able to process and respond to emotive aspects of research because of previous pain or need for self-protection. I found creative elements of my research helpful in ensuring my emotional responses were recognised and processed. For example, when I created a 3D collage on my desk during analysis (Appendix Four), this was inspired by a picture of my grandmother that resonated with data from one of my participants. They had described an old lady in her eighties, with a grey background and sitting by an empty fire. Using this particular picture of my grandmother, which matched the participant's description, helped me to bring my "wound into a work" (Romanyshyn, 2010, p. 285). I brought my career role as granddaughter to my role as researcher. This particular picture had been reoccurring for me since my interview with the participant, so constructing the collage helped to process the image so that the personal meaning this stirred was then better focused on and able to interpret the participant's meaning.

3.3.4 Ethics

Before the *Methods* chapter is introduced, where the practical application of ethical principles is discussed, the theoretical approach to ethics will now be considered. Ethical guidance included the four principles suggested by Beauchamp and Childress (2013): respect for autonomy, not to cause harm, beneficence and justice; and adopting learning from previous qualitative research with participants living with dementia, for example Cridland *et al.* (2016a)'s recommendations for interviewing people living with dementia. Four areas of ethics in qualitative research have been proposed by Tracy (2010); procedural, situational, relational and exiting ethics. Examples of how these four ethical principles were addressed in this study will now be detailed, incorporating Beauchamp and Childress (2013, p. 13)'s ethical principles applied through general "moral norms". Further detail and examples about ethical decisions made during the research process are also detailed in the *Methods* and *Discussion* chapters:

3.3.4.1 Procedural

The approach to ethics adopted within this study is not limited to 'tick box' procedural considerations, but has sought to be flexible, compassionate and respectful of those living with dementia (Nuffield Council on Bioethics, 2009). In essence, the ethical approach of this study was

focused on *doing* research ethically rather than simply *talking* about ethical practice. Ethical approval for the study was granted by the School of Health and Life Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland in September 2023 (ref 21551; confirmation letter attached as Appendix Five). Procedure during this study also respected autonomy through the recruitment process, for example using a gatekeeper model of recruitment and adhering to timescales for follow-up contact to avoid inadvertent pressure on participants. Participants were recruited using a gatekeeper model of recruitment to safeguard participants and ensure that they had someone with an existing relationship they could raise any questions or concerns with. This approach meant that participants were likely those more interested and engaged with the topic than representative of all women living with young-onset dementia in the UK. However, because participation in research must be voluntary then there is an inherent bias in the sample of those volunteering (Robinson, 2014). To mitigate this a range of organisations that could be potential gatekeepers were contacted, for example gatekeepers focused on research participation and others delivering general support.

One of the gatekeepers for this study was Join Dementia Research (JDR). JDR notifies potential participants (when they have opted-in to receive notifications) about potential studies they are eligible for, and potential participants can then indicate their interest or disinterest in participating, supporting their autonomy. Where potential participants were contacted through JDR about the study and declined, a polite thank you was sent to acknowledge their response and reassure (when appropriate) that this was not a problem. Whilst it was important to be warm and friendly so that I could build rapport with participants, I was aware my personal qualities may have made it more difficult for participants to withdraw if desired, and this was one reason why a gatekeeper model of recruitment was used.

Participants were informed through the *Participant Information Sheet* (Appendix Six) that they could withdraw from the study at any time, up to 14 days after their interview date. Participants were reminded of this before each interview. Introductory meetings with participants provided opportunity for them to ask questions of me about myself or the study, and for me to discuss whether participants wanted or needed a supporter with them for our interview. Where possible, participant preferences were prioritised throughout data collection, for example accommodating a request to be interviewed at an Alzheimer Scotland centre and using Zoom rather than Teams.

3.3.4.2 Situational

Situational ethics requires that “researchers must repeatedly reflect on, critique, and question their ethical decisions” (Tracy, 2010, p. 847). This is important for avoiding unintentional harm to participants, for example by continuing an interview when it is distressing for the participant; but

also conversely not enabling a participant to feel or express upset or negative emotions during an interview. To avoid causing harm, the *Participant Information Sheet* (Appendix Six) was created so that potential participants could be informed about participation before making a decision, and initial introductory conversations with participants provided opportunity for them to meet me and ensure they were comfortable before the interview.

By using the objects to begin each interview, participants were able to avoid harm, for example talking about emotionally painful or distressing subjects. Choosing an object offered them control and enabled them to have a directive role in the interview (Edwards and I'Anson, 2020).

All participants were sent a follow-up email as soon as was practical after their interview, thanking them for their participation and signposting to further sources of support. Where specific needs had arisen during the interview, such as the need to connect with others living with young-onset dementia, specific signposting was provided (such as to the Young Dementia Network) when participants said they would be comfortable receiving this.

3.3.4.3 Relational

Throughout the research process I sought to prioritise compassion (Beauchamp and Childress, 2013) alongside participant's needs, for example through relational ethical considerations such as reciprocity and ongoing reflection (Tracy, 2010). This was not always straightforward. For example, I wanted to avoid causing upset to participants but also wanted to respect participants' right to express upset and share about upsetting experiences. I sought an approach that was person-centred, focused on the needs of the individual participants (Kitwood, 1997). I was also aware of my professional role as a researcher needing to be balanced with my personal needs, such as providing a safe research space for participants to share honestly and openly, but ensuring I also had opportunity after the interview to process my own emotions.

3.3.4.4 Exiting

It is important that after participants have participated in the research they feel respected for their contributions, and feedback is one way to facilitate this (Cridland *et al.*, 2016a). In respect of exiting ethics, I discussed future contact with participants at the end of each interview and through a post-interview email. Participants were invited to opt-in to receive further updates about the study as it progressed. All participants chose to receive updates about the study and several such updates were sent after the data gathering phase of the study was completed. Several participants have contacted me by email to thank me for the updates and their feedback has indicated that this approach to 'exiting' the data gathering has been positive for participants.

3.4 Methodology Summary

This *Methodology* chapter has discussed the philosophical elements of this study and described the theoretical basis upon which the study has been undertaken. Reality is understood as interpretivist or relativist; there is no one reality we all share. Meaning is conceptualised using a constructionist paradigm, which emphasises how we each as individuals construct our own meaning. The methodological approach in this study is qualitative, with RTA adopted as a method of analysis and part of the overall methodology alongside approaches related to disability, gender and career. The chapter has concluded with an overview of quality and rigour within qualitative research and some ethical considerations. Ethics are, however, not limited to theory and how the ethical principles were put into practice is described throughout the following *Methods* chapter.

4. Methods

4.1 Introduction

This *Methods* chapter details how the study methodology was applied through the data gathering methods, beginning with presentation of the participant inclusion criteria and how participants were recruited to the study. The chapter then details how interviews were used to gather data in the study and then the phases of analysis undertaken to generate the findings, which then follow in the next chapter, *Findings*.

4.1.1 Methods and Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA)

The *Reflexive Thematic Analysis Reporting Guidelines (RTARG)* (Braun and Clarke, 2024b) were drafted for the reporting of RTA research in journal articles, and have been adapted for this thesis. Most relevant to the *Methods* chapter is detail of how the data were generated and analysed, not for the purpose of replication (Braun and Clarke, 2024b), but to provide a thorough overview of how I gathered data and undertook analysis for this study. This includes description of my own interaction and connection with participants as the researcher and creative analytical approaches. The *Positionality Statement (IV)* provides more detail on my personal and professional positioning in the context of this research (Braun and Clarke, 2024b).

4.2 Participants

To address the research aim, to explore how women living with young-onset dementia experience life roles in the context of career, the research participants needed to be women living with young-onset dementia. Given the understanding of career as *life and work*, a flexible approach to career was important and therefore I did not include specifics about current or previous employment or life roles in the participant inclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria were designed so that a wide range of women living with young-onset dementia could potentially be included (for example, both those continuing paid employment and those not in employment).

4.2.1 Participant Inclusion Criteria

The participant inclusion and exclusion criteria are detailed in Table 4 (below):

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Have a diagnosis of young-onset dementia	Do not have a diagnosis of young-onset dementia
Aged between 50-70 years	Aged younger than 50 or older than 70 years
Identify as female	Identify as male or other sex or gender
Live in the UK	Live in a country other than the UK
Able to use and access appropriate technology	Unable to use or access appropriate technology
Capacity to understand study and provide consent	Unable to understand study or provide consent, or capacity to do so unclear.

Table 4: Participant Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Further detail about each aspect of the inclusion criteria now follows:

4.2.1.1 Diagnosis of Young-Onset Dementia

To be eligible for inclusion in the study, participants needed to be women living in the UK with a diagnosis of young-onset dementia. The formal diagnosis of dementia was necessary to ensure the integrity of the data, as potential symptoms of dementia can be attributed to other causes during the diagnostic process. Due to factors such as delays with diagnosis and the way diagnosis is recorded relating to age, dementia that is young-onset is not always formally recorded as such (Carter *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, any participants who identified with a young-onset diagnosis were eligible for inclusion even if their dementia diagnosis was not formally recorded before they were 65 years old (or maintained as young-onset as they grew older than 65 years). This approach emphasised the importance of a young-onset dementia identity rather than the bio-medical label of diagnosis.

4.2.1.2 Age

The age range of participants was between 50-70 years old, corresponding with the ‘maintenance’ or ‘decline’ stages Super (1980)’s Life-Career Rainbow. The ages and stages of Super (1980)’s Life-Career Rainbow were conceptualised in 1980 and therefore do not reflect social changes in recent decades, such as an increase in retirement age. The decline stage, for example, begins at age 65 when many women are continuing paid employment. In 1980 women could retire at age 60 years, compared with men who could retire at 65 years, and the default retirement age in the UK continues

to rise¹⁰. However, despite changing social and legal perceptions of ‘old age’ or retirement, young-onset dementia continues to be defined as dementia with onset before the age of 65 years (Dementia UK, 2022). The average time taken to obtain a dementia diagnosis is over 4 years (Dementia UK, 2022), so even those recently diagnosed are likely to have been living with significant symptoms for some time. Due to variances and difficulties with diagnosis specific to younger adults, no timescale from diagnosis to study participation was included as part of the inclusion criteria.

4.2.1.3 Gender

I sought to be sensitive to different understandings of sex and gender identities. It was not assumed that all participants identifying as female were born biologically so or define their gender or sex in accordance with biological constructs. During recruitment I accepted and respected participant’s assertions of their own sex and gendered identities. If the participant identified as a woman then she met this aspect of the inclusion criteria.

4.2.1.4 Live in the UK

Participants also needed to live in the UK. Scotland has developed its own dementia strategies (as discussed in the *Background* chapter) and has a culture related to dementia distinct from other areas of the UK (for example, the influence of the Scottish Dementia Working Group). However, a practical consideration was the comparatively small number of potential participants in Scotland compared with the rest of the UK. Therefore, whilst initial focus was on recruitment in Scotland, when the study was disseminated through Join Dementia Research (JDR) this was extended to the entire UK. One participant was not from the UK. She had previously lived in the UK and was recruited through JDR, which she had joined because there was no equivalent in the country where she resided.

4.2.1.5 Access to Technology

Participants needed to be able to use the technology necessary for an online interview. Though participants were welcome to have supporters with them to assist with the technology if required, access was also necessary in respect of having a reliable internet connection and a suitable device available. Due to the confidential nature of the interview, participants were unable to use a

¹⁰ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/analysis-relating-to-state-pension-age-changes-from-the-1995-and-2011-pensions-acts/analysis-relating-to-state-pension-age-changes-from-the-1995-and-2011-pensions-acts> [Access date 01/06/25]

computer in a public library or similar space, so access needed to be possible from their home (or other private location of their choosing).

4.2.1.6 Capacity to Consent

In Scotland, there is a “presumption of capacity and this can only be overturned where there is medical evidence stating otherwise” (Office of the Public Guardian (Scotland), Undated). Participants needed to have the capacity to understand and respond to the invitation to participate in the study, complete and return the consent form and use an online meeting channel; all indicating a level of cognitive capacity that confirms a ‘presumption’ that a participant understands their involvement. In addition, as part of the recruitment strategy I met with participants prior to interview. This provided an opportunity for myself as the researcher to discuss the research and participation requirements, ensuring that all participants clearly understood what the study was about and what involvement entailed. Participants were welcome to have a ‘supporter’ with them during the interview if they chose, and a separate information sheet and consent form were created for supporters (these can be found in Appendix Eight and Appendix Nine). Three participants chose to be interviewed with a supporter. Each supporter was the husband of the participant. Participants were reminded about the consent they had given before interviews commenced, as detailed in the *Interview Schedule* (Appendix Seven). Several participants had difficulty completing the consent form due to formatting on their device (for example, the boxes to initial not being visible). When participants experienced such difficulty, I read the consent statements to them verbally and asked them to confirm after each one, completing the form on their behalf. I then emailed the completed form to participants and asked them to respond by email to confirm their consent.

4.2.2 Recruitment

4.2.2.1 Recruitment Strategy

As participants for the research were women living with young-onset dementia, recruitment and data gathering were intentionally flexible and adaptable (Campbell, Dowlen and Fleetwood-Smith, 2023). A gatekeeper model of recruitment was used to recruit participants to this study.

Organisations working with potential participants were contacted and asked for their support with introducing the study to women living with young-onset dementia. These organisations were primarily those with existing relationships with the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice (ASCPP) at the University of the West of Scotland, which has been an established dementia research centre for over a decade. Whilst this did exclude potential participants not engaged with the gatekeeper organisations, this approach minimised the potential for coercion or pressure (however

unintentional) to influence participants. Participants would have opportunity to discuss with someone they had an existing relationship with, and raise any concerns or questions with them rather than myself if they preferred. It was important to involve and gain support from gatekeepers early in the research process (McFadyen and Rankin, 2016) and be proactive in preparation (Kay, 2019), so several potential gatekeepers were identified and contacted when ethical approval for the study had been granted.

Recruitment was planned in phases, the duration and number and number of which were dependent on the success of the preceding phase. It was important to manage recruitment so that sufficient participants took part in the study but also to avoid too many volunteering to participate within too short a time frame, because this would have made scheduling of interviews problematic (considering the degenerative nature of dementia). Proposed phases of recruitment were therefore:

- Phase one: Recruitment through Alzheimer Scotland (national charity with local groups, dementia cafes and resource centres; and home to the Scottish Dementia Working Group)
- Phase two: Recruitment through Age Scotland (national charity that has a broad scope with a specific focus on dementia through About Dementia)
- Phase three: Dementia Engagement and Empowerment Project (DEEP) and Young Dementia Network (organisations promoting involvement of those living with dementia in research)
- Phase four: Join Dementia Research (a database of people living with dementia and others who would like to participate in dementia-related research).

If insufficient numbers of participants were recruited through the four phases then alternatives were considered, such as promotion of the study through social media channels. Each phase of study involved contacting the organisation, introducing myself and the study, and discussing how they might support participant recruitment (such as sharing information about the study with individuals they knew or sharing in a news bulletin for members).

A minimum of two weeks between phases was planned, with flexibility for this time to be considerably longer should active recruitment be ongoing with an organisation. Should the maximum number of participants have been recruited during earlier phases, recruitment would have stopped before proceeding to the later phases. It was expected that the recruitment for the research would be ongoing for approximately six months from October 2023 (when ethical approval for the study was granted). This was extended to June 2024 as recruitment took longer than anticipated, with the twelfth and final interview in early July 2024.

4.2.2.2 Recruitment Administration

Recruitment adhered to the UK General Data Protection Regulations (2018). Potential participant's name and email address were recorded in accordance with GDPR so that a *participant information sheet* could be sent to them. The *participant information sheet* (Appendix Six) was also recorded in video form (via YouTube¹¹) in case this was the preferred format for receiving information (Wilbanks, 2018) and to make the information as accessible as possible. The sheet incorporated dementia friendly guidelines (DEEP, (2013)). I engaged with a 'critical friend' (a person living with young-onset dementia) and invited their feedback about study plans, particularly the language used to ensure it was accessible. The purpose of the friend was to ensure that insight from the lived experience of dementia was incorporated into the study, and to help me as a researcher develop plans that sensitively reflected the needs of those living with dementia. I also created a single-page summary of the study for gatekeeper organisations to use when discussing participation with potential participants (Appendix Ten). Gatekeepers were also sent a copy of the *participant object instructions* (Appendix Two) and *participant consent form* (Appendix Eleven). Following advice from the university's legal team, a *participant privacy notice* was also created, and was available for gatekeeper organisations or participants on request (Appendix Twelve).

Data management for this study adhered to all UWS guidelines, for example the UWS Code of Ethics (2020). The timing of ethical approval has significance because at the time of application the university was subject of a major criminal cyber incident that shut down IT systems across all departments, prompting a major review of data management procedures. These procedures were still in development at the time data collection for this study commenced, for example the UWS Code of Research Practice and Research Ethics was published in early 2025. Whilst the university now requires data management plans for research studies, this requirement was not in place at the time of data collection for this PhD and I detailed how I would manage data within the ethics application. Following the cyber incident I was required to modify data management in accordance with updated instruction from the university. Participant data, such as recordings and transcripts, were stored on my university 'one drive' with two factor authentication in place. A *participant privacy notice* (Appendix Twelve) was created as this was a requirement for all UWS-funded PhD studies. Advice and guidance were obtained from the university's legal team to develop this, and care was taken to ensure that the language was as clear and accessible as possible whilst compliant with the legal requirements.

¹¹ Available via this link: <https://youtu.be/zYziCfDJ83Y> [Access date 15/04/2025]

After sending a potential participant the *participant information sheet*, I planned to leave a minimum of three working days before follow-up contact. This was to be sensitive to potential memory difficulties, but also ensure that participants had opportunity to consider the information and not feel pressured by premature follow-up. Potential participants were offered the opportunity to meet with me online to discuss participation, ask questions and ensure they were comfortable using the technology required for the interview. This was also an opportunity for participants to ensure they felt comfortable communicating with me, to establish rapport and schedule the interview. I sought to accommodate participant preferences throughout in regards to scheduling of meetings and interviews as this was more likely to engage participants (Cridland *et al.*, 2016a) and meet their needs. However, in consideration of my own health needs and the need to cognitively process each interview, I planned to have a maximum of one interview per day and the day following each interview kept free to enable sufficient time to process my initial impressions and reflect. This plan also supported flexibility should participants have needed to reschedule at short notice.

Pseudonym Selection

After data gathering ended, participants were each assigned a pseudonym to ensure confidentiality when reporting the study. I considered using the objects participants chose as pseudonyms. However, I felt it was important participants were identified by names that reflected their female identities and lived experiences. I was also sensitive to names having attributes that may not reflect participant identities (for example, a name that is common for elderly people). I therefore adopted a creative approach to choosing pseudonyms. I noted the object participants chose along with a feature from crochet reflections I created following each interview (detailed in *Reflecting Through Crochet*), and looked up the Scottish Gaelic translations of these words. As I am not familiar with Scottish Gaelic, I used the letters or my guessed sounds from these words to form names generally understood to denote a female identity in the UK. This helped to ensure that the pseudonyms reflected elements of both the participants and my understanding of them.

4.2.3 Number of Participants

Discussion of sample size is problematic in qualitative research because data adequacy is more about the quality of data than number of participants (Hennink and Kaiser, 2022). Sample size is linked to the concept of data saturation, evolved from grounded theory, which is not appropriate for all types of qualitative research (Braun and Clarke, 2021). Saturation implies that no new insights or learning can be gained from further data, but this is theoretically incompatible with RTA because of the researcher's ongoing role in the interpretation process (Braun and Clarke, 2021). Quantifying the

number of participants required in advance of data gathering was difficult due to the adopted reflexive approach (Braun and Clarke, 2016), the need to consider the depth of data while data gathering was ongoing and the impossibility of quantifying the qualitative (especially in advance; Braun and Clarke (2021)).

The purpose of data gathering was to collect rich ‘thick’ data large enough to “justify claims regarding patterned meaning” (Braun and Clarke, 2022b, p. 13). Malterud, Siersma and Guassora (2015) have suggested the term ‘information power’ is more appropriate in qualitative studies than ‘saturation’, because the focus should be on the quality and depth of data rather than the quantity of data. Therefore, small sample sizes are appropriate in qualitative research (Hennink and Kaiser, 2022). As quality of dialogue in interviews is a contributory factor of the information power (Malterud, Siersma and Guassora, 2015), identifying the number of participants before data gathering started was not specific but rather a range, and needed to be flexible as the data gathering process progressed. It has been suggested that for a moderate sized study exploring experience, or understanding and perceptions, 10-20 participants are required (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Considering the need to balance ideals with practicalities (Braun and Clarke, 2022b), I sought to recruit 15-20 participants with a maximum limit of 22 (to ensure that the data could be analysed within the timescale for thesis submission and the amount of data was manageable). Having a sample range rather than target ensured I could respond flexibly as participant recruitment and interviews commenced (Robinson, 2014).

4.3 Data Gathering

Data in this study was gathered rather than collected. Collection implies that data was somehow passively waiting to be found and put together, whereas gathering more accurately reflects the researcher’s role in bringing data together and generating meaning from this (Braun and Clarke, 2019a). I sought to be sensitive to the needs of the participants as I considered the right method for data gathering. For example, avoiding a method that would be inaccessible or onerous but was also appropriate for addressing the research aim and objectives and exploring the complexities of career. The chosen data gathering method of semi-structured online interviews using object elicitation will now be discussed.

4.3.1 Interviews

Data gathering in qualitative research can be facilitated in various ways. Interactive methods include interviews and focus groups; and observation, secondary sources and written sources such as diaries

can also be used (Braun and Clarke, 2013). The chosen method of data gathering for this study was interviews. This was because interviews were appropriate for addressing the research aim and objectives, and I wanted a method that was sensitive to potentially emotive areas of career (such as family roles). This consideration meant that focus groups were not appropriate because data is generated within a group rather than individually (Niebauer *et al.*, 2020). A group interaction could potentially be difficult or distressing when individual perspectives and experiences differ. A group dynamic would have also undermined the exploration of an individual's experiences.

Whilst observation has been used as an inclusive approach within dementia research (Webb *et al.*, 2020), I was sensitive to the ethical considerations connected with observation and perhaps especially so because of my own negative experiences of being observed by medical personnel to verify my ME symptoms. Observation would also have prioritised my understanding or interpretation of the participant's reality rather than their own, which would have conflicted with the interpretivist ontology of this study. As career is a subjective entity, it could be argued that it is not observable in the sense that whilst tasks and activities could be observed, the meaning and importance of these is not known to the observer; nor how tasks and activities connect to the roles and stages of career. Bartlett (2012, p. 1718) used a diary method because this enabled "insights into a person's thinking, an inner world otherwise unknowable through participant observation alone", and I likewise considered how I could better understand what was 'unknowable'.

I considered emerging qualitative methods, such as a qualitative survey, but this would have limited flexibility to explore further with participants (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Therefore, a semi-structured interview was decided upon as the most appropriate method for data gathering. I also decided that interviews would take place online, innovating the traditional interview approach where interviewer and interviewee meet in an agreed physical location.

4.3.1.1 Practice Interviews

An interview schedule was developed for use in the interviews (Appendix Seven). Pilot testing interview schedules is recommended (Cridland *et al.*, 2016a), and practice interviews with the study's critical friend (a person living with dementia) and Depute Director at ASCPP were undertaken. These, along with advice from the university ethics committee, supported development and refining of the schedule. Whilst no formal pilot interviews were undertaken the interview schedule worked effectively during both the practice and initial interviews with participants and was therefore not edited further. The practice interviews were also a helpful opportunity to get feedback on my interview skills and gain confidence before interviews with participants commenced, for example through gaining familiarity with using the schedule in interviews (Cridland *et al.*, 2016b)

4.3.1.2 Online Interviews

The decision to organise interviews online was made in consideration of my needs as a researcher. Travel exacerbates my fatigue and therefore travelling would have undermined my ability to facilitate the interview. In addition, not having a car and difficulty with climbing stairs would have also made traveling and visiting unfamiliar locations difficult (for example, because I would need to ensure access to a toilet). As dementia causes fatigue (Bartlett, 2014), I did not feel comfortable asking participants to travel because of the possibility of travel exacerbating their fatigue. However, interviews needed to take place somewhere that was suitable (for example, private and without background noise); where participants felt comfortable and could have someone with them for support if they wanted. Online interviews enabled participants to participate in their own private space (Seitz, 2015) without the intrusion and disruption of a researcher visiting, and offered participants “greater control over the research environment” (Clarke and Braun, 2019, p. 25).

Using Teams to facilitate interviews ensured that practical and ethical considerations were balanced. Teams was chosen because it was the platform approved by the university and met data protection requirements. During recruitment a participant requested an interview using Zoom, because she found this to be more accessible than Teams. After checking that using Zoom was compliant with university requirements, I set up a university account and used this to undertake interviews when a participant preferred this. While traditional interviews may exclude those unable to travel (which is pertinent in Scotland, where many live in rural and remote locations), it is acknowledged that online interviews exclude those unable to access the internet or use the necessary technology. Data gathering commenced in Autumn 2023, in a post-pandemic context where many social groups and meetings had moved to online formats due to the necessity of social distancing regulations. It was therefore anticipated that online platforms would already be familiar with many potential participants. One participant preferred to be interviewed at a local dementia café, where a private room was available for us to speak, so this interview did not take place online.

Introductory Meeting

A preliminary introductory meeting with participants was incorporated into the data gathering design. Meeting prior to interview is recommended when interviewing people living with dementia (Cridland *et al.*, 2016b). The purpose of this was to identify any support needs and provide opportunity for participants to gain familiarity with both myself and the meeting software. Supporters were also welcome to attend the introductory meeting, and two participants preferred an introduction with their supporters by telephone. The meeting also provided an opportunity for the participants to ask questions and ensure they were comfortable speaking with me. We discussed

their preferred channel for interviews, Zoom or Teams. One participant preferred to be interviewed at her local Alzheimer Scotland Resource Centre and arrangements for this were made with her supporter. Participants had generally understood the *participant information sheet* (Appendix Six) and *object instructions* (Appendix Two), but sought reassurance that their chosen object was appropriate or asked me for further guidance about what to choose.

Towards the end of the introductory meeting, I asked participants if they were happy to arrange an interview date and time with me, or if they would prefer some more time to think about participating. I also checked with participants if they would find a reminder about the interview helpful so I could remind participants about interview arrangements in accordance with their preference. Participants were offered the option to have two shorter interviews rather than a longer one if they preferred. One participant indicated she might prefer this, though during her interview when asked if she was ok to continue, she replied that she was. This highlights the need for a flexible approach when interviewing people with chronic conditions such as dementia, as flexibility supports accessibility by accommodating fluctuating and unpredictable symptoms (Budworth, 2023).

4.3.1.3 Semi-Structured Interviews

The interview design promoted a conversational interview style reflecting the “flexible and fluid approach” compatible with RTA (Braun and Clarke, 2022b, p. 13). Semi-structured interviews are interviews with “a consistent set of questions or topics” (Blee and Taylor, 2002, p. 92). The form of the interview was akin to a “guided conversation” (Dicicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006, p. 315), which facilitated the exploratory nature of the study and avoided assumptions about what was important to participants. As both illness and career experiences are individual and contextual, the lack of set questions strengthened the data gathering process by allowing participants choice in how and if they referred to these potentially sensitive subjects.

As detailed in the *interview schedule* (Appendix Seven), each interview began with an introduction where I greeted the participant (and their supporter if present) and asked if they would like the consent form read to them again, if they were happy to continue participating and for me to record the interview. If a supporter was present, I thanked them for attending and reminded the supporter that questions would be addressed to the participant. I discussed taking a break with participants. All told me they were happy to verbalise if a break was needed, however no breaks were requested during interviews.

To begin the interview after recording had started, I asked all participants to confirm their name and age. I then asked about the object they had chosen to represent their career. Discussion then

developed from the object about their experiences. The *interview schedule* (Appendix Seven) included 'question prompts' to help support continued discussion. These were generally most useful at the beginning of the interview as we developed rapport and ease with one another. To end the interview, participants were asked if they had any career highlights. I included this in the *interview schedule* following feedback from the practice interview with the ASCPP Depute Director, to ensure interviews ended positively for participants. I then asked if there was anything else participants would like to share that we had not discussed. The length of interviews ranged from 46-93 minutes.

4.3.1.4 Object Elicitation

Object elicitation was chosen as the method for starting each interview. Participants were asked to bring an object to the interview that represented their career and tell me about it (detail about the objects participants chose, along with an image I created of the objects, is included in the *Findings* chapter). Using visual materials can help support a relaxed tone for interviews (Brown, 2019). As a less traditional method, object elicitation supports "mutuality and democracy" between the researcher and research participants (Aldridge, 2012, p. 122). Not all participants chose physical objects, for example one participant had forgotten to choose something but agreed her choice with her supporter as the interview began. Description and explanation of the choice meant that object elicitation was effective even without an object visually present.

Using object elicitation to begin interviews helped to ensure that interviews began positively, from a place of comfort for participants. Having to explain the object positioned the participant as the expert (Rainford, 2020) from the start of the interview. Participant's choice of object offered them control and enabled them to direct and pace discussion (Edwards and l'Anson, 2020) and control the initial agenda (Willig, 2017). Objects supported rapport building from the outset, encouraging the participants to talk during the initial phase of the interview (Dicicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006). Participants were not required to tell me about their choice of object in advance. This ensured that participants could adapt to how they may be feeling on the day or even the hour of the interview and allowed for improvisation (Pottinger *et al.*, 2022). In addition to the *participant information sheet*, further information and guidance was provided to support participants in choosing an object (Appendix Two).

I was inspired by the work of Guy and Banim (2000), who used wardrobe interviews in their research with women, and Buse and Twigg's (Buse and Twigg, 2014; Buse and Twigg, 2015a; Buse and Twigg, 2015b) research focused on dress and living with dementia. As dementia is a progressive condition, moving to a care home may be necessary as care needs increase. Buse and Twigg (2015b) described

how family carers supported this transition and decided what clothing would be kept or discarded. By using object elicitation, I sought to explore the meaning of participants' chosen objects in the context of career and living with dementia. Such meanings would only be known to participants unless articulated. By enhancing understanding of how our identities and experiences are connected to objects, better decision making and understanding may be facilitated when someone living with dementia can no longer articulate their emotional or sentimental connection to what they own and have.

"To uncover women's knowledge and skills that are hidden and/or undervalued, feminist scholars often make innovative use of research methods" (Brooks, 2011, p. 5). Using object elicitation in online interviews with people living with dementia was such an innovative approach. While the interviews did rely on verbal communication, the objects were a visual tool; similar to how photos have been used alongside interviews to prompt deeper thinking and expression (Glaw *et al.*, 2017). Object elicitation also enabled a sensory element to the interview as the participants had the option to touch, hold and interact with their object. Engaging the senses through using an object was a form of embodiment in the interview (Campbell, Dowlen and Fleetwood-Smith, 2023). As most interviews took place online and I was not present in the room with participants, the object facilitated a connection through the senses and a way of 'feeling' participant experiences (Campbell, Dowlen and Fleetwood-Smith, 2023) alongside hearing the participant's words.

It was expected that because of the recruitment of participants through gatekeepers, those participating may have had prior experience of involvement in research. This experience, and the need to perhaps plan what to say in advance because of memory or other dementia-related symptoms, can result in rehearsed narratives. Object elicitation can enable a deeper exploration of what has been rehearsed (Pottinger *et al.*, 2022). In her research with cancer patients living with terminal diagnosis, Willig (2017) found that object elicitation elicited "in the moment" unrehearsed reflections (Willig, 2017, p. 220) and "fresh engagement with lived experience" (Willig, 2017, p. 215). Using object elicitation was a tool to "make the familiar strange" through a visual element (Mannay, 2010, p. 95), and engage the senses (Woodward, 2020) in the interview. Instructions about choosing an object were produced (Appendix Two), as it was anticipated that as a creative approach participants may not have experienced this before. Examples of different objects from my own career were included as guidance so that I was not asking of participants something I was unwilling to do myself (Pottinger *et al.*, 2022), or ignorant of the potential emotional response that the process of choosing and discussing an object might trigger (Willig, 2017).

4.3.1.5 Ending Interviews

The risk of psychological harm and mitigation of psychological risk had been considered and detailed as part of my ethics application, and an extract detailing this section of the application has been included in Appendix Thirteen. Support for a participant experiencing distress during interviews was focused on ensuring participants could choose to stop, take a break or continue the interview. Inclusion of a final question about highlights of career (Appendix Seven) was designed to end interviews positively, and each interview was scheduled with free time afterwards, so that I was able to spend as long with participants as they wanted. The follow-up email also included the contact details of external sources of support, such as Alzheimer Scotland, in case participants would benefit from this.

After asking if there is anything further that participants would like to discuss, I would then advise participants that the interview was ending and stopped recording. With two participants, we continued discussion beyond the end of the interview. With one participant I decided to end the interview due to the duration (the longest interview, at 93 minutes). The participant wanted to continue talking about difficult and emotive aspects of her experience, and I felt an ethical tension (Schmid, Garrels and Skåland, 2024) between my role as a researcher gathering data and as a person caring about the woman I was speaking with and wanting to minimise her distress. Our discussion continued for more than 30 minutes after the interview, ending comfortably when the participant received a phone call from someone she wanted to speak to. I met with my supervisor following this interview, as I was unsure how to process both my concern for the participant and my own distress (Smillie and Riddell, 2023).

On reflection, when preparing for data gathering I had focused on participant wellbeing. Whilst I had considered the potential to be emotionally affected by interviews, I had not appreciated the specific ways in which this would challenge me. For example, the emotional connection I felt with participants and needing to accept the limitations of my role as researcher (Quinn *et al.*, 2024). The need to develop rapport with participants was necessary for their comfort and to support the gathering of rich data, but wasn't necessarily straightforward to detach from when interviews were completed (Quinn *et al.*, 2024). After ending the interview, I would advise participants that I would be sending a follow-up email and I asked how they were feeling. The follow-up email was sent as soon as was practical after the interview (usually within the hour) and specified the contact details of the Alzheimer Scotland helpline (or Alzheimer's Society for participants in England). The email also reminded participants of their right to withdraw from the research (and the applicable date two weeks from the interview). Participants were asked if they wanted to be kept informed about the

study as it progressed. All wanted to receive updates and consented for their email to be used for this purpose.

4.3.1.6 Interview Perspective

When interacting with an interviewer it is not possible to communicate all aspects of our truth. This is because it is not always possible to know the whole truth about ourselves, and this can be even more challenging when living with a cognitive impairment. Memory can be an unreliable source of information, even for those who are not living with dementia, because “all memory is shaped by cognition, culture, and context” (Nathan, Newman and Lancaster, 2019, p. 396) and what is true for an individual may not be subjectively accurate or factual. Feelings are also not static and change, and perspectives can alter with time and further construction through interactions with others and further experience. In addition, it isn’t always possible to verbalise what we feel and experience (Reavey and Johnson, 2008). As two individuals, the participant and myself each brought our own dynamics (Pottinger *et al.*, 2022) into the construction of the interview to facilitate “co-construction of meaning between researcher and participant” (Braun and Clarke, 2022b, p. 13) during our time together. The aim of the interviews was to gather participant perspectives on their careers in the context of living with young-onset dementia, whilst recognising that their perspectives would be incomplete because their careers were continuing to evolve and change.

4.3.1.7 Transcription

All participants consented to have their interview recorded (both picture and sound). Teams and Zoom automatically generate a script when producing a recording and I edited these to ensure the transcript was an accurate reflection of the interview dialogue. The interview that took place at a local dementia cafe was recorded using Teams so that the transcription method was consistent with all interviews.

I completed all transcription manually. Transcripts were verbatim, however repetitions of single words were limited to three per incidence (to enhance readability). Sections of dialogue that were inaudible were indicated with ‘[unclear]’ in the transcript. Such sections were listened to several times, and the picture recording and slower speed function used to try and distinguish unclear words or phrases. The grammatical approach sought to reflect the pace and inflection of speech as I understood it (for example, not using full stops when it may have been grammatically correct to do so and adding commas to aid readability during longer sections of speech). Transcripts were anonymised during the editing process, using ‘P’ and a number to ensure the consent form and transcript were consistent (pseudonyms were adopted during analysis). Where participants named

individuals or other potentially identifying information, names were replaced in square brackets with the relationship to the participant, such as '[nurse]' or '[son]'. As a lengthy process, each interview transcription took place in stages and was then reviewed when complete for a final accuracy check. Transcripts were therefore thoroughly read before initial coding took place (Watts, 2014); this aided the early stages of analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

4.4 Analysis

Analysis is the stage of the research where the researcher uses the data to answer the research question (Brown, 2019) or address the research aims and objectives. It involves organising and interpreting the data (Creswell, 2018). Thematic analysis is used in qualitative research to generate themes from the data that help to summarise and explain what was found out through the research. Reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) is a form of thematic analysis and was used to analyse the data in this study. RTA is part of a “family of methods that are focussed on developing and reporting themes from qualitative data” (Braun and Clarke, 2024a, p. 609).

4.4.1 Reflexive Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis can be used across research paradigms, but problems arise when the type of thematic analysis does not align with the research paradigm. For example, RTA is “big Q” thematic analysis, meaning that it is fully qualitative and is therefore suitable for qualitative methodologies within an interpretive paradigm (Braun and Clarke, 2023, p. 699). Other types of thematic analysis such as codebook or coding reliability reflect more mixed or postpositivist methodology (Braun and Clarke, 2023). What is now known as RTA was introduced as thematic analysis by Braun and Clarke (2006); most approaches using thematic analysis at that time were not fully qualitative and more aligned with a postpositive rather than interpretative methodology (Braun and Clarke, 2024a). Finlay (2021, p. 104) has suggested that thematic analysis can be “scientifically descriptive” or “artfully interpretive” and RTA aligns with the latter, where creativity and reflexivity are integral to the approach. RTA is distinct from other thematic analysis approaches in several ways, for example through not equating the quantity of data with its importance relating to themes, and the researcher’s involvement in the analysis process.

In RTA, the purpose of analysis is not to discover ‘truth’ but to interpret; the focus is on the journey rather than arrival at findings (Braun and Clarke, 2019a). Themes do not exist pre-analysis but are interpreted and created by the researcher (Braun and Clarke, 2019a; Braun *et al.*, 2019b; Braun and Clarke, 2023). In RTA, the researcher’s subjectivity is “a resource for knowledge production” (Braun

and Clarke, 2020a, pp. 7-8) rather than an uninvited bias or influence, requiring bracketing or other separation from the data.

A theme consists not of a common topic but of a shared meaning, and is “crafted by researchers actively developing and generating themes through labour-intensive open analytic processes” (Braun and Clarke, 2024a, p. 613). Themes are not superficial or generalised topic summaries (Braun and Clarke, 2024a), but bring together aspects of shared meaning that only a thorough and in-depth analysis could articulate. The stages of this in-depth analysis are detailed in the *Phases of Analysis* section of this chapter.

4.4.1.1 Reflexive Practice

Reflexive practice or openness is an important component of both RTA (Braun and Clarke, 2024a) and feminist research. Researcher reflexivity ensures that the analysis process is one that includes the combination of myself as the researcher, the data and variety of interpretation (Braun and Clarke, Undated). Feminist approaches challenge the positivist criteria of a detached and neutral relationship between the researcher and those they research, advocating instead for a relationship where information is mutually shared and acknowledgement that those participating in research know more than the researcher (England, 1994). Researcher reflexivity is therefore integral to a feminist approach because the researcher and the researched relationship influences data collection. It is not a detached or distanced process but connected with the researcher’s “self in process” (Greene and Griffiths, 2003, p. 80). The reflexive and personal is “a hallmark of feminist approaches” (Thomas, 1999, p. 68). Creative methods are used by feminist researchers, particularly in research involving oppressed women (and those living with young-onset dementia could be considered to be oppressed), to access stories and experiences that traditional interview methods, such as interviews or surveys, may miss (Brooks, 2011) and to avoid conforming to (and implicitly validating) norms in research that don’t necessarily fit with feminist approaches (Clarke and Braun, 2019). For research to be feminist, what is normal or usual needs to be critically examined and rethought (Greene and Griffiths, 2003).

Reflexion was continual during data gathering and recorded in writing at specific stages following interviews. These stages were after the interview (either later that day or the following day, depending on the timing of the interview), after relistening to the interview (usually the following day) and during interview transcription. Creating these notes helped me to familiarise myself with the data and explore the thoughts and feelings it provoked at different time periods following the interview. It also helped me to process the interview, particularly the emotional responses that

interviews provoked, enabling me to work through such responses so I could better explore the data. For example, when coding the reflexive notes I created a *to do with me* code, where I noted what I called ‘pings’. These were examples from my notes where I felt I could especially relate to the participant’s experience or feelings. Acknowledging these responses supported my analytic focus on what was important in the data; bringing myself into the process without being in the way of it.

In addition to written notes, I also used crochet, modelling and art as part of the analysis process. Being able to *do* as well as write supported my creative thinking during analysis, allowing me to explore and approach the data with different perspectives. Creativity was also a way I practised self-care during the data collection and analysis process. For example, my art journal was not part of the analysis process. It was an activity that helped to calm my mind, and allowed me to take a step back and maintain a healthier balance during the intensity of the different phases of the research.

4.4.2 Phases of Analysis

How to process, analyse and interpret data is “very much a subjective choice” (Brown, 2019, p. 35) and “reflect the questioning activities of the researcher” (Watts, 2014, p. 4). Analysis should be based on the data but go further than what can be found on the surface (Braun and Clarke, 2006). To achieve this, Braun *et al.* (2019b) suggest six phases of RTA. These six phases may not necessarily be linear steps due to reflexive nature of the process. The phases may overlap, blend and mature recursively (Braun and Clarke, 2020a) and are focused on interpretation (Braun and Clarke, 2020a). The six phases are familiarisation, generating codes, constructing themes, revising themes, defining themes and producing the report (Braun *et al.*, 2019b). Working through the phases can be considered more of an art rather than a “mechanical application of protocol” (Finlay, 2021, p. 106). Further detail about how I undertook each of these phases now follows:

4.4.2.1 Phase One: Familiarisation

From the first interview, I developed a structure to support the familiarisation stage of analysis. Each interview was listened to a minimum of three times: usually the day following interview, during transcription, and then after transcription to check the transcript with the recording. Reflective notes were usually taken following the interview (specifically when was dependent on the timing of the interview), relistening to the recording the following day, and during transcription. I recognised that the way I process emotions, particularly when distressing or difficult, needed time. I therefore took a flexible approach to the timing of familiarisation in consideration of the emotionally demanding nature of the research (Smillie and Riddell, 2023). For example, I delayed relistening to one interview to give myself additional time to process the emotional impact from it.

Reflecting Through Crochet

Recognising that thinking and reflecting about data is not always conscious or engaged (Brown, 2019) and is a “combination of science and art, rigour and creativity” (Watts, 2014, p. 11), I sought to capture reflections not only in writing but also through crochet. Inspired by Clare Danek, who used a ‘stitch journal’ to enhance her reflexivity during her PhD research¹², and Harrison and Ogden (2020)’s discussion of femininity, creative skills and women’s work in relation to knitting, I decided to use crochet to support the familiarisation stage of data collection. Brown (2019) created a poem and art installation as part of her reflective process, creating something that combined participant data and researcher reflections. Crochet was a way I could combine the data with my reflections, and also a method of embodying the data; creating something that could be touched, felt and seen. Braun and Clarke (2020a, p. 5) have stated that “the analytic process involves immersion in the data, reading, reflecting, questioning, imagining, wondering, writing, retreating, returning”, and crochet provided a mechanism of engaging with each of these actions. Conscious thoughts guide and create writing, whereas crochet enabled me to think through my fingers. As I focused on the ‘doing’ of crochet I was able to express and articulate ideas that writing alone may not have captured.

After each interview, usually when transcription was completed, I crocheted a line to represent the interview. I utilised my extensive ‘yarn stash’ (existing collection of crochet materials) to facilitate choices of yarn, colour, and stitch and used written notes to explain and explore these choices. Each line was labelled with a keyword linking the interview data to the crochet. The crochet reflections were sewn into a poster, which has been included below (Figure 4). This ‘work in progress’ was presented during the data gathering phase of the research at the UWS Research Festival in May 2024, and this prompted interesting discussions about how we understand and respond to data in a qualitative context.

¹² <https://claredanek.me/stitch-journal/> (April 2020) [access date 01/06/2025]

Figure 4: Crochet Poster

Crochet is a type of craft that is similar to knitting. Knitting uses two needles, whereas crochet uses a single hook. Stitches are created by threading yarn through fingers and the hook in particular ways to create different shapes and patterns. I would describe my crochet skill level as an ‘intermediate beginner’, and it is an activity I do most days. I find the repetitive muscle movements calming and the making process positive as it can transcend fatigue, enabling my mind to yield alternative insights that the focus required for writing reflexively might hinder.

Fleetwood-Smith describes reflecting using words but also through “visual journaling” in her ‘method story’ detailing her dementia research (Fleetwood-Smith, Tischler and Robson, 2021, p. 5). Using crochet to facilitate reflexivity and familiarisation of the data set is part of my method story, and reflects my involvement as a researcher in the analysis process because I used the crochet to think through my fingers and interact with the data through vision and touch. This enabled me to better understand how I was responding to or processing the interview data, sometimes confirming my understanding through transcription and sometimes presenting alternative perspectives. For example, when crocheting Elle’s reflective piece, I realised that the ‘cloud’ shape I had constructed was a way of representing the sense of elevation I felt from her data. As a cloud is elevated above the ground, so I felt Elle’s experiences were elevated, somehow transcendent from the difficult circumstances she had described.

During transcription I considered how to visually represent the data through crochet. For example, Clare chose a 'tree of life' necklace as her object to represent her career and returned to this metaphorically at several points during the interview. I therefore crocheted a branch with brown wool, adding green leaves to literally reflect the tree of life. Other representations were more abstract, such as Ruth's interview. She spoke about the importance of voice, and I visualised the image of sound waves and the bars on a volume control, and chose a fluffy yarn with lots of loose strands to be a visual depiction of voice. By using crochet, the data were not only represented visually but also through touch, which can "bring consciousness to interactions that are often subconscious" (Zino *et al.*, 2021, p. 12). Using a combination of reflective notes and crochet, I was able to familiarise and reflect on the data in writing, visually and through touch; each form of thinking contributing to a thorough foundation to develop analysis further.

I also found crochet an invaluable way to remember the data. Much of the familiarisation stage of analysis was undertaken whilst data collection was ongoing, and this required multitasking and overlapping of recruitment, organisation, transcription and reflection of interviews. The distinct lines of crochet helped me to remember the individuality of each interview, not only the content that was discussed but the participant's face, expressions, tone and the feelings I experienced when we spoke. Writing needs to be read, and audio heard, but the crochet was instantly accessible to me through sight and touch. Having created each line of reflection the thinking that went into the making was entwined with the stitches; and by looking at and touching the lines I could recall and describe each interview in detail.

4.4.2.2 Phase Two: Coding

During data collection, when interviews had been transcribed and quality checked, I uploaded the transcripts to Nvivo 12. Nvivo is a software package that supports data analysis and organisation, and was chosen for pragmatic reasons; it was supported by the university and had accessible training in how to use it available. Prior to data collection, I undertook Nvivo training with the University of East Anglia and also attended webinars hosted by Lumivero (the software owners) about using Nvivo to support RTA. I created cases (or codes) by highlighting sections of the transcript and assigning or creating a code that described that section of text.

Semantic Coding

Figure 5: Example of Semantic Coding

The image above is an excerpt from Penny's transcript. The highlighted text was coded to 'career artefacts', because Penny and her supporter were telling me why she chose marker pens to represent her career. Initially, I used my research question and prominent areas from the literature review to guide the coding process deductively.

When all interviews had been completed and coded, I then refined these codes "systematically and thoroughly" (Braun and Clarke, 2022a, p. 35). I had learned from the crochet reflections that having a visual way of representing and exploring the analysis was important for me, and I bought a concertina sketch book to use as an analysis diary. This also provided another outlet for me to think with my fingers, and record thoughts or reflections informally so I could better understand how the analysis was progressing. I experimented with using quotes from participants, my own thoughts, doodles and drawings as well as recording the coding I was doing using Nvivo. I found this approach helped me to mentally hold and make sense of the dataset as a whole and in parts at the same time (Campbell Galman, 2022). Using the analysis diary in this way, and adopting a creative and flexible approach to how I used it, enabled "kinesthetic questioning" (Campbell Galman, 2022, p. 400). I was asking questions not only of the data, but of myself, and the story that was beginning to be generated from the data.

As the physical environment can affect thinking (Oakley and Sejnowski, (Undated)), I ensured that my analysis was undertaken in different places. As travel often exacerbates my ME symptoms, I work most effectively from home. However, home has several limitations. It is an environment that is familiar, often lacks natural light and does not have outside space. As phase two was underway I visited friends in Cumbria and worked in their garden, and felt the different sensory experience there (for example, hearing birdsong and feeling the sun and breeze on my skin) enabled me to think and focus differently and enhanced the connections and understandings that I was forming. I summarised my thinking during this week using pictures as a form of metaphor to represent the analysis. Thinking through metaphors can be an alternative to traditional academic analysis processes and facilitate questions,

but openness is important to ensure that metaphors don't become a barrier or hinder the imagination (Greene and Griffiths, 2003). I also met with a career guidance professional from Skills Development Scotland (SDS) to discuss my analytical progress, which supported my thinking through an alternative physical and contextual space.

Latent Coding

"Coding in [RTA] ranges from semantic to latent" (Braun and Clarke, 2022a, p. 57). Semantic codes relate more to meaning derived from what participants actually said, whereas latent codes are more conceptual and include the researcher's interpretation of what participants meant. These two approaches are not necessarily distinct and coding can reflect elements of both (Braun and Clarke, 2022a). To explore more latent meaning in the data, I uploaded my reflexive notes from each interview to Nvivo and coded these for more conceptual meaning. An example of this is included below (Figure 6). I created a code, *grey moments*, for when I had a sense of sadness from the data:

Figure 6: Example of Latent Coding

Grey moments contributed to theme development. I experimented with representing different aspects of my notes in visual ways, such as diagrams depicting the links I had noted between interviews. I felt it was important to reflect on these notes in a different environment, so went to a local coffee shop and again summarised my reflective notes with pictures. One of these, the 'peer of dementia' (which can be found in the *Findings* chapter), was helpful to summarise multiple strands of thought that needed further reflection.

Recognising that writing was part of the analysis process and necessary for me to progress through the phases of the process, I began 'writing up' by exploring the object choices of participants. I felt that discussing these choices was an accessible way of starting to write because participants had explained their choices during interview, and therefore the reflexive element of the process was structured by the participants' words.

4.4.2.3 Phase Three: Generating Initial Themes

To begin phase three, I extended my writing about the chosen objects to start discussing some initial themes. I used the visual representations as a route into this so I could start exploring via the keyboard rather than the pencil. As I was writing, I felt the need to return to creativity again to support ideas as they were developing.

Clay and Collage

I used creative ways of thinking to support the writing process. I needed to explore ways of understanding the data that enabled analysis through and within profound fatigue. For example, when writing about peer support I wanted to extend the image of a pier that I had previously drawn and create something more tangible and 3D, because of the multiple aspects of peer support I was exploring. I created a model using silk clay to support my exploration of this.

Bröckerhoff and Seregina (2022) used collage as a reflexive approach to rethink and conceptualise their data. While I had used some collage techniques in my personal art journal, inspired by Bröckerhoff and Seregina (2022) I created a collage on my desk, using 3D elements such as silk clay and bubble wrap to capture the data in a way that was not fixed or stuck (Appendix Four). When constructing the collage, I used images and shapes that I felt were right rather than planning and thinking the elements of the collage through in advance. After constructing the collage and photographing it, I made notes in my analysis diary about the different elements of the collage and also shared this photo with two colleagues and noted their responses. Creating the collage was helpful in deconstructing my linear and formalised approach to the data, which I felt had been a barrier to generating deeper and further insights.

Poetry

Inspired by Van Rooyen and D'Abdon (2020) I returned to the words of the interview transcripts using poetry, exploring poems as an alternative way of seeing the participants' words (Woodward, 2020). Like collage, poetry was also unfamiliar to me and would therefore compliment my visual exploration with a text-based approach. The poems also created an opportunity to go back to the original transcripts for further familiarity. I created a poem for each participant, reading through the transcript and selecting lines of text that struck me as I read. For some poems, I also included lines from my reflections, so that the poems would include both the participant's words and mine. I decided to use different forms to create the poems, for example cutting and pasting electronically and physically cutting and sticking paper; and also using acrostic, free form, storytelling and combining interviews to explore the words and meaning in the transcripts. The poems were not

intended to reflect the transcribed interviews but rather to deconstruct and present the data in an alternative way, to explore the potential to generate meaning by exploring the data from an innovative angle to encourage imaginative engagement (Van Rooyen and D'Abdon, 2020). Creating the poems enabled me to stay engaged, through 'play' rather than a more formal analysis with the data, during a period of extreme fatigue when both reading and writing were excessively challenging.

I have included an example poem below, using the transcripts of two interviews that had left me with lasting emotional responses:

Figure 7: Example Poem

I chose to create the poem in this form because I wanted to imagine how an interaction between these two participants might influence my response to the data. This somewhat abstract way of bringing the data together helped me better interpret meaning. It helped to clarify how each interview was more mixed in respect of what was said by participants than I had previously appreciated, and that though the feelings the interviews evoked were disparate, both participants told me about positive and negative aspects of their experience. For example, the quotation "I've got a tremendous amount of pain" was said in a positive context because the participant was telling me about ways she was trying to stay healthy and active, masking the reality of the participant's daily struggle. In the fifth line, one participant says "I would have thought at 60, I'd be at the top of

my career” and this is followed by the other saying “we make our plans and God laughs at us”; both participants were expressing in different ways the shared experience of future plans changing and the present not being what had previously been expected.

One way that using creative approaches such as poetry and crochet enhanced the rigour of the analysis process was through the way they facilitated enhanced engagement with the data (Koch and Harrington, 1998). Koch and Harrington (1998) have argued that rigour in qualitative research needs to be focused on the researcher’s reflexive approach and process of analysis, and therefore description of the creative approaches that supported my thinking and connection with the data have been detailed.

4.4.2.4 Phase Four: Developing and Reviewing Themes

In my reporting of findings, I was developing the theme *The Peer of Dementia* and another more focused on employment, and had started drafting a specific subtheme about Stigma. Stigma is an example of subtheme that I identified was more interesting than important, because it wasn’t contributing to “a convincing and compelling story about a pattern of shared meaning” (Braun and Clarke, 2022a, p. 35). I was also influenced by a blog post from Kate Swaffer¹³, in that whilst it was important to include participants’ experiences of stigma in the findings, this subtheme wasn’t adding anything new or helpful but could potentially do so as part of the ‘story’ in another subtheme(s).

I identified quotes to support the theme titles and help me to articulate the central organising concept (Braun and Clarke, 2022a) for each theme. I then sought supervisory feedback on this early draft of the *Findings*, which allowed me to pause and then continue with phase five of the analysis to scrutinise the themes further.

4.4.2.5 Phase Five: Refining, Defining and Naming Themes

During phase five I changed the order of the *Findings* chapter and used more subheadings to better organise the story of the themes and subthemes. Through this I identified better links between the theme concepts and was able to improve titles for the themes and subthemes to capture and describe what they were about. I revised my use of quotations. I ensured they were carefully selected and embedded in a way that provided context, and supported how I had understood and interpreted the data.

Following feedback from my supervisor, I went back to my findings and focused on ensuring the ‘story’ of the data was strengthened by better incorporating the interpretive process that I had

¹³ <https://kateswaffer.com/2024/09/20/dementia-advocacy-is-it-broken/> (2024) [access date 01/06/25]

undertaken. I named the themes, with synopses of each. The theme names were developed from the data, using words participants had used to describe their experiences in a way that summarised the essence of the theme or subtheme.

4.4.2.6 Phase Six: Writing Up

I completed the final drafts of the *Findings* chapter in accordance with feedback from my supervisor. A key change made during this phase was the structure of the chapter, which changed from the original approach. I used a creative writing style that was more relatable and made the findings more readable. I presented my findings at a staff network event at the University of the West of Scotland, supporting my understanding of what the important aspects of my findings were and how they could meet the quality criteria of being relevant and resonant (Finlay, 2021).

Braun and Clarke (2022a) suggest that when writing up during phase six the researcher needs to refine and finish, however “doing TA well” (Braun and Clarke, 2022a, p. 36) means letting go of a linear or fixed approach and going ‘back’ to earlier phases if need be. During this final phase of analysis the *Findings* were subject to what I describe as ‘jiggling’, where earlier phases of the process were repeated to further refine themes and bring out the story of the analysis. This was most prominent in the second theme, where most subthemes were renamed and there was substantial reorganisation. In the first theme, the third subtheme *Letting Loose* was also substantially jiggled to better reflect its different elements. As a final revision, I further refined the sections *Alternative Work* and *(Dis)enabled to Contribute* by revisiting the organising concept for these subthemes and jiggling further to ensure the distinction between the two, which are connected but different, was clearer.

4.5 Methods Summary

This *Methods* chapter has detailed how I gathered and analysed data for this study. Participants were recruited through several gatekeeper organisations and the interview approach consisted of semi-structured online interviews using object elicitation. Transcription of interviews provided a basis for initial data familiarisation, which then progressed through six phases of RTA and included creative elements. The findings generated through the analysis process will now be presented.

5. Findings

5.1 Introduction to Findings

This chapter presents the findings of the study through two major themes, generated through RTA (reflexive thematic analysis). These two themes are *The Career Tree* (*Working Differently*, *Making Champagne* and *Letting Loose*) and *Dementia Peers and Professionals* (*Lifting Each Other*, *Being Able to be Honest* and *All I'm Worth*). Each subtheme is structured into sections which reflect the characteristics of each subtheme (Braun and Clarke, 2022a). Figure 8 below visually represents the two major themes, six subthemes and their sections:

Figure 8: Major themes and subthemes

The chapter begins by introducing the participants before the findings are reported in detail, ending with a short summary.

The use of the term and title *Findings* is used here to comply with thesis convention and submission requirements, and should not be interpreted as an understanding that I “found”, ‘discovered’ or ‘identified’ pre-existing themes” (Braun and Clarke, 2024b, p. 5). This *Findings* chapter details the outcome of the analysis process described in the previous chapter. Whilst *The Career Tree* has a

greater word count than *Dementia Peers and Professionals*, in keeping with the RTA ‘Big Q’ approach, quantity of words is not an indicator of relative importance (Braun and Clarke, 2022a).

5.1.1 Participant Introduction

Twelve participants were interviewed for this study. They were recruited from a variety of gatekeeper organisations, as detailed in the *Methods* chapter. A table detailing participants’ names (pseudonyms), ages, employment background, the objects they chose to represent their careers, and whether they were interviewed with a supporter is included below (Table 5); followed by short introductions to each participant with further details about each of their respective careers.

Participant	Age	Employment Background(s)	Object	Interviewed with Supporter?
Bea	61	Hospitality and administration	Framed photograph of daughter	Yes
Beth	59	Law and social work	Saxophone	No
Clare	75	Healthcare	‘Tree of Life’ necklace	No
Darcy	54	Education and administration	Starbucks coffee cup	No
Elle	61	Healthcare and social work	Project publication	No
Fay	62	Education	Pocket watch/ locket	No
Fiona	68	Retail	Mobile phone	No
Iona	59	Administration	Multitasking picture	No
Leanne	68	Hospitality and charity	Childhood book	No
Penny	64	Management and education	Flipchart paper and marker pens	Yes
Ruth	51	Healthcare	BSL sign for ‘voice’	No
Tabitha	63	Finance and charity	Metallica CD	Yes

Table 5: Participant Characteristics

Short introductions to each participant now follow, in alphabetical order:

5.1.1.1 Bea

Bea and her supporter met with me at a dementia cafe for our interview. She had chosen a framed photograph of her daughter on her graduation day as her career object, and we started by discussing this before she told me about how she had begun working in hospitality and her roles in hotels. After having her daughter, Bea started working for a school and developed dementia whilst in employment there. She needed to reduce her hours and found her role stressful, particularly the need to multitask, which she had previously been able to do very well. It took approximately 18 months to be offered a “package to leave”. Bea told me about how she now enjoys aquafit, rock choir and going on holidays.

5.1.1.2 Beth

Beth had previously worked in probation and social work roles, and was working as a solicitor when she had a stroke at home and subsequently developed dementia. Our interview took place shortly before her 60th birthday, and she was finding it difficult to understand this because the years leading to this milestone age had been very different since the stroke; she had been “laid up upstairs” for about a year. She had only just begun to receive professional support following her dementia diagnosis, and was finding the impact of dementia on her routines, finances and home challenging to navigate. She chose her saxophone as her object because she had been playing it since the age of three, and she would not be “separated from it” even though she had forgotten how to play it as well as she had before.

5.1.1.3 Clare

Clare used her object, a “tree of life” necklace, as a metaphor to describe her career journey and the different branches she had experienced throughout her life. Professionally, she’d had her first job in an office and then left this role to join the armed forces, where she trained to be a nurse. Her army role ended when she married and had her daughter, who needed additional care. Clare also cared for her husband when he developed dementia and told me how she had made “champagne out of the bloody dementia” through her advocacy work. We discussed the meaning of career during our interview and how her roles as nurse, mother, carer and person with dementia had all been part of her career ‘tree’.

5.1.1.4 Darcy

Darcy relocated to the middle east after marrying her husband and had stayed to be close to her (adult) children, though her parents were in the USA and she visited them regularly. Her chosen object was a Starbucks coffee cup, which had significance for her because she'd bought it when she started her job as a preschool manager. She had started to develop problems with her memory in this job, and when the school closed during the pandemic this was her "escape". She is missed from the school, and they message her "all the time". Darcy had also previously taught music and craftwork at a local arts centre, and was continuing to enjoy various craftwork activities and cooking at home.

5.1.1.5 Elle

Elle had recently received her hard copy of a report that she had been working on with a university at the time of our interview and she chose this as her object. She got involved with their "experts by experience" group within a few months of her diagnosis and enjoyed being involved in research; ensuring that professionals were enabled to have a person-centred approach to supporting people living with dementia was very important to her. She had started her own young-onset support group after finding none were available in her area. She had originally trained as a nurse, and then when her children were older went to university and qualified as a social worker. She had enjoyed this role, working with older people, but had "no support at all" when her dementia symptoms started. After leaving her social work job it was over five years before she received her dementia diagnosis, and during this period she had tried to find alternative employment but was "turned down every time".

5.1.1.6 Fay

Fay had wanted to be a teacher since early childhood, and she had worked as a teacher and then a depute¹⁴ for over 37 years. She spoke about the significance of individuals to her career, such as her parents who had supported her to go to university. They had given her a pocket watch/ locket (her chosen object) with a rose design as a graduation gift and encouraged her that "this is now your time", and the "precious commodity" of time had been important throughout her career. She had been reluctant to retire from work when she developed dementia, but now felt more positively about this. She told me that getting her dog and being part of a peer support group had been

¹⁴ Depute is the short form of depute head teacher in Scotland. Elsewhere in the UK, deputy head teacher is generally used.

significant “turning points” for her since diagnosis, and she enjoyed being involved in research and different projects, such as an intergenerational project with nursery children.

5.1.1.7 Fiona

Fiona had a diagnosis of dementia with lewy bodies, which had been diagnosed after being admitted to hospital with hallucinations. She had lived with epilepsy since childhood, and we discussed her experience of both stigmatised conditions in our interview. Fiona had been upset by being treated differently by others because of her dementia diagnosis. Fiona had wanted to talk to others with young-onset dementia so she could better understand her experiences, but had not been able to access this form of support. Her dogs were a comfort for her, and they helped her to relax. She chose her mobile phone as her object because she used it to call others and it had photos on it of those she loved, such as her family and her dogs. She had previously been employed as a chocolatier and had enjoyed this very much, but had needed to leave this role because of her epilepsy prior to developing dementia.

5.1.1.8 Iona

Iona had chosen a picture of a person with multiple arms doing different tasks (representing multitasking) as her object to represent her career. She had worked in administration roles for different employers and felt that multitasking summed up her employment experiences. She had been told to stop work when she was diagnosed with dementia and found this “shocking”; she had been working since she left school and enjoyed doing so. We discussed how since developing dementia she was continuing to multitask, but not using as many arms as the picture she had chosen depicted. Iona was involved in several dementia groups focused on advocacy and research. She told me that speaking at a dementia conference had been a career highlight, along with traveling with her sisters. She also loved music, and through a dementia café had connected with a choir that she loved being part of.

5.1.1.9 Leanne

Leanne chose a book she had been given as a child as her object, and this reflected her passion for reading and travel. She had worked in the travel industry for many years, had travelled around the world, and had also worked in multiple countries. She’d had a “great summer”, traveling to Europe and the USA. Leanne was the only participant in paid employment at the time of our interview. She worked part-time in administration (and also volunteered) for a local charity. She described her work as “an absolute joy most of the time”. During our interview Leanne reflected on how she had gained

confidence through dementia, and she gave the example of speaking publicly at a dementia conference as an example of this.

5.1.1.10 Penny

Penny and her supporter had forgotten to select an object before our interview, but decided that flip chart paper and marker pens would reflect her role as a trainer. Penny had been responsible for delivering training for an organisation covering a wide area of Scotland and it had been a role she really enjoyed. When her dementia symptoms started, she had tried to discuss concerns with her manager but kept being told she was working well, so Penny resigned. After a difficult period of depression and waiting for a diagnosis (which took about 18 months), Penny was encouraged to go to a local resource centre by her link worker (part of the post-diagnostic support offered to those in Scotland) and from there “everything was on the up”. She enjoyed keeping active with her supporter and felt a positive aspect of developing dementia was the new friends and experiences she had gained.

5.1.1.11 Ruth

Ruth had been diagnosed with frontotemporal dementia (FTD) and explained that this affected her speech. She chose the British Sign Language (BSL) sign for ‘voice’ for her object because she had been “passionate” about using her voice from a young age. She had been working in the NHS as a support worker when she developed dementia, and told me about how her job had been “taken” from her. Though she hadn’t been able to continue her paid role, she had a voluntary role with the same NHS trust to promote dementia awareness and felt more support could have enabled her to continue her paid role for longer. Having felt “written off” since her diagnosis, Ruth had started taking and sharing photos as a form of ‘voice’. Her work has been exhibited and featured on the local news.

5.1.1.12 Tabitha

Tabitha had started working for a bank when she left school and had worked there for many years. When she developed dementia she had been working for a health charity supporting people in group settings, and her supporter felt this meant she found it a “difficult bridge to cross” to now participate in dementia support groups. She chose a CD to represent her career because it was something she’d “always had about the house”. Family was important to her; she had cared for her father (and received her diagnosis shortly after he died) and went out with her sister every week. Tabitha also loved her dogs and enjoyed walking them. She had Alzheimer’s Disease, which had

initially been misdiagnosed as vascular dementia. Her career highlight was her wedding day at the family farm, where there had been lots of music and dancing.

5.1.2 Participant's Objects

A drawing of the objects participants chose to represent their careers can be found below (Figure 9). This drawing was created during the familiarisation phase of analysis and supported my visual and creative approach to data analysis:

Figure 9: Participant Object Choices

5.2 Theme One: The Career Tree

(Working Differently, Making Champagne and Letting Loose)

5.2.1 Introduction to The Career Tree

This theme explores the ways that participants were continuing their careers while living with young-onset dementia, with a focus on how dementia had changed participants' career trajectories.

Past employment roles continued to be important for facilitating new opportunities after paid work had ended, and for taking on new challenging roles when living with a diagnosis. Participants had differing experiences of leaving paid employment. Lack of control at this career stage contrasted with the choices they were able to make as they moved on from the traumatic and difficult period following diagnosis. The naming of this theme was inspired by Clare, who used her 'tree of life' necklace to speak about the importance of her "good roots" and "branching out" in her career. The roots of pre-diagnosis continued to facilitate career branches post-diagnosis.

5.2.1.1 Working Differently

"... You need to work a little bit differently, and people around you just need to accept that you need to work a little bit differently. And I think that would make an awful big difference"
(Fay)

Working Differently includes the sections *Leaving Paid Employment*, *Communities*, and *Alternative Work*. Experiences of leaving paid work were significant to participants, and the pain and loss when employment roles ended often contrasted with the enjoyment and successes they had experienced while working. An important aspect of enjoying work was the community connected with employment, where kindness could be shared by and with participants. Though several participants who were no longer in paid employment had found alternative roles, these alternatives did not simply replace the roles they'd previously had. This emphasises the importance of working differently; not only in respect of being able to adjust ways of working in employment as dementia develops, but also how participants were working differently in voluntary roles.

Leaving Paid Employment

With the exception of Leanne, none of the participants were in paid employment at the time of our interviews. All the participants told me about paid employment they had undertaken during their lives, indicating the importance that past employment continued to have in the present. Participants spoke about their jobs with pride and recalled their roles positively, often smiling as they described activities and duties that had been part of their employment. Penny described her role as "varied" and she had "loved it", Bea told me there was "never a dull day in a hotel" and Darcy told me working at her school had been "so nice. It kept me happy". For participants, paid work had been a central component of career and the influence of their past roles endured.

Several participants told me about how their dementia symptoms had impacted their work and that they had left their jobs as a result. Bea had felt content about this, but for Fay this had been difficult

because she hadn't wanted to leave work. Iona had been told to stop work whereas Darcy felt the need to "escape":

"Initially I was fine, but it just gradually got worse and so I was looking for a way to get out, and that was my escape when covid started... So I just didn't go back" (Darcy)

Darcy hadn't had a manager to raise her concerns with, and the pandemic offered an "escape" that wasn't previously available. Control over leaving work was often with (unnamed) others rather than the participants. Bea had reduced her hours, but it took 18 months for her leaving package to be agreed:

"I knew there was something not right. So, I went down to three days, and then I just, they eventually get, gave me a package to leave, which was quite happy [laughter]" (Bea)

The decision to terminate Ruth's employment was based on paperwork and she "didn't have a say". The diversity of experiences participants described are unified by being reliant on others; whether wanting to leave work and needing the appropriate entitlements and administration organised, or wanting to continue but this not being facilitated or considered.

Participants that detailed how their work ended indicated that organisational policies and procedures had been followed. None of the participants told me they had challenged any such procedures (for example, through legal action). In respect of reasonable adjustments, Bea and Leanne had reduced their hours at work and the people who should have been supporting Fay did not do so. Elle told me that "nobody would employ me anyway with a diagnosis like I have"; this indicates that the expectations of those living with dementia don't include employment. I asked Ruth if she felt her employer could have done more to support her at work:

"It's the NHS. It's the NHS. I mean, I, I know that they're just on their knees, 'cause they are, but... I do think that they of all people should see the value..." (Ruth)

Penny had tried to raise concerns with her manager, and felt resignation was her only option when this was unsuccessful. Ruth told me about her "termination of the contract" meeting, indicating that she had been subject of a formal process, and about "the person who I'd never even met, who was delivering the news" being upset at this meeting. Fay said that "the only option that was left to me was to retire" after other's 'box ticking' didn't materialise in the support she needed. It was evident that participants had engaged with formal processes to maintain their employment, but (with the exception of Leanne, who had maintained her employment) this engagement had not enabled them to continue. None of the participants specifically mentioned having formal support, such as through legal advice or union representation.

Feelings were often conflicted as participants internally negotiated the reality of how their dementia was affecting their work with the hope of improvement (for example, through more support from an employer or an improvement in symptoms). Bea had found trying to manage her employment responsibilities stressful, so was “happy” that she would no longer be at risk of making a mistake that would be detrimental to her employer. Beth was adjusting to her diagnosis, and while recognising she was “not fit to practice” had also maintained her professional registrations in case her cognitive abilities “miraculously” improved. Leaving work was an emotionally complex process for participants, and possibly for employers too. Ruth described tears from her manager. Elle’s manager told her she was a problem:

“I was having problems doing my work. And my manager’s approach towards me was no, you’re not having problems, you are a problem, there’s the door. And so, no support at all”
(Elle)

This perhaps indicates the pressures employers must balance between individual needs and organisational performance, and this balance not weighing favourably towards employees with dementia. Fay had resisted ending her paid work, but on reflection felt positively about it:

“So, although I didn’t want to go, hindsight, it was the thing to do, because I’m in a much, the, the, the lack of pressure and deadlines and schedules and responsibility has helped me to keep being well” (Fay)

The feelings employees with dementia have about leaving work before this happens, when it happens, and after it happens are not necessarily linear or consistent. It is therefore important that employees with dementia are supported not only with reasonable adjustments to continue working (when appropriate), given correct advice and guidance about entitlements such as pensions, but also with sensitivity for the changing emotional impact that leaving their employment has had, has now and will have in the future.

Communities

An important aspect of paid employment was the wider social opportunities and community connections that it facilitated. Fiona explicitly spoke about her colleagues as being friends and the importance of the social element of work:

“We used to get there, have coffee, everybody get together, you know, talk about all sorts, really good friends, and we met socially as well. So, used to go to the pub, and have dinner [laughter], used to have a real good time... I really miss that” (Fiona)

Although Fiona was “fine” about missing her colleagues because she could still see them socially, no longer being an employee changed the dynamic because the “after work” element of connection could no longer be enjoyed. Frustrations from employment had a focus on the ways people at work had failed participants, rather than the impact of dementia. For example, Darcy described becoming increasingly concerned and “emotional” about not remembering things she needed to at work, and how she didn’t have anyone to support her:

“I was just one person. I mean, even though there was a receptionist, but I was just taking care of everything from A-Z and I just, I couldn't manage to do it all by myself, you know, I needed a helper, and I didn't have one” (Darcy)

Fay had colleagues to support her but they had let her down:

“People ticked all the boxes, went to all the right meetings, but at grassroots level, the people who needed to support me and to help me, they weren't doing it. And so, it very quickly fell apart” (Fay)

The influence of colleagues and others in the workplace on employment was important to participants. The others they worked with and around were a source of encouragement and enjoyment. Developing dementia whilst an employee doesn’t mean that the importance of enjoying work stops, nor enjoying the interaction with others and being someone that they enjoy interacting with.

Communities at work did not only consist of colleagues but were extensive and broad. Fay’s role as a teacher meant she was well known and involved in the community where she lived, and after leaving her job this community connection was maintained:

“I knew them as a young child growing up, we'd all grown up together. So, my connection with the community is very strong still. And that helps, because I came into this phase of my life kicking and screaming because I didn't want to leave my work” (Fay)

Fay’s work community was her local community, because as a teacher she had met and developed relationships with families local to the school and had lived in the area for most of her life, and this ongoing connection was significant for her. Other participants also described their connections with their work community positively, even when these had been in the past. Darcy recalled traveling to another city and unexpectedly meeting a parent she had known through her work:

“She knew me right off the bat, and I said I'm sorry, but I don't recognise you. She said, you don't remember me?... I remembered who she was at that time, and I was so thankful I got to meet her, because she was, she was very, very kind” (Darcy)

Clare also told me about overhearing a conversation where a previous colleague had been telling someone what it was like nursing with her, not realising Clare could hear, and Clare had found her “kind” and the conversation “enlightening”. Bea repeatedly told me about her colleague who had done a particular aspect of her job for her, because Bea had hated it. Participants recalling such encounters signifies how kindness is an underestimated aspect of career. Opportunities for giving and receiving kindness with others may be reduced after leaving employment, so participants describing past events connected with their employment may evidence how much kindness still matters and the need for such opportunities to continue when employment ends. Kindness, defined as “the quality of being friendly, generous and considerate”¹⁵, is distinct from pity, sympathy and politeness and may be an important aspect of career that those living with dementia miss when their roles as employees end.

Kindness is an important aspect of the work community because participants valued receiving kindness, and being able to offer this. For example, Elle told me that a highlight of her role as a social worker had been conversations with the older people she supported. Elements of kindness and care were significant, even for those in less overtly ‘caring’ professions. For example, when I asked Beth what had attracted her to “dark jobs” focused on child protection, she told me that “I think I just wanted to help really”. Fiona had enjoyed being friendly with her customers. Leanne described the people supported at the charity she works for as “glorious”. Penny told me that one of her favourite aspects of traveling for her job was “the people”. The community of employment extends beyond the formal connections between colleagues but also to customers, clients and wider community; and the importance of this community does not stop when employment ends. Bea had felt very anxious about making a mistake at work involving the children, and one of Penny’s main concerns that led to her resignation was knowing she was no longer doing a “good job”. Participants articulated a form of ‘duty of care’ to their work communities; not wanting to let their employers, or the communities that were connected with their employment, down. This adds further complexity to the employment role when living with dementia, the need to continue being part of the wider work community but also needing to maintain the standards of helping and care that the community needs.

¹⁵ Google dictionary with definition from Oxford Languages

Alternative Work

Though all but one of the participants were no longer in paid employment, several did not seem to have stopped being 'employed' through alternative forms of work. This presented as a contradiction, with the stopping of employment and the financial, social and other benefits paid roles offered; but continuance in professional and skilled roles. None of the participants in such roles told me they were paid for their involvement, so it is presumed that these roles were unpaid or only covered expenses. Ruth's experience epitomised this contradiction, as her paid employment with the NHS Trust she worked for had been terminated but she was welcomed as a volunteer:

"I'm, but it's, it's an envoy role that's working, or volunteering, we don't get paid, for the same Trust that I used to work for. So, my, I'm, I'm good to go on their premises, attend meetings and do anything that I do... But yet, I wasn't, I, they weren't able to keep me on as an employee... Some people say I shouldn't do it on that basis, which I understand. But then, what do you do?" (Ruth)

For Ruth, there was a conflict between her willingness to work and advocate for improvement in dementia services, and doing so for the employer that had terminated her because she developed dementia. The employer is seemingly contradicting themselves, valuing her skills and input in a voluntary capacity when they had not done so by continuing to pay her as an employee. Ruth was aware of this but in asking "what do you do?" she had chosen her role as an envoy over an ex-employee, choosing to focus on what she could offer rather than what the employer had not offered.

Though Elle had felt put on the "scrap heap" after her dementia symptoms started and been unable to secure paid work, she had been involved in several research projects and groups, and had started a support group for women living with young-onset dementia. The object she chose to discuss her career was a printed publication of a Masters module that she had written in collaboration with a university and others living with dementia; it represented "about three years of work". In addition to writing and designing the module, she would also be involved in the teaching and marking of the module. Elle's experience highlights a further complexity of career when living with young-onset dementia; living with a degenerative cognitive impairment and maintaining capacity to work, learn and contribute. While Elle acknowledged the extra time and energy it took to organise and complete work, she clearly maintained professional skills and abilities. She told me that she "work[ed] harder now than I ever did when I was getting paid to work".

Towards the end of our interview, Fay shared an example to illustrate how she was able to use her skills in her employment role even though dementia symptoms were affecting her work. Fay had

started to struggle with remembering names and faces, so she “used to call children lass or bud”. A family had come to the school to ask for her help, but they couldn’t remember her name. The receptionist realised they were asking for Fay because they wanted the depute “that calls me lass”:

“I was finding it really hard to match faces and names... And, do you know what it proved to me was although I didn't know that person's name, well, they didn't need to know my name either. We were able to perfectly well get along, meet each other's needs. I was able to deal with the circumstance that they brought in that day and needed help with. And it didn't matter that I didn't know their name, and it didn't matter that they didn't know me, my name, because actually we knew each other. We knew the people and we knew the person”
(Fay)

Her difficulty with names, and the family not remembering her name, did not matter. What mattered was that she was able to provide the support the family needed, and for Fay this was evidence she was useful and skilled, she was still able to work, she just needed to do so differently:

“It just means you need to work a little bit differently, and people around you just need to accept that you need to work a little bit differently. And I think that would make an awful big difference” (Fay)

Forgetting names is a common experience, it happens to those living without dementia as well as those living with dementia. The forgetfulness did not prevent Fay from utilising her lifetime of experience and skills to help the family who needed her. Participants needed employers to, as Ruth phrased it, “looked at how I could have continued, for as long as possible, even if it was reviewed”. Being able to enjoy a period of working differently may have eased the career transition by reducing the sense of grief and lament for lost opportunities.

Participants generally spoke about career in the past tense, indicating that career was thought to end when employment ended. For example, Tabitha articulated in her interview that she did not have a career:

Tabitha: *“Well, I don't, I don't know that I, I could say I have a career 'cause, you know, but.”*

Rachel: *“It is a very tricky word because I think we really associate it with work, don't we?”*

Tabitha: *“Yeah, yeah”*

Supporter: *“Would you say you have a career at the moment?”*

Tabitha: *“No, no”* (Tabitha, supporter and Rachel)

For Tabitha, employment and career were synonymous and therefore she did not identify as continuing a career, though her life was continuing post-diagnosis. Losing the role of employee and losing an employer are significant, even when the skills and attributes from paid employment are utilised in unpaid roles. For example, though Penny had told me about many activities she now enjoyed and was busy with, when I asked her what she particularly enjoyed about this stage of her career she replied that “I don't know if I'd call it, it's a career anymore?”. Her supporter then challenged this view, demonstrating the critical nature of the employee role to career:

Supporter: “... *Just people need to have a different definition of what career means*”

Penny: “*Yeah. Yes, I guess so*” (Penny and supporter)

For Penny, it wasn't just part of her life that had finished and “gone” but part of her, part of her identity and who she was. Whilst Ruth had also found alternative work through voluntary roles and photography, not being an employee remained difficult for her because “you feel part of the world by being involved in employment”. Voluntary work may therefore be limited in how it can continue connection with “the world” compared with paid employment. Penny also expressed sadness about losing her employee identity:

“I would really like for people with dementia to have a, still have a, a role in employment because, you know, it's part of you, you know, and when you take that away part of you is gone” (Penny)

When I asked Beth about her career highlights, she felt these had also “gone”:

“It seems to be rubbished, because it's gone... I've lost it, it's, it's like, it's a loss” (Beth)

This sense of finality indicates that even when participants had found new roles after leaving employment there was a loss arising from their dementia that could not be remedied. Beth's feeling that her career highlights were “rubbished” suggests that she had something she valued but could no longer enjoy that value. Bea was “happy” with her leaving package from work, and Fay had come to understand her loss of employment as positive for her overall wellbeing. Both were now enthusiastic about the roles they were now engaged in, which may indicate how important alternative work and activities are for career to be understood as ongoing rather than “gone”. Whilst this study has defined career as *life and work* the participants' experiences show how career may be continual, in the sense that it continues throughout life, but it is not simply continuous; career evolves and changes but aspects of it do go and are lost. While new roles facilitated continuity of career and this was positive for participants, the pain and grief from loss of employment isn't necessarily healed by continuing or contributing purposefully through alternative work.

5.2.1.2 Making Champagne

“You know, they say, what is it? That you're given lemons, you could make lemonade. Well, I think I made lemonade. I think I bloody made champagne out of the bloody dementia if you ask me, because I just met like-minded people” (Clare)

Making Champagne is about the impact of dementia on participant’s careers beyond paid employment. While *Alternative Work* focused on how participants were using their professional skills in other formal contexts and felt disconnected from career, *(Dis)enabled to Contribute* follows on from this to explore how participants were able to contribute and continue their careers in less formal ways. The *Void Of Dementia* describes the difficult period following diagnosis that participants experienced and what helped them to move on from this. *Purpose* then explores the different elements of purpose and daily focus participants told me about.

(Dis)enabled to Contribute

There was a sense of frustration shared by participants that their roles as employees could have continued but hadn’t; their professional contributions had been dis-enabled. The importance of paid work for Leanne (as the only participant who was a paid employee), and those who were no longer in paid work did not end when their employment ended; but being able to contribute, to use skills and talents with or for the benefit of others, was an important way that careers continued. Leanne was continuing in her paid role and “absolutely love[d]” her job. Though she had “cut back” her paid work, she was also involved in volunteering and research activities. She highlighted the importance planning now had in her life post-diagnosis, and understanding the “journey”:

“It's the journey. It really is the journey. Getting to know it is a journey, that's the main...”
(Leanne)

Conceptualising career as more of a journey than a status may be especially helpful in the context of young-onset dementia. Participants articulated various ways that they continued to contribute after diagnosis. Iona told me that she had loved music throughout her life, and after developing dementia found it “problematic” to continue singing at church but was instead singing as part of a community choir. Iona had also enjoyed traveling, but was unable to do so during the pandemic because of lockdowns and had used the internet to address this; viewing historical sites and other countries online. Determination was therefore enacted not only through the doing of activities, but also in the journey of trying and trialling different ways and alternatives. For Clare, her “purpose in life changed” with her dementia diagnosis. She utilised her natural inquisitiveness and passion for

learning through research and “became a dementia activist”. She was able to develop a new activist identity and find new purpose, through the ‘lemons’ of dementia she had made champagne:

“You know, they say, what is it? That you're given lemons, you could make lemonade. Well, I think I made lemonade. I think I bloody made champagne out of the bloody dementia if you ask me, because I just met like-minded people” (Clare)

Clare was continuing to contribute her skills and talents as her career and “purpose” changed because of dementia. Some other participants found it hard to understand how their contributions were valued and appreciated beyond the context of their formal employment roles:

“I just wish there was more, more for people like me, I think. I wish that, that I could have been allowed to work a bit longer. ‘Cause I feel like I’ve still got stuff to contribute, but nobody seems to want my contribution” (Ruth)

The way Ruth articulates her frustration, firstly for “people like” her, and then about what her employer had “allowed”, indicates an understanding that what is allowed isn’t only about the individual. Being “allowed” to continue work impacts colleagues, family and friends, and those who would potentially be affected by the employee’s “contribution”. Ruth appears to be referring to her employer when she says that “nobody” wants her contribution, because it was evident her contribution was wanted in other contexts, such as her voluntary work and photography talents.

Participants had shown initiative, ingenuity and creativity when the progression of dementia had presented challenges. Beth told me about using You Tube videos to help her with tasks such as using the washing machine. She spoke of this in negative terms. I suggested it was a “very creative approach”:

“...I just thought it was painful, because I've been desperate... And I know how I want to feel, but I couldn't achieve it... I felt stupid watching You Tube, it didn't seem, I will look at it different now you've said what you've said. But I felt it was me failing, because I couldn't do, I couldn't naturally, quickly, do these, these things” (Beth)

By reconsidering her use of You Tube more positively, as a creative solution rather than a sad necessity, Beth was able to find purpose as she reflected not on her “failing” to do things she had before, but on her ability to find a solution to help her feel how she wanted to feel. There was purpose in using You Tube because dementia had presented problems, and she was developing her role as someone solving those problems. She was no longer solving problems as a solicitor, but doing so with purpose nonetheless. This was an expression of how her career was continuing; she was

working through problem solving and contributing to her career journey as she negotiated life through the aftermath of diagnosis.

Participants were not only living with young-onset dementia but were experiencing a life stage where aging can also impact career, for example through decline or 'weakening' of physical health. This also affected how they were able to continue contributing:

"People don't recognise that, with people with dementia, the struggles. The brain energy and the struggles that we go through for our tasks of daily living, don't get easier. They get harder, and we get weakened with aging process" (Clare)

For some participants, such as Ruth, there was a sense of urgency to use her voice as much as possible before dementia took it from her. For others, such as Penny, there was a defiance of physical limitations as she planned wild swims and strenuous hill walks. She had adapted such activities with her supporter, for example he had started giving her directions when she ran because her eyesight was deteriorating. Clare described being in physical pain, but had joined a gym so she could 'walk' in the water. Ruth continued to drive but carried a card explaining she had a neurological condition, in case an accident occurred and someone mistook her dementia for drunkenness. These examples demonstrate the contradiction of being able, but that ability being increasingly difficult to actualise.

Void of Dementia

Participants articulated a distinction between before and after a dementia diagnosis. Diagnosis of dementia was described not so much as a transition but more of a schism. It was not a gentle progression or natural shift, but a state from which participants needed to "move on" or "turn" from:

"I went into a very dark place. I'm not going to lie, you know, I could not get up in the morning and work out what the hell I was doing. I had no idea. I had no, I had no direction, I had no sense of, I had no sense of anything. I could not work out what was the point in my life" (Fay)

Ruth felt that after diagnosis she was "written off" and had started to become "invisible". I named this state as the *void of dementia*, because it was a place of darkness, loss and invisibility; a place of "no direction" and painful struggle described by several participants. Penny and her supporter discussed the void during our interview:

Penny: *"I just couldn't cope with it more, anymore and so it was, I just had a brave pill and resigned..."*

Supporter: *"But that in itself brought on, not a breakdown, but it did bring on depression"*

Penny: *"Yeah, correct, yes"*

Supporter: *"Because all of a sudden you'd gone from a piece of work that you really enjoyed and you'd invested a lot of yourself in to, to having nothing and feeling, well what do I do now?"*

Penny: *"That's right"*

Supporter: *"And all the, the self-esteem and the self-worth and all that just dropped through the floor"*

Penny: *"That's right. And then we went, were a very dark patch, didn't we?"* (Penny and supporter)

The language Penny and her supporter used to describe this "very dark patch" evokes a sense of void; with "struggling", "depression", "having nothing", loss of "self-esteem" and "self-worth". Both Fay and Penny spoke about suicide, having received dementia diagnoses and lost their jobs. It is not possible to know whether adjusting rather than ending their jobs would have prevented such a sense of despair, but employment could have offered some form of continuance during a time when much felt irrevocably changed and lost.

Hindsight does influence perspectives. Participants like Penny had been able to reflect on how her employment had ended and the feelings diagnosis had evoked. For her and her supporter maintaining positivity in how they shared their experience was important, to not forget the void but also avoid focusing on it. Penny's supporter had reminded her to tell me about this "dark patch" so that I could understand the impact of the link worker after she received her diagnosis. Beth's diagnosis had been more recent, and she seemed to be navigating the *void of dementia* as she experienced upset and distress about the impact of dementia on her life. Along with having to manage on a drastically reduced income, "unplanned", she felt much less able to manage everyday activities independently:

"I kind of knew how to do everything. I would be self-sufficient. My own hair, my own nails, face, back. I'd do my make-up. I'd clean my house inside and out. Cut my lawns... I could cook for a large family... Now, I can't remember where I put the tea bags" (Beth)

The *void of dementia* involves adjustment to diagnosis. For Clare, this was a time of lemons before making lemonade (or even champagne), and participants such as Fay and Penny also contrasted how negative they had felt after diagnosis with the positivity they now felt. Perspectives closer to the void differed from those further from it, potentially indicating how time to adjust is important after diagnosis. Moving on from the *void of dementia* took various forms. Leanne, Iona, Penny, Elle, Clare and Fay all told me about their involvement with research or activism activities post-diagnosis. They linked these activities with a sense of purpose following loss of employment, as Penny and her supporter describe:

Supporter: *"It was work again [at the resource centre]"*

Penny: *"It was"*

Supporter: *"And having a purpose wasn't it?"*

Penny: *"That's right"*

Supporter: *"And it was the that, you know, and again, you talk all about self-esteem and, you know, personal pride and whatever, but that's what it brought back because all of a sudden there was somewhere where Penny could go, where opinions were still sought and valued and she could make a difference and contribute to things again"* (Penny and supporter)

Research and activism were key facilitators into more purposeful roles that positively influenced wellbeing from the void after diagnosis. Involvement not only engaged participants in activities that were "work again" but also had additional benefits such as meeting others with a diagnosis and being part of improving lives affected by dementia.

Purpose

None of the participants defined purpose, and like career it's a word that is likely to have had different meanings and connotations for each individual. In the context of this analysis, purpose is understood to be about daily determination, because participants spoke about purpose in the context of the activities they were doing and involved with. As well as research and advocacy, participants told me about less formal roles and activities that they found purposeful. Leanne enjoyed reading and had restarted Tai Chi, following support from her link worker who had encouraged her to be more active. Darcy found macramé (knotting yarn into decorative shapes) relaxing, and enjoyed cooking, sewing and crochet. Iona and Bea were members of choirs. Fay connected purpose with her dog:

“That was a real turning point, because I had to get up, and I had to feed him, and I had to take him out to toilet, and I had to train him... he was the first real link I had with being back in, back in the real world again, and responsibility, and having something to do, and having a value and a purpose. And somebody who needed me. He needed me, just as much as I needed him” (Fay)

This excerpt from Fay’s interview highlights some key components of roles that have purpose; opportunity to learn, enjoyment, connection with others and having something important to do. Another important component is challenge, and the opportunity for those living with dementia to surprise themselves with new skills and talents. Ruth had tried singing at an event:

“I could sing it, which [has] surprised me, in a way, because I was thinking maybe that’s something I should try and do more of? Just because, it can make you feel good, can’t it?”
(Ruth)

Feeling good, and sharing feeling good, was a way in which connections with others were established or maintained following diagnosis. Fay’s role as a dog owner not only gave her something purposeful to do, but there was mutual need for one another. In her employment role, Fay had been needed in multiple ways, and she recognised in our interview that having her dog was a link to “the real world”, where she was still needed. Dogs also facilitated this connection for Fiona:

“I go on the computer, do games on the computer. Read a lot, I read a lot, I like reading. I’ve started doing jigsaws [laughter]... It’s mainly for my brain I do it, like crosswords, things like that, you know. Music. What else do I do? I take the dog out, yeah, I take the dog out, because they tell you to go for walks” (Fiona)

Fiona made a distinction between activities she did for herself, such as crosswords, and taking the dog out, because the dog needed this. Tabitha’s supporter recognised that “to be needed is a very important human need” and purpose in roles beyond employment reflected this need to be needed. Being connected to and needed by others is an important aspect of roles with purpose when living with dementia. The following exchange between Bea and her supporter highlights this:

Bea: *“I still feel that I’m still ok”*

Supporter: *“Yes”*

Bea: *“You know, very, you know, people think hh-mm, dementia, but”*

Supporter: *“I mean, you get up, you dress, you wash, you do the laundry”*

Bea: *“Aquafit [unclear] basically I do everything” (Bea and supporter)*

For Bea and her supporter, part of being ok was being needed. She had told me about receiving her leaving package from her employer, then asserted that she was ok, then expressed concern about what others thought because she was living with dementia. Her supporter affirms her assertion that she is ok, and provides examples to reassure her, and she then adds to his list. There is often a focus on the needs of those who are living with dementia, but this example from Bea highlights how those living with dementia also need to be needed. Bea's supporter helped her articulate several examples of activities that were difficult or no longer possible because of dementia, such as cooking, so there was not a denial that dementia had had significant impact on Bea's life; but having described the difficulty of the diagnosis process and leaving her job, the focus was on what was good and enjoyable.

Bea also told me about attending the local dementia café and being part of the rock choir:

Rachel: *"And you enjoy the performing?"*

Bea: *"I love it, because I've got, I've got, I've, most days I've got something to do"* (Bea and Rachel)

Bea was not the only participant to highlight how important it was to have something to do every day. Several participants spoke positively about how they had multitasked and managed multiple elements of their job under pressure, and continuing this sense of variety was part of continuing career post-diagnosis:

Rachel: *"And it sounds like you've kept that variety, that was important before your diagnosis. You're still doing various things now"*

Iona: *"Yes, and I've always enjoyed music"* (Iona and Rachel)

Fiona contrasted her experiences at work, when "every day it was different", to her life living with dementia, where "you do more of the same thing". Whilst variety was therefore important for participants, it wasn't necessarily as easy to achieve when no longer employed. It was necessary to undertake routine activities (such as dressing and cleaning) but also to participate in other activities that met a need to be creative, be with others or help make a difference. All participants mentioned several activities that were part of their routines and different people or groups they interacted with. While this seemed largely positive and enjoyable, several challenges with such variety were discussed.

For some participants, the more routine activities such as household maintenance were challenging, reducing capacity for other less practically essential activities. Beth struggled with aspects of her

selfcare routine and household tasks such as making her bed. Darcy had assistance from her family and a housemaid to help her maintain her home, and told me about getting “totally lost” in the process of replacing a duvet cover. Traveling was difficult for Bea and Fiona; they had utilised disability assistance to use trains, for example. Tabitha’s supporter helped her with managing going out and attending appointments. They felt that the daily reality of living with dementia gave them a “survival” focus:

Supporter: *“My purpose? You don't really get to indulge in that kind of thinking so much, because day by day, where's your other sock?... If we were looking, if you ask the question what are you looking forward to that, that becomes interesting. The next little weekend break holiday, a little two days in Donegal, not much in the way of purpose”*

Tabitha: *“No”* (Tabitha and supporter)

This highlights an important aspect of role continuance when living with dementia, that for some the activities that they would like to enjoy or previously looked forward to are no longer possible. This may be because symptoms prevent participation, the enjoyment from participation is overwhelmed by the difficulty of doing so or those living with young-onset dementia do not have the support they need to participate. For example, Tabitha’s supporter reminded her about plans to visit her sister that were a little different than usual, because her sister was going to see her onto the bus and Tabitha’s supporter was going to see her off the bus. This indicated that Tabitha’s sister and her supporter had considered Tabitha’s needs and made a plan that was accessible and safe for her, enabling her to visit when this wouldn’t have otherwise been possible.

Finding and maintaining roles with purpose seemed to be of critical importance for moving on from the *void of dementia*, connecting pre-diagnosis and post-diagnosis career roles. Elle was grateful for her previous employment and care giving experience, because using the skills she had gained she set up her own support group when she learned none were available in her area:

“I kind of run groups during my social work, I said well in that case I'll set up my own... It's always rotten for anyone to get the diagnosis, but I thought, well, at least, I was able to move on positively quite fast because I think I was able to see the fact that I could use that professional background in a positive way, plus the fact that I'd had personal experience of supporting family members” (Elle)

Fay also found purpose through using her professional skills in a different context, as part of a dementia advocacy and research group:

“I was part of looking at applications and bids and, debating and, do you know, really used, I used every single skill that I hadn't used from leaving my job. Because I was encouraged not to bother reading, not to bother writing, not to bother, you didn't need to do that... all the things that you just did instinctively in your job... And then [Group], every skill I used as a depute I used again” (Fay)

For Fay, being “encouraged not to bother” was part of discouraging her from purpose. Using her skills was instinctive for her and this hadn’t diminished because of dementia, or even because of losing her job. To move on from the difficult period participants described after diagnosis often meant going back to their past skills and experiences and using these in different contexts, and being encouraged and enabled to do so.

5.2.1.3 Letting Loose

“Now it's a case of, that's, that license to let loose, you know, getting over m[y]self. It's like, it doesn't matter” (Leanne)

Inspired by Leanne’s “license to let loose”, *Letting Loose* explores how participants’ priorities transitioned while continuing a career with a dementia diagnosis. Several participants had been able to focus on activities they enjoyed and understand dementia as a form of “a new beginning”. *Letting Loose* was also about the loosened daily structure and the implicit sense of purpose through work that participants missed when their paid work had ended. *Knots of Messages* refers to loosening in another form, as participants sought to untangle the external messages they received about dementia with their personal experiences and identities.

Transitioning Priorities

Participants shared an implicit permission to prioritise what they wanted to while living with dementia, for example through how they compared experiences before and after diagnosis. Leanne phrased this as a “licence to let loose”. For Penny, it was a “a new beginning... a different one” and she agreed with her supporter that “it’s how you tackle it that’s important”. Leanne told me about an international journey she had made alone, and problems with her flight and finding her way. When I told her that would have made me feel stressed and upset, she replied:

“That's the thing about having the diagnosis. Before, I would have felt sorry for m[y]self and this is awful. Now it's the case of, this is a challenge. If I can take on this challenge, how good will I feel?” (Leanne)

For Leanne, there was a contrast between how she would have reacted to such challenges before her diagnosis and afterwards. Participants needed to make the most of their abilities during the time they had to enjoy them. While for some it felt “good” to take on challenges, for others there was a sense of frustration and being let down. Ruth felt “left with dementia” after her job ended and she had struggled not with boredom, but with the frustration of wanting to ensure her activities were of “quality” and “worthwhile”. Without her paid employment role, she had struggled to understand how her activities met these priorities:

“I just get frustrated ‘cause I’m not doing anything of quality [gestures air quotes with hand]. I struggle to find things that are, or can be, classified as quality or valuable” (Ruth)

However, Ruth also shared about how she had used photography as a way of communicating; “something to say without saying”. An exhibition of her photographs had been curated by a local organisation to raise awareness about young-onset dementia and the range of symptoms, and she had been interviewed for the local news and sang a solo at an event. Ruth’s experience illustrates that the day-to-day reality of living with dementia can contrast with highlights that are experienced during the journey. Whilst those living with young-onset dementia may have roles with purpose this may not necessarily be felt during ‘in-between’ periods where they perhaps aren’t meeting with others, practicing hobbies or achieving outcomes they are working towards. When in paid employment day-to-day purpose and priorities are incorporated into the routine of work, without paid employment that sense of purpose can be harder to establish and maintain.

Ruth’s experience offers an alternative perspective on what letting loose means while living with dementia; that the “quality” of how time is spent can be looser to define and purpose harder to claim, in spite of achieving career highlights and defying other’s expectations. Several participants told me about career highlights experienced after their diagnosis as well as before, indicating that diagnosis is a career transition point at which priorities shift:

“The thing that I liked best during my social work was, I always liked going out and doing assessments on people... that was my favourite part of that. And, and I like now because I have my own young-onset group, but I also facilitate a, an online group” (Elle)

Elle was able to recall her “favourite part” of her paid work but also told me “I like now”, linking to the need to feel good and have purpose. It is possible to like the phase of career that develops following a dementia diagnosis even if that does not include paid work or has necessitated different priorities. Even if participants didn’t like that their paid work had ended, and missed their jobs, liking and enjoying career post-diagnosis was often facilitated by others continuing to like and enjoy time

shared together. Enjoying interactions with others also provided a sense of variety that could be missing when no longer working. When I asked Fiona about her career highlights, she told me how she had enjoyed meeting others and the daily variety her role as chocolatier had offered. Now she was no longer working, the importance of variety was expressed through meeting other people and her dogs:

“The highlights is just like meeting people. Yeah, meeting people... the highlights of my life at the moment are my dogs, and seeing other people. I mean I've got [Partner]. But, you know, it's the same thing... It's seeing people, and talking about different things to people” (Fiona)

Some participants explained that their dementia diagnosis had given them a form of permission to care less about worries, concerns or inhibitions they may have had before and do what they wanted:

“Normally I would say, oh no, I'm not doing that. No, I'm not doing that. But I did it. It's almost like a, like a benefit to FTD, because I couldn't care less” (Ruth)

Darcy similarly expressed that she didn't “care about a lot of things. I don't let anything bother me”, whereas previously she had struggled with stress and overthinking. While Ruth attributed this sense of greater freedom to her FTD, this may have been because of the way FTD affected her cognition and thinking, or perhaps because of how diagnosis had impacted her outlook on life and how she approached decisions. Leanne also felt that dementia had facilitated a form of bravery and offered her a new form of confidence:

“I introduced a research session at the Alzheimer's Annual Conference, which is so far removed from anything I would ever have done. And, I think that was just ego... and, you know, second guessing. Now it's a case of, that's, that license to let loose, you know, getting over m[y]self. It's like, it doesn't matter” (Leanne)

Knots of Messages

Letting loose was not only about how priorities transitioned for participants (what they did), but also how they understood their identities and how they felt. *Knots of Messages* is about how the sense of self could be tied to other's negative expectations and perceptions of dementia. Fiona was seeking to understand her dementia in a context where she felt others did not; processing and reconciling the image and understanding she had of dementia with her own experience. For her, her understanding of dementia was perhaps having more impact on her life than dementia itself:

“The worst thing about dementia, I, you know, you see on television, where you see people sat in chairs, wheelchairs, all around television... like, couple of months in, that's what I thought it would be like. So, I said to the counsellor, I said I'd rather have cancer” (Fiona)

Understanding dementia is complex, involving not only clinical explanations but the influence of media images, what other people think, and what knowledge and perceptions the person living with dementia had when diagnosed. When Fiona was diagnosed she thought she would be confined in a chair “straightaway”. She attributes this understanding to images she had seen on television, indicating that the image portrayed in the media of dementia is one of older people in the later stages, which was difficult for Fiona to reconcile as a younger person experiencing hallucinations. When Elle set up a young-onset dementia support group, she was aware that for some people dementia wouldn't have been something they could be open about:

“I was always very kind of out about my dementia, I didn't see it as something to be ashamed of” (Elle)

This suggests that for some, dementia is an aspect of themselves that needs to be in rather than “out”, to avoid potential negative reactions or interactions. Being able to understand dementia when living with a diagnosis means confronting negative pictures and unravelling the knots they can create, to re-understand what dementia is and what it means when sad and grey images are the prevalent norm. Fiona had a clinical picture from her doctors that she couldn't make sense of, and an image from the television that she couldn't relate to. She had not been able to connect with others who could understand her dementia experience, and maintaining family roles was challenging because not everyone in her family understood her diagnosis and ongoing needs. Her partner and step-daughter treated her “as normal” but her son treated her “as a child”, which she attributed to his way of coping with her diagnosis. Fiona was not only seeking an understanding for herself, but also an understanding of how others were feeling and behaving towards her.

Several participants expressed motivation to reduce stigma and improve communication about young-onset dementia, such as Leanne who connected making a difference with how she could change understanding of dementia:

“I'm more active, engaged and doing things because of it and because I can, because I've got the diagnosis early enough, and that's why I want to make kind of some sort of a difference in terms of getting messages out there. Getting it is not an end of life” (Leanne)

Leanne told me that dementia meant “a bloody awful end” but her assertion that it is “not an end of life” reflects the stigmatised message still prevalent about dementia, that life ends with diagnosis.

She was motivated by wanting improved outcomes for others “in the future”. A difference is needed in how dementia is understood, evident from participants’ motivation to make this difference. Penny and her supporter told me about a particular picture they had seen on the front of a magazine:

Supporter: *“What comes up time and time again for us is a picture of a little old lady that, the in, in a grey background, little old lady in her eighties, she must have been, sat, you know, looking at an empty fire. And it’s, it was a grey, dark picture of dementia”*

Penny: *“Yes”* (Penny and supporter)

Penny had felt “really cross” with this picture because it didn’t fit with the “trying to get the up-to-date sort of way of being” that was very important to her and her supporter. Challenging the “grey, dark picture” associated with dementia was an important part of post-diagnosis purpose for participants, whether through engaging in professional-orientated roles such as speaking at conferences, publishing educational resources about dementia or exhibiting their photography; or through singing, walking their dogs and swimming. In contrast to what could be a grey outlook, participants described their careers in multicolour with the greyness of challenges they were experiencing blended with the colours they were using in their roles with purpose.

5.2.1.4 Summary of The Career Tree

Participants valued the wider community that being in paid employment enabled them to be part of and enjoy. They felt that more could have been done to have enabled them to work differently after they developed dementia, so they could continue for longer. When paid work ended participants’ careers continued, but their careers were not continuous. The period following diagnosis was one defined by loss, however with appropriate support new branches and directions of career were realised. Participants had contributions they were keen to utilise and offer to others, but the context of this offering had needed to change. The roots of pre-diagnosis roles facilitated connections with others and ongoing contributions post-diagnosis. Post-diagnosis roles were not only those relating to continuation in professional or personal contexts but discovery of new roles and seeking solutions to overcoming challenges in daily life. Roles with purpose enabled a moving on from the void of dementia into a phase of career where challenges were met, even enjoyed, and new confidences realised; enabling highlights of careers to be realised even though paid work had ended, and participants were living with a terminal diagnosis.

5.3 Theme Two: Dementia Peers and Professionals

(Lifting Each Other, Able to be Honest and All I'm Worth)

5.3.1 Introduction to Dementia Peers and Professionals

During the analysis process I used drawing and other creative approaches to aid my visual thinking. As I combined analysis of my own reflective notes with participant data, I had a strong visual image of the 'peer' of dementia:

Figure 10: The 'Peer of Dementia'

This image was inspired by the importance of peers to participants, and the understanding that was developing about who peers were, and how they were part of the 'tree of life' that Clare used to describe her career. The 'pier' is akin to a branch that forms after diagnosis that would otherwise not be part of the career tree. Creating this image helped me to express the meaning from the data that

participants' careers were extending from the safety of what had been before, out over dangerous and difficult territory, and their peers were ensuring they didn't have to stay where they were, but their careers could go beyond what would otherwise be possible.

This importance of peers was complex, and the pier seemed like a fitting metaphor to explore these complexities. A pier is a raised structure that extends out from the shoreline into the sea. They are typically made of wood, with a flat platform at the top and wooden beams underneath holding the platform above the water. A pier can be considered a building because it is a built structure, but also not a building because it has no walls or roof, and I learned from participants that peers were also understood in different ways. Participants articulated a distinction between peers and professionals, particularly medical professionals, with the importance of peers described in various ways.

5.3.1.1 Lifting Each Other

“Every Monday teatime, we'd come together for an hour online and it was like we could, so that we could kind of come together and, and say oh God I've had a hell of a week and offload... we'll be having a really good laugh together and lifting each other's spirits” (Elle)

Lifting Each Other includes the sections *Togetherness* and *Dementia Activism and Support*. Whilst opportunities to be together with others living with dementia were valued by participants, there were complexities with doing so, such as the positives and negatives associated with meeting online. Complexities with activism and other forms of support are also explored, such as the need for encouragement and support to start and be involved in activism groups and activities. *Lifting Each Other* is therefore about the benefits of connection and interaction with others living with young-onset dementia, and contributing more widely to improved outcomes and understanding about the condition.

Togetherness

Participants discussed the importance of other females in their lives, such as support from their friends and sisters. Fay, Darcy, and Fiona spoke about the importance of their female friends. Fay, Iona and Tabitha spoke about their sisters. Beth reflected that “it's good to be with women”. In the context of young-onset dementia, being able to talk for and with other women may help to facilitate a safe space for women to connect with and support one another. The three participants who were supported at interview were supported by their husbands, and several participants told me about their (male) partners involvement in their lives both in the past and present, and future plans together. Gender is therefore not a prerequisite to being a peer but for these participants the context was important. The need, for example, as Fiona expressed, to meet others “like me” may

mean that meeting other women is preferable to a mixed gender group. I asked Elle if she felt there was a benefit to being part of a women-only dementia activist group:

“You could talk about absolutely anything, you know, you talk about things such as menopause. You could talk about anything like that, that a man wouldn’t understand. And, it was just, it was just really freeing” (Elle)

Elle told me that a men’s group had also started because the men had felt a women-only group was “sexist”. This indicates that both men and women (and likely those with non-binary gender identities) find opportunities to meet and connect with others who share gendered aspects of their lives valuable and beneficial.

Participants spoke about meeting others both in-person and online, and advantages and disadvantages with both were recognised. For example, while participants enjoyed opportunities to meet up in person, such events could be tiring and necessitate extensive planning. Clare still wanted to attend events that she had previously, but the need to plan so she could manage was onerous:

“I used to go to conferences and I was used to travelling and I was a social butterfly, and, do you know what I mean? I had, I haven’t got what it takes. I haven’t got the energy to do that, you know? And everything is a big plan” (Clare)

She had found support from her daughter and “pace and space” helpful in how she managed attending events. Clare told me that she was “very alone” but had practical support online, such as reminders to take her medication.

Elle had been part of an online peer support group, but this had not continued as the facilitators “had to go off and do other projects”. Being able to meet together was therefore not simplistic, it involved multiple channels and others living with and without dementia, but simply having a weekly online meeting for an hour had significant importance:

“Every Monday teatime, we’d come together for an hour online and it was like we could, so that we could kind of come together and, and say oh God I’ve had a hell of a week and offload... we’ll be having a really good laugh together and lifting each other’s spirits” (Elle)

Whilst the uptake of online facilitation has evidently benefitted participants because they told me about attending meetings online and were comfortable being interviewed online, it may also be compounding isolation for those without a local group who find internet access more difficult because it is increasingly assumed (for example, after the necessity of using online channels during the pandemic), that access is either available or could be made available. This isn’t necessarily the

case when living with dementia, for example because of not having support with the more technical aspects of using software. I was able to be flexible and meet one participant in person for her interview with her supporter, but in a group context accommodating individual needs (even with sufficient willingness, insight and flexibility) would be much more difficult. This is not only about groups being on or offline; software that is easier for one person may be problematic for another. For example, Elle asked if she could be interviewed using Zoom rather than Teams because this was more accessible for her. Other participants were used to Teams and happier with this. What is easier for some will be more difficult for others, and due to the impact of dementia 'more difficult' may mean impossible. Meeting together was therefore a difficult balance between people, technology, and differing needs.

Dementia Activism and Support

Several participants were involved in dementia activism and this took various forms, such as research involvement or participating in working groups that aimed to influence dementia policy and practice through the benefit of lived experience. Activities included speaking at conferences, research participation and coproduction, writing and publishing, poetry and funding bids. Participants spoke about such activities in the context of the groups they were part of, or other individuals involved, such as when Elle told me about the team that had worked together to produce the MSc module. Being active together was a form of peer support that participants spoke positively about. Clare had been involved in the research and writing of several dementia-related publications with multiple organisations and individuals. She told me she "became a dementia activist" through the "searching and researching" activities she had undertaken; it was part of her individual identity but also important as a collective or social identity:

"I was blessed with all, going to the good roots, the solid foundation, faith, family, work, you've got different types of families, you know? Your work family, your work whatever, and, so yeah, so now I've got my dementia family and my dementia activist family" (Clare)

Clare used her tree of life necklace to explain how she felt the roots of her life were a foundation for the branches that were growing (such as gaining a dementia activist family) and the leaves sprouting (her activism-related achievements). This illustrates the important connection between the activism activities and being active together. These were not separate but dual aspects of peer support for participants. Other activists were peers, and the activism activities a context in which such peer relationships could thrive.

Fay had a “magnificent specialist nurse” who set up a support group, based on a “meeting centre model”, that was initially for those with a young-onset diagnosis. Fay had been reluctant to go because of her mother’s experience:

“I went just to keep everybody happy, keep everybody quiet, I went, I thought I’ll not go back. I’ll go once and that will shut them all up, and I’m not gonna go back. And I just loved it, meeting people, who all had very similar experiences, or very different experiences, but who are all kind of feeling the same about certain things” (Fay)

Fay described her support group as her “proper turning point”, but it is a point she wouldn’t have reached if it were not for those encouraging her to go, those she described as the “everybody” she needed to keep happy. Penny had also been somewhat reluctant to attend a support group:

“For a while I thought this is the end, you know, I’ve got dementia and what am I going to do now? And actually the [Name], the link worker, I never really wanted to be involved in anything like this, and... any groups... so I went along and it was brilliant... It was wonderful [laughter] and that really helped me to just go forward” (Penny)

Penny’s supporter had said that Penny’s link worker would not “take no for an answer”. The link worker met her outside a store in the pouring rain and Penny described standing there waiting and questioning why she was going, but after she did “everything was on the up”. Penny hadn’t enjoyed being a “groups person” but with encouragement tried something new and gained much from doing so. Iona had decided to join an activist group when she “learned what went on” from a member of staff at Alzheimer Scotland. Such experiences show that some support and encouragement was necessary for starting a potentially whole new branch of career post-diagnosis. For Fay, Penny and Iona this encouragement was spoken of positively, but participants such as Tabitha and Fiona hadn’t had such positive experiences, so balance is needed to ensure that encouragement isn’t manifested at the wrong time or in the wrong way.

5.3.1.2 Being Able to be Honest

“It is all about being positive and the positivity and, but also it’s, it’s about, it’s about being able to be honest. And you can go in, and you can say this has been an absolutely week, and folk will say, oh do you know, I was like that” (Fay)

Being Able to be Honest includes the sections *Timing and Form*, *Equal Status* and *Ripples of Loss*.

Each section highlights a different aspect that contributed to *being able* to share honesty with others. The timing and form of support needing to be right for individuals. Support provision varied

in the different geographic locations the participants resided in, and not all participants had been able to access support that met their needs. How peers were defined and understood was focused on sharing an equal status; this didn't necessarily relate to age or sharing a 'young-onset' diagnosis, and included animal companions. Participants also shared sadness at losing friends and being treated differently after developing dementia.

Timing and Form

Though peer support groups exist throughout the UK, participants highlighted two issues: lack of local groups and lack of appropriate groups. Darcy was not living in the UK, and the only support available to her was through her family. Iona, Penny, Fay, Clare, Bea and Leanne lived in Scotland and told me about the peer support and activism they were involved in. Both Leanne and Penny highlighted the benefit of their support (also known as link) workers, offered as part of a promise for at least one-year post-diagnosis support to all those diagnosed with dementia in Scotland. Fay also lived in Scotland and received support through a specialist nurse. Elle and Ruth lived in England, and Tabitha in Northern Ireland. Participant experiences and involvement with peer groups indicated that there is a strong network and culture of peer support in Scotland that is less distinct in other areas of the UK. This is an important context of peer support because of the impact external stigma about dementia has on internal stigma. Just as the pier over the water must be accessible from the mainland, so the provision of peer support is facilitated by the wider social context. This wider social context does not appear to be the same for all women across the UK. Beth and Fiona lived in England. I asked Beth if she would find meeting others with dementia helpful:

"How are we gonna understand each other [laughter]? I keep thinking, if I'm ga-ga, and they're ga-ga, how does that work [laughter]?" (Beth)

Beth was not sure how connecting with others living with young-onset dementia might feel. She described herself as "ga-ga" with an "if" qualifier, and perhaps attending a group was a concern for her because of the potential to affirm that she was no longer "clever":

"I never thought that I would be unintelligent like I am now. 'Cause it's taken away my, I'm not clever anymore" (Beth)

Being part of support groups had been a source of encouragement and hope for others, but for Beth there was a sense of risk that by being with others with dementia she would share a "ga-ga" identity with them, rather than have this perception challenged. This was also the case for Fiona, who told me:

"I've still got all my marbles. And I just wanted to talk to someone who's like me, who understood, you see... There's nowhere" (Fiona)

Timing of support was important. Reference to having "marbles" and being "ga-ga" indicates an internalised negative perception about dementia that may need time before being externalised in a public or social arena.

The right group at the right time could be a very constructive experience, but if the form and timing of the support was not aligned then groups could be hurdles or barriers to career rather than a positive influence. Fiona had attended a group and not found it appropriate for her needs:

"You sat in a circle. And it was just silly. It was silly. It was right at the beginning of the dementia, and it frightened me, because they were really far on, with the dementia" (Fiona)

Fiona indicates, by saying that it was "right at the beginning" of her dementia, that the timing of the group was not right because the others attending "were really far on". For Fiona, the right timing wasn't only about her own readiness but how she compared with other people in the group in respect of progression with dementia. Beth was perhaps unsure if meeting others with young-onset dementia would be positive or not, if it would be better to be "ga-ga" with others or without them, and Fiona's experience is evidence that timing of peer support needs to not be frightening or distressing.

Fiona's experience also highlights a further aspect of how groups can be appropriate for women living with young-onset dementia, by avoiding 'silly circles'. The form peer support takes matters. She had been expecting somewhere she could sit with others who would "have a cup of coffee, sit at tables and talk to you"; similar to what Penny had experienced at the Resource Centre:

"The first day in the Resource Centre was fantastic because they were actually sitting down, doing work in the Resource Centre and they were, you know, talking about all sorts of things and what we were going to do and, and I thought this is great" (Penny)

When I relistened to Fiona's interview, I noted my discomfort that I (as someone not living with dementia) had been able to join a local dementia café and sit at tables and talk with people as she had hoped to do, but she had not been able to access this. I asked in my reflective notes, "*why shouldn't Fiona have that? Have that basic human need to be with people like you met?*" Some participants had support that was accessible and appropriate, and others did not. There was a clear distinction. None of the participants indicated that they'd accessed appropriate support but preferred or chosen not to engage further with this.

Similarly to Fiona, Tabitha experienced a sense of childishness and lack of alignment with her needs when she attended a local support group:

Supporter: *"We were given plastic eggs, like you know, like hen eggs, but plastic and the little paint kits, paint the eggs for Easter [unclear]"*

Rachel: *"And was that something you enjoyed, Tabitha? How did you find that?"*

Tabitha: *"No, no. I didn't enjoy it. It just, it just, it just felt so childish"* (Tabitha, Supporter and Rachel)

Penny described an environment that had professional connotations, such as "sitting down, doing work", similarly to Fay who told me that "it's about meeting, but doing something as well... having an activity that's stimulating". Tabitha experienced something "childish", and her supporter suggested in the interview that it had been too hard a transition for her; to have led groups in her employment to then being a member of a group as someone living with dementia. Darcy had told me about how craftwork was something she continued to enjoy but no longer did so at the local arts centre, where she had previously taught. Being creative may have been something she preferred to maintain privately, or perhaps she preferred not to adjust to being part of a group she had previously been able to lead and teach. For some, painting eggs may have been enjoyable, and it could be considered a family-friendly activity inclusive of those at different stages of dementia or without a diagnosis; an opportunity to enjoy something creative and indulge the playful inner child. However, given the needs that those living with young-onset dementia have in respect of maintaining an adult identity and role (one of intelligence and autonomy rather than dependence), the intentions of activities like painting eggs have potential to manifest as infantilisation and an assumption that more complex crafts are inaccessible.

Effective peer support was facilitated by reflecting familiar and comfortable settings from career that peers would have in common and enjoy irrespective of dementia, such as a café or office. This is an important insight about the relevance of career to the enablement of successful peer support. Sitting in a circle or painting eggs wouldn't likely be something women living with young-onset dementia did as part of their careers pre-diagnosis. Careers were continuing, and therefore peer groups that reflected roles of continuance rather than regression to earlier life stages, such as child, were welcome. By connecting professionalism to the group, the context was positively influenced. For example, Fiona felt like the group she attended reminded her of an 'Alcoholics Anonymous' meeting. This set-up jarred with her expectations and wasn't something she could relate to or felt comfortable with.

Equal Status

Fay and I discussed how peers were defined during our interview, after she told me about how both meeting others with young-onset dementia and getting her dog had been significant in her life after developing dementia. She described having to adjust her thinking around age when her support group was extended to include older people:

“How dare you even go there and think that because they were older, they wouldn’t be able to bring something? And so, I very quickly learned to readjust my thinking. So, when I say peers, there are peers in the diagnosis and in the stage of the diagnosis, they may be age-related peers, or not at all” (Fay)

Fay’s ‘readjustment’ of thinking has wider applicability, as peers for women with young-onset dementia need to be defined and understood flexibly. Fay offered another example of a peer connection that was related to her previous employment, an inter-generational project with nursery-aged children. Fay had been a teacher (and latterly a depute head teacher) and was able to continue working with younger children through this project. These children were her peers because they were part of the positive community that was around her. They were peers because they supported her in the way that she needed. Friends, family and others in the community may have positive intentions but peers are able to actualise such intentions as support for the individual. Peers are generally defined as those “with equal status, class or age”¹⁶ and the emphasis for participants was on equality within the peer relationship, avoiding a dynamic where differences (such as age or diagnosis) changed the value or status they held. Fay felt that peers needed to be understood “in different levels and in different contexts” and was not, for example, related to age:

Rachel: “That’s really interesting actually, that it’s not really related to age... or even diagnosis. It’s more just being part of that... positive community around you?”

Fay: “Yeah, yeah, yeah. And, and it is all about being positive and the positivity and, but also it’s, it’s about, it’s about being able to be honest. And you can go in, and you can say this has been an absolutely week, and folk will say, oh do you know, I was like that” (Fay and Rachel)

Participants found peers in places where they could be honest, where they did not have to worry about their young-onset dementia and felt safe being themselves. Fay told me she would not return to the *void of dementia* or place of “desperateness” again because she had found peers, peers who

¹⁶ The Free Dictionary by Farlex

“didn't care that I might not be able to find my way back out the toilet”. While “being with like is always good” (Beth), what ‘like’ meant had a wide range of interpretations:

“I like being with people who drink tea [laughter], because I only drink tea. So, maybe on that basis, it would be good to meet other people like me” (Beth)

Having some form of commonality and connection, even as tentative as mutual appreciation for a cup of tea, could enable peer relationships to form. Such relationships took the form of friendships, or something more akin to the dynamic of colleagues. Peers enabled and encouraged positive outlooks within the gritty reality of living with dementia. Though a shared ‘young-onset’ diagnosis may be part of this or an aspect of being alike that enables connections to form, age was less important than other factors such as sense of humour or lack of judgement. This reflects the wider social context in which age is increasingly becoming less of a reliable indicator of a woman’s career role or life stage. I asked Fiona how her needs as younger woman with dementia differed from those of an older woman. She told me that whilst it was harder to accept as a younger woman, the needs were the same.

Ripples of Loss

While peer support was spoken of positively, one aspect that was negative for participants was the loss of friends and other relationships. Participants attributed this to friends misunderstanding the meaning of a dementia diagnosis and discomfort with how to continue the friendship. Having a dementia diagnosis changed their ‘status’ and therefore how relationships continued:

“I did lose a lot of friends when they found that I've got dementia, and not because they didn't like me anymore. It was just the fact that they didn't know how to cope with me and, you know, I'm a different person, [laughter] you know? And, and actually, I'm the same person, but actually I think I'm probably stronger because of the experience” (Penny)

Penny felt that her dementia diagnosis necessitated her friends having to “cope” with her, or manage her relationship with her differently. She knew her friends continued to like her, but their loss in no longer maintaining a friendship with the “stronger” Penny was her loss too. She had missed out on the continuing enjoyment those friendships would have offered, and hadn’t been able to share her ups and downs with those she otherwise would have before developing dementia.

Fiona shared an example of how quickly this loss could occur after diagnosis:

“We went on holiday soon after I got diagnosed, with my family, because I wanted that. And some of them treated me as normal. And some of them treated me completely different. Completely different. A couple wouldn't talk to me. I think they were frightened that I'd

changed so much, or I've changed completely, you know, but other people just accepted me like that" (Fiona)

Fiona was treated differently "soon" after her diagnosis. Being treated differently was very painful for Fiona, perhaps especially because since childhood she'd had a condition she felt had impacted her life much more than dementia had. We discussed how at the time of her diagnosis with epilepsy it was not a well understood condition, and Fiona was again experiencing being reacted to with fear and negative assumptions. Fiona attributed her family being frightened because of her having changed, indicating that they understood dementia to involve a very rapid deterioration in cognition. This may also be an understanding that women themselves have when they receive their dementia diagnosis, and that can be difficult to reevaluate alongside others. It may involve projecting internalised fears onto others, potentially contributing to the breaking down of relationships. However, several participants had experienced the rejection and loss of friendships based on the diagnosis and did not express that this had been precipitated by them, but that the friends had chosen to withdraw or cease contact:

"And lots of people walked away, and lots of people, I've never heard since I got a diagnosis, do you know, I've just never seen them or heard from them again" (Fay)

The loss of established friendships underlines the importance of peer support. Friends can become peers after diagnosis but might also 'never be seen or heard from again'. The connection with peers is different because the diagnosis is honestly shared and accepted; there is reassurance in a connection that others may not be able to access. The waves may batter the pier, but it will stay standing however weathered. This may be why animals were of special importance to some participants, because they could be trusted not to walk away but, in the case of dogs, literally walk alongside. Fay and Fiona considered their dogs an important peer because of their capacity for honest and unconditional love and acceptance:

"You'll talk to dogs. They don't judge you, you can talk to them... they'll love you, unconditionally" (Fiona)

Tabitha told me how she enjoyed being out with her dogs. Ruth and I also discussed the importance of animals in her life. Her birds could be heard throughout the interview, and she told me about an incident while out shopping with her dog. She had been struggling with the prices and sizes and sought assistance from staff, who then told her she had to pick up and carry her dog inside the store. Her balance was impacted by dementia and she could not do this, so she walked out because she "didn't have any response". While Ruth may not have had a verbal response, she did have an

enacted response that communicated the priority of her physical and emotional need rather than the store's instruction. In this example people had let Ruth down and not treated her with sensitivity, they had made assumptions about what was possible for her. However her dog had been her ally and left the store with her, she hadn't needed to verbalise any response to her dog or explain herself.

Flexibility was therefore important when understanding who peers were for participants. Just as a pier is a construction with purpose, but not necessarily defined as a building, peers were those offering support and acceptance even if this wasn't specifically defined as such. To use Clare's phrasing, peers were simply "like-minded people". For participants this included others with young-onset dementia, older people with dementia, nursery-aged children, friends, family, the wider community, and animals. They were not just like-minded in having positive attitudes about dementia but committed to journeying with the person living with the condition through laughter and tears and everything in between.

5.3.1.3 All I'm Worth

"I had said about my job. I don't know, don't know what to do because of my job. And she said, once the memory cafe opened properly that I could hand, hand out cups of tea. And I was like, I couldn't, is that, is that all I'm, that all I'm worth now? Just dishing out tea, that I'd probably end up chucking over everybody because I have a tremor" (Ruth)

All I'm Worth begins with *Post-Diagnosis Waves*, focusing on the dementia-related professionals that participants had interacted with and varying experiences with pre- and post-diagnostic support. *Career Connection* discusses how participants' professional backgrounds were relevant to the dementia diagnosis process and support needs after diagnosis. However, this relevance was not always appreciated by dementia-professionals and participants articulated a disconnection between their needs and the support and advice they received.

Post-Diagnosis Waves

Participants in Scotland expressed high regard and gratitude for the post diagnosis support they had received, for Fay this had been from a specialist nurse and for Penny from her link worker. I asked Leanne how this had been useful for her:

Rachel: *"So was it the sort of getting started with what would be helpful that they were most useful for, or was it the accountability of what do you want to do?"*

Leanne: *“Well, it, I suppose it's a mix of both. The fact that, it was very much, asking what interests were, so it was very personalised”* (Leanne and Rachel)

This personalisation enabled the specialist nurses and link workers to be peers for the participants, because they were responsive to what they needed as individuals. Often, the emotional impact of dementia does not begin at the moment of diagnosis, but much earlier as symptoms begin and progress. However, personalised support was missing for participants before the diagnosis and involvement of link workers.

Participants wanted to be heard by the medical professionals involved in their care. During the diagnostic process participants expressed a lack of congruence between medical assumptions and their lived experience, and this perpetuated a gap between what they were experiencing and what they were able to understand. Beth knew that her symptoms were not the result of depression, because “depression doesn’t make you forget where the [laughter] damn teabags are” but she felt her doctors were “stuck” on depression. She wasn’t listened to and this made life worse, not better. She wanted to understand why she couldn’t find her teabags. Darcy experienced similar frustration:

“And then they tell you, yeah, but we tested you for, I don't know what, and your memory seems to be very good. But how come, I don't remember even to take a shower every day?”
(Darcy)

What she was being told did not help her understand why she was forgetting to take a shower. These everyday aspects of care, making a cup of tea and having a shower, are impacted by dementia and yet questions about this impact had gone unanswered. Participants questioned who was being helped by the need for ongoing tests and monitoring post-diagnosis:

“What's the point of going to these appointments? Whose benefit is it? It's not mine” (Ruth)

For Ruth to state that she was not benefitting from the appointments suggests that not only was she not being heard, but also there was a failure to communicate what “the point” was. Participants were spending time and energy attending appointments, resulting in frustration when this did not benefit them or seemed to be pointless.

Clare also felt there was a lack of congruence between the cognitive assessments she undertook and the impact of dementia on her day-to-day life:

“They're taking me in here and asking me, pick this up, and who's the Prime minister and who's this and who's that? And I can't bloody manage showering. I mean, what's more

important? Who's the Prime minister or getting showered and getting dressed in time to get out? Get their act together, you know?" (Clare)

By not listening and responding to participant's needs, medical professionals were missing what was "more important". A solely medicalised approach to dementia care post-diagnosis missed opportunities to address concerns participants had and offer assistance or advice to manage what they were finding most difficult. A disconnect occurred between what doctors were explaining or advising and how this was helpful. For example, Leanne told me how important it was that people understood how to delay or slow the progression of dementia symptoms:

"Your doctor tells you to drink more water, but does the doctor tell you what drinking water can help prevent? And that is an important link" (Leanne)

Without a connection between what participants were told, or being asked to do, or the questions they had and the answers they received; fears, worries and frustrations had potential to become increasingly unsettling. Fiona described being scared because she didn't understand her hallucinations, she needed to know why she was getting them as an early symptom but "I don't know why, but then, the doctors don't know". Participants were reliant on medical expertise so that they could understand themselves; if the doctors didn't know or couldn't provide answers then they had to live with uncertainty and unanswered questions. Whilst not reasonable to expect even the most advanced medical experts to necessarily have the answers, participants often didn't feel their questions and needs were seen and heard (with the exception of link workers and specialist nurse). Participants were not only living with a lack of understanding, but the frustration of not knowing if the understanding would be there had they been listened to. This underlines the importance of peers because there may be "nowhere" else offering answers or an alternative picture:

"If you go to the consultant, or the doctors, well the doctors, they don't really know they're talking about, they don't understand" (Fiona)

Family members reacted differently and not always positively to diagnosis. Darcy felt supported by her family, but her daughter had found it difficult to understand how Darcy's dementia affected her; for example she had questioned if Darcy loved her grandchildren because she had struggled to care for them alone:

"My two grandbabies, sometimes I need to get away... And my daughter doesn't understand that. She doesn't understand, why you have to go away from the kids? Don't you love them? I yes, I do. I love them a lot, but I can't stay with them 24/7" (Darcy)

Those close to participants needed to understand that dementia wasn't just about one symptom, such as memory loss, but the holistic impact on the person they loved. Darcy could continue her role as grandmother, but not in the way she had done previously. Her daughter hadn't understood this, and this led to a questioning or undermining of the grandmother role. For Fiona, being treated differently by her son wasn't "the best" for her, but Darcy needed her daughter to understand she needed a different way to care for her grandchildren. This highlights complexity in maintaining relationships with those living with young-onset dementia, not knowing and needing to learn what needed to change and what needed to stay the same; a balance which the person living with dementia may not know themselves, especially as their dementia progresses.

Career Connection

Career and dementia were entwined. As employment was impacted and changed due to dementia, so employment (and other aspects of career) affected how dementia was managed and impacted individuals; and more appreciation of this connection is needed. For example, Beth had been working as a solicitor before she developed dementia following a stroke. Being able to articulate herself, process complex information quickly, and recite case law had been skills she had used daily in her employment. Whilst sad that she was not able to utilise these skills as she had before, there was frustration that her GP had not connected her abilities with her employment rather than her symptoms with dementia:

Rachel: "Sounds like your GP doesn't understand that you're living with dementia, but still able to articulate yourself..."

Beth: "Yeah, and if I did those jobs then language would have been very high. So, they're not looking at that... they just ignored that, and I suffered" (Beth and Rachel)

There was a sense of dismissal in participant experiences. Beth's cognitive difficulties were not dementia because she articulated herself too well, Darcy was told her memory tests were good and this didn't help her with remembering to shower, and Clare was much less concerned about the Prime Minister's name than about being able to get ready and go out. An example of the power of professionals to perhaps do more harm than good through assumptions and lack of insight was described by Ruth. She sought advice about her job after diagnosis from an occupational therapist and nurse:

"I had said about my job. I don't know, don't know what to do because of my job. And she said, once the memory cafe opened properly that I could hand, hand out cups of tea. And I

was like, I couldn't, is that, is that all I'm, that all I'm worth now? Just dishing out tea, that I'd probably end up chucking over everybody because I have a tremor" (Ruth)

She was given wrong information "from a [gestures air quotes with hand] professional". She was seeking support for her employment, and not only didn't get it but found that:

"People in the service, talking to people, and discussing people, at that time, were not even giving them the right information. They don't even know themselves, which is scary. Really scary" (Ruth)

Instead of getting the information and advice that she needed she had been given "shitty bits of paper" and left scared rather than empowered, informed or supported. Beth was "just starting" to receive formal support following her diagnosis. An occupational therapist had visited her home:

"She watched me. She asked me to do certain things in the house. She says my house looks like, it's a bit of a mess. There's no, there's some organisation, but she can see that it's gone, and, 'cause I don't know where to put things" (Beth)

The home had been a significant area of distress for Beth during our interview, because she lived alone in a large property that was now feeling more like a "prison" because she felt "lost" and unable to manage maintaining it. The occupational therapist had confirmed what Beth had been thinking, that her organisation was "gone", but this confirmation seemed to lack any element of support or encouragement. During the transcription of our interview, I noted my discomfort about how Beth described the way the occupational therapist had spoken to her:

"I feel negative hearing that Beth was being watched and told her house was a mess... There's something like an additional power in being told something by a professional. I wonder if hearing the OT's words affected her feelings about her house... if the OT had been more positive... would she have felt more positive about the house and managing living there?" (Rachel's notes)

Participants in this study respected the professional advice and medical procedures they were advised were necessary, however it was less clear that their own professional expertise, skills and experiences were also respected. Some participant experiences indicated that they were somewhat dismissed because of diagnosis (or lack of diagnosis, when the process was ongoing). Participants suffered because they were not listened to by the medical professionals from whom they sought understanding and help.

5.3.1.4 Summary of Dementia Peers and Professionals

In the context of the careers of these women living with young-onset dementia, peer support was not passive, but active and purposeful. It was accessible and supportive when it met participants' needs, and detrimental to wellbeing when it did not. Being accepted as someone with young-onset dementia was also important; irrespective of whether peers shared characteristics such as age, gender or diagnosis, so the way peers were understood needed flexibility. It was important that peer support was facilitated in ways that reflected the ongoing careers of those living with young-onset dementia. After diagnosis, participants would have benefited from medical professionals incorporating an understanding of their careers and how these were being (and would be) impacted by dementia. Being able to understand their dementia, and have those close to them understand what they needed, was important for participants to continue their careers, but their questions were often unanswered.

5.4 Findings Summary

This chapter has detailed the results of analysis of data following interviews with 12 women living with young-onset dementia. Two major themes (*The Career Tree* and *Dementia Peers and Professionals*) have explored how women experience life roles in their careers whilst living with young-onset dementia.

The subthemes of *The Career Tree* were *Working Differently*, *Making Champagne* and *Letting Loose*, each focusing on a different way careers continued to grow while living with a diagnosis. For several participants leaving paid work had been a significant change in their careers due to dementia. The communities they were part of at work often facilitated being able to give and receive kindness. Alternative forms of work did not replace the paid roles that had previously been part of careers, but were important ways that participants were able to contribute their talents and skills and undertake activities they found purposeful. Participants also found creative activities such as singing positive enablers of careers post-diagnosis. Participants also shared about the difficult and upsetting period they had experienced following their diagnosis and shared ways that they had found helpful to move on from this distress. There was often a need to reconsider career priorities and ensure variety in daily life. Participants also felt it was important to them as individuals to address wider negative and stigmatised messages about dementia.

Dementia Peers and Professionals focused on the positive and negative ways that others impacted career after diagnosis. The subtheme *Lifting Each Other* explores the importance of participants

connecting with others “like me” and how important involvement in dementia activism activities and dementia support was for participants. *Being Able to be Honest* examines how peers were those of equal status to participants, and how the timing and form of support was important for ensuring it met their needs. Peers were described in various forms and contexts, highlighting the importance of flexibility when understanding who peers are for women living with young-onset dementia. Several participants had found it difficult to lose friends or be treated differently by those close to them following diagnosis. *All I’m Worth* discusses how participants had experienced formal support following their diagnosis, and how for several participants negative interactions with medical professionals had been a career barrier.

5.4.1 Key Findings

Women living with young-onset dementia have careers that involve change and challenge. Whilst significant career barriers and negative aspects of living with a diagnosis were discussed, participants shared a varied range of insights into how their careers were continuing positively. The findings from this study indicate that:

1. Women with young-onset dementia continue their careers in a number of ways post diagnosis. However, diagnosis is a significant disruption to career and therefore careers are not continuous.
2. Being diagnosed with young-onset dementia can change the feelings and needs participants have related to their careers, and these feelings and needs continue to evolve after diagnosis.
3. Women living with young-onset dementia gain benefit from support which incorporates career-related needs and experiences.
4. Connecting with peers who enable career aspirations and career continuance following diagnosis is important to women with young onset dementia.

6. Discussion

6.1 Introduction

This study, *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career Development*, has addressed the research aim of exploring how women living with young-onset dementia experience life roles in the context of career. The key findings arising from this unique and original study will now be explored further. This *Discussion* chapter begins by discussing the findings in the context of other research. The literature review identified that paid employment was an important aspect of career for those living with young-onset dementia, as well as non-paid roles and activities, and disruption to the lifecycle. This chapter begins by reviewing these areas alongside the learning from this study, highlighting the important insights gained relevant to young-onset dementia and career.

Key theoretical and practical considerations are then reflected upon, including the unique and innovative application of the Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) in the context of young-onset dementia, and the use of creative approaches during data analysis. Such approaches enabled me to interact with the data differently, for example thinking with my fingers as I used a hook and yarn to crochet during data familiarisation. I also reflect on the interview approach adopted in this study and advocate for future research to consider online interviews as a primary form of interview, rather than a secondary alternative to 'in-person' interviews. I highlight how object elicitation enriched the data collection process and was used successfully online with participants living with dementia. The chapter ends with theoretical and practical recommendations for future research, career guidance professionals and for future policy development; summarising the useful and practical learning generated through this study.

6.2 Paid Employment

Paid employment roles were not the only career roles participants in this study had, but they were ones of significant importance, "integral in their stories" (Chaplin and Davidson, 2014, p. 149). Three areas of concern were identified in the literature review as significant in relation to paid work: *Symptoms at Work*, *Support at Work* and *Leaving Work*. The area of key significance to participants in this study was leaving their paid work roles. As women living with young-onset dementia, the participants were continuing to have careers after diagnosis. However, one of the four key findings

in this study was that while their careers continued, they were not continuous. The impact of dementia was such that careers did not carry on as before. Whilst career continuation involved many positive elements, the loss of paid employment had significant and ongoing negative impact. This may be particularly salient for women, who may have had lower employment-related expectations at earlier life stages (Christopoulos and Bromage, 2009) leading to an enhanced importance of employment in later life.

Losing paid employment was in some respects negated by alternative roles, for example being able to use professional skills and abilities through advocacy or research (Bartlett, 2014; Broders and Wiersma, 2020), but these alternatives did not replace paid roles. The grief and upset triggered by leaving paid employment was a source of deep distress to participants and this endured as their careers continued. This supports the suggestion from Ritchie, Tolson and Danson (2018) that support for the transition of leaving employment is as important as support whilst at work. Whilst women are more likely to have had paid employment that is “discontinuous [and] interrupted” (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005, p. 108), the lack of support when leaving employment because of dementia may make this transition especially difficult. Leaving work was, as Rabanal *et al.* (2018) also found, a significant loss, and participants in this study described the negative impact this had and continued to have.

Participants had an enduring sense of finality about their jobs, and the abilities and contribution they actualised through those jobs no longer being part of their lives and careers, a sense of loss echoing findings from Rabanal *et al.* (2018). The findings highlighted how the *void of dementia* was a significant phase of career for participants in this study. They articulated a distinct time of darkness and grief between receiving a diagnosis and moving into a more positive space. Other research has also highlighted the difficult period following diagnosis (Gerritzen, Orrell and McDermott, 2024; Kohl *et al.*, 2024a; Nygard *et al.*, 2023). The *void of dementia* was often connected with receiving a diagnosis, the lengthy process of which can be distressing for women (Broders and Wiersma, 2020), and losing paid employment at around the same time. Fay, Penny, Ruth and Beth lost their paid employment soon after being diagnosed or during the process of diagnosis, while for Elle her employment ended over five years before diagnosis (due to her symptoms); all articulated experiencing the *void of dementia*. However, how participants reacted to the loss of their employment varied. For example, Evans (2019) found that leaving work could be experienced as a relief and in this study Bea articulated a sense of relief. Kilty *et al.* (2023) found that continuing work with the support needed was preferable to leaving work, and in this study Fay would have rather continued working with the supports she needed. None of the participants in this study related positive experiences of the process of leaving work; describing delays, missed opportunities and a

lack of support and understanding. As also found by Ashworth (2020), participants in this study did not describe any celebration in recognition of their leaving or retiring. Though participants in this study experienced the *void of dementia* and loss of paid employment as part of their careers, all were continuing their careers while at different stages of adjusting to diagnosis and loss of employment.

Broders and Wiersma (2020) found that the loss of something to do every day after employment ended was difficult for women, and this was echoed through this study. This related not only to activities, but also social aspects of work, such as the communities connected with employment (including relationships with colleagues, and opportunities to help and interact with others). Several participants mentioned a continuity in such connections, such as keeping in touch with friends from work. Ritchie, Tolson and Danson (2018) found that leaving work meant losing contact with friends at work (especially for their male participants), so the relational dynamic (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005) of women's careers may enable women to continue work-related relationships differently or more effectively than men. As work is an important source of social connection (Johannessen *et al.*, 2018; Ritchie, Tolson and Danson, 2018), continuance of these relationships is an important part of career post-diagnosis. 'Resilient Communities' is a thematic focus of Scotland's 2024-2026 two-year Dementia Strategy delivery plan (Scottish Government, 2024). Whilst this focuses on the communities local those living with a dementia diagnosis, the findings of this study highlight how work can also be an important source of community and may be an aspect of the plan where gendered differences need to be identified.

There was suggestion from some participants in this study that their employers had been open to them continuing work. As found by Ritchie, Tolson and Danson (2018), this suggests a willingness from employers but lack of practical knowledge and understanding to facilitate continued employment successfully. Once these women with dementia left their workplaces, all their experience, skills and intangible benefits of their inclusion were gone too. Ending work roles should be an aspect of career employees with dementia have a greater degree of control over, ensuring that when the time is right to leave this is a positive experience and "smooth transition out of their working life" (Smeets *et al.*, 2024, p. 1123). This may be of particular importance for women, as they may have experienced multiple unexpected career transitions (Bimrose, McMahon and Watson, 2013) and interruptions (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005) prior to developing dementia.

Leanne was continuing in her paid role for three days a week alongside volunteer work, evidencing that continued employment is possible with a diagnosis. She had "cut back work", congruent with Karjalainen *et al.* (2022)'s finding that working differently may mean adjusting or adopting flexible

hours. However, while some participants in this study did mention adjustments, the lack of specific detail about these and a focus on how employment ended, suggests that their experiences were dominated not by flexibility and adaption, but by leaving and loss. Rigid and time-constricted processes appear to be hindrances to the flexibility that employees with young-onset dementia need. For some participants in this study symptoms at work were interpreted negatively, correspondent with Issakainen *et al.* (2023); others, for example Penny and Darcy, were encouraged to continue working but without the support and understanding they were needing. This also connects with the key finding that career-related feelings and needs change and evolve, because dementia is a degenerative condition and therefore processes need to accommodate the changing needs of employees with dementia. Several participants in this study worked for large public sector organisations and yet reported negative experiences, though Ritchie, Tolson and Danson (2018) suggested that larger employers may be better resourced to facilitate adjustments.

For women, who may already be seen as having somehow failed to age successfully due to dementia diagnosis, adjustment to roles could be understood as part of the “living well discourse” (Sandberg, 2023, p. 206). When there is a failure to facilitate employment adjustments, this could be internalised as a failure to ‘live well’, compounding the loss of employment with a loss of successful career-related identity. Participants in this study had needed employers to shift focus from limitations and loss related to their diagnoses to their individual skills and capabilities. Findings from this study suggest that simple strategies may support employers to manage employees with dementia in the workplace, congruent with Rabanal *et al.* (2018) where managing dementia was made possible by relatively simple strategies. In a recent study from the Netherlands, Smeets *et al.* (2024, p. 1119) explored “the experiences, work values, and support needs of employees with young-onset dementia” and the central theme they found was the “desire to work”, with work adjustments and flexibility being an important part of this. In contrast to Chaplin and Davidson (2014), where relative seniority and greater control was found to facilitate continued employment, Smeets *et al.* (2024) suggested that the opposite may also be true; because of the level of responsibility and cognitive capacity of some employment roles. The participants in this research, *Young-Onset Dementia and Women’s Career Development*, were working in a range of job types and levels of responsibility when they developed dementia, yet all but one had left their employment. This suggests that the flexibility to work differently is not currently a reasonable expectation for an employee with dementia, though reasonable adjustments are a legal requirement, contributing to a schism in the continuation of career. This is a significant concern, given that understanding of adjustments was identified as problematic nearly 25 years ago in Ohman, Nygard and Borell (2001)’s seminal study.

Though a key finding from *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career Development* is that those living with young-onset dementia need to understand how their feelings may change over time, this is also important for those close to them, such as colleagues and friends. Participants needed to be treated with sensitivity and consideration of their dementia diagnosis, but also with respect for their personhood; differently but also the same. Ashworth (2020) also found that being treated the same by colleagues was valued, for example continuing to joke and banter; something that participants in Ritchie, Tolson and Danson (2018)'s research missed when they weren't working. Positive responses from others helped those with young-onset dementia to accept their diagnosis (Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac, 2014), however several participants in *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career Development* hadn't experienced positive responses in their workplaces. This suggests further complexity to be explored as to how colleagues can support someone with young-onset dementia, maintaining a positive continuation of workplace relationships that are the same, but also understanding and inclusive of the dementia diagnosis.

6.3 Non-Paid Work and Activities

6.3.1 Non-Paid Work

Achieving fulfilment through career can be considered as "aligned to what feels like a personal achievement at any point in time" (Stalker and Hambly, 2023, p. 18), and participants in this study described various achievements and aspects of career that were fulfilling and enjoyable but were not paid employment. The enjoyment aspect of career is salient given that prior retirement and other future plans are often significantly altered because of dementia (Clemerson, Walsh and Isaac, 2014). It is important that those receiving a diagnosis know that their careers will not only continue but can continue to be enjoyed.

Though participants here continued using professional skills and abilities in non-paid work roles and activities, these roles were not replacements for paid employment. This supports the finding from Ashworth (2020), who found that even when no longer working occupational status continued to influence the sense of self. Super (1980)'s inclusion of the 'citizen' role as part of the Life-Career Rainbow added interesting insight here, with citizenship being distinct from paid work but an important element of career. Like career, citizenship is a somewhat abstract term but it has been understood as part of development of personhood in dementia research (Bartlett and O'Connor, 2007). Bartlett (2014, p. 1291)'s research focusing on advocacy activities described these as "citizenship in action". Citizenship can therefore be understood as a career identity or role (Super, 1980), and also an action or activity that is part of career. Of note is that the 'citizen' and 'worker'

roles are distinct (Super, 1980); one does not replace the other. Also of note is that the Life-Career Rainbow included transitions or changes within the 'worker' but not the 'citizen' role, which was depicted as static throughout career. For those living with young-onset dementia, the findings of this study indicate that citizenship is not static but holds new meaning after diagnosis. In addition, the relative prominence of the 'worker' role to career was not depicted in the Life-Career Rainbow, nor the loss of paid work due to a reason other than retirement.

Participants in this study were able to find purpose, opportunities for social connection and contribute their talents through voluntary roles. Establishing such new roles helped participants to move on positively from the *void of dementia* or difficult period following diagnosis. These roles took various forms, both formal and informal, but shared the characteristic of being purposeful and enjoyable. Post-diagnosis roles enabled participants in *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career Development* to be and feel useful and contribute in ways they found meaningful, identified as important by van Vliet *et al.* (2017). Voluntary roles that are accessible when living with dementia may be scarce (Novek and Menec, 2023), and this means the opportunity to engage with dementia-related advocacy, research or support is especially important. As suggested by Tilki *et al.* (2023), keeping active was also an aspect of career that some participants in this study enjoyed. However, in contrast with Tilki *et al.* (2023), participants were specific about who they did these activities with and did not mention team sports or exercising with others living with dementia (though Penny had started running after encouragement from a friend with dementia).

Being able to engage with meaningful activities can help people with young-onset dementia to have a positive focus, rather than a negative focus on their dementia (Stamou *et al.*, 2024). Participants' experiences in *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career Development* evidence that it is not only engagement with activities, but enjoying interactions and relationships with others as part of these, that bring positivity to career post-diagnosis. Peers support career continuance, and meaningful activities such as research involvement and advocacy were often spoken of in the context of the group or others with whom the activities were enjoyed.

Dementia support can often focus on older age (Stamou *et al.*, 2024), and it is important for young-onset needs to be addressed through support delivery and design (Rabanal *et al.*, 2018). Support for those with young-onset dementia that incorporates career expectations commensurate with a younger life stage is more likely to be appropriate and enjoyable for younger adults. The findings of this study show that careers had an important influence on support, particularly in regard to the form and timing of support provision. When and how support was provided varied for the participants in this study. Their experiences indicate that, just as with feelings and needs, support

provision needs to be flexible. The timing of support connected with both the life stage and the stage of dementia that participants were experiencing. Elle established her own young-onset group because the existing groups near her were for older people, an example of how sometimes groups designed for older adults do not meet the needs of those of a younger age (Novek and Menec, 2023).

Career experiences also influenced the form of support that was right for individuals, such as facilitating groups in formats and settings that reflected career spaces that were likely familiar and comfortable for participants; such as a professional setting where skills could be practised and shared. This links with person-centred approaches in the context of dementia, where it is important to account for individual personalities and preferences (Kitwood, 1997). The activities participants in this study described had tangible purpose and benefits, with diverse teams and groups. A diagnosis of dementia should not fast-forward towards 'decline' (Super, 1980), so support that focused on the 'maintenance' (Super, 1980) of work roles was valued by participants. Clare, Elle, Penny, Fay and Iona all told me about specific work-related outputs they had produced through the forms of support they were engaged with. In the *Literature Review* two workplace programmes were discussed, *GOOTH* (Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff, 2011), and *Side by Side* (Robertson, Evans and Horsnell, 2013; Robertson and Evans, 2015; Evans, Robertson and Candy, 2016). Whilst they had not been part of such a programme, the participants in this study valued activities that were professionally orientated. Elle's academic report (her career object) represented about three years work that she had undertaken with other people living with dementia and academic staff. Fay was involved in an intergenerational project, Ruth volunteered as a dementia envoy, and Penny helped to deliver dementia training at hospitals for trainee nurses. Participants wanted to share their experience and continue to be and feel useful through their careers; but valued opportunities to do so that were not separate or segregated from others without dementia (as participants were in the workplace programmes).

6.3.2 Non-Paid Activities

Research has highlighted the benefits of creative and artistic activities for people living with young-onset dementia (Stamou *et al.*, 2024), and more formal settings were not the only form of support influenced by career in *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career Development*. Participants such as Bea, Ruth and Darcy all enjoyed creative activities such as singing, photography and macrame. However, Tabitha found a group that organised a creative activity for Easter was not right for her because it had childish connotations. The opportunity to learn and be challenged whilst living with dementia may be an important factor, for example Bea was able to lip read for her choir

performances outdoors and Ruth had photography lessons. Forms of support therefore need to be sensitive to career-related needs. Those living with dementia are likely to have had to end their paid employment prematurely and therefore enjoy the opportunity to use their professional skills in a research or advocacy context. However, the opportunity to learn or practice new activities or hobbies is also important, reflecting how the 'leisureite' role (Super, 1980) may gain prominence when paid employment ends.

Participants in this study found benefit in being able to share rather than simply talk about experiences, a finding shared with Scott *et al.* (2023). Some participants in this study described how they had been unsure and somewhat reluctant to engage with support initially, but contrasted these earlier feelings with more enthusiastic subsequent perspectives. Issakainen *et al.* (2023, p. 11) found that "finding one's way to this kind of group may take time", so encouragement to engage with support groups may be necessary. A balance is therefore required to encourage engagement with support but not force or coerce this in the wrong form or at the wrong time.

In this study, whilst participants from Scotland were positive about the support they had been able to access, this was less consistent for those from other areas of the UK. Availability of suitable support in the UK was highlighted by Gerritzen, Orrell and McDermott (2024). In Scotland, everyone diagnosed with dementia is entitled to one-year post-diagnostic support (Scottish Government, 2023), and participants in *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career Development* spoke very positively about their experiences of this. However, a limitation of the Scottish approach is that only about half of those entitled to the support currently receive it (Public Health Scotland, 2024), therefore further research is needed to understand the impact on women missing out on the support they should be receiving. One implicit benefit of the Scottish approach is the conversations facilitated through link workers and specialist nurses, who are aware of and have knowledge of the support provision available and can encourage engagement. Knowing what to expect from a group and who it is designed for has been suggested as helpful (Gerritzen, Orrell and McDermott, 2024). Relying on internet searching or a leaflet is less likely to be effective than a personal relationship (Novek and Menec, 2023).

Peer support was very important to participants in *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career Development*. A key finding from this study is that peers support career continuance through encouraging and enabling those with young-onset dementia. The need to define and understand peers flexibly was important to participants; it was important that peers were like them, such as others living with young-onset dementia, though this was not necessarily a requirement. Peers were those participants shared equal status with, and with whom they could share mutual acceptance,

supporting the finding from Issakainen *et al.* (2023) that support groups can be important spaces where those with young-onset dementia can be themselves with others who are living with a diagnosis. Peers were able to offer what employment often had not, support and encouragement to fulfil potential and continue careers through different roles. For example, while Leanne was continuing her paid role, she had also benefitted from peers who were living with dementia. She was involved in supporting dementia research and had presented at a dementia conference, which was “so far removed from anything I would ever have done”.

Participants sought connection with others who were “the same sort of people” (Fiona), able to relate to their lives and share insight into their diagnosis. The findings of this study suggest that gender may be an important element of sameness and an important consideration of peer support provision (Wiersma, Harvey and Caffery, 2022). For example, Elle had been part of a woman-only support group and found this beneficial, Darcy spoke about the importance of her connections to other women and her grandchildren, and Tabitha maintained an important connection with her sister. Fay had met a friend who was “absolutely the same” through her support group; “the same age, and at pretty much the same stage”. Her friend’s journey with dementia had differed from Fay’s, and she had died two years before. Fay expressed how losing her friend, and others from their support group, was part of the ‘brutal honesty’ of journeying with one another and giving and receiving support.

Sameness was multifaceted, and not simply about shared diagnosis or gender but more related to equality of status. Two participants directly challenged the importance of peers being of similar age. For Fiona, the needs of older and younger women were “just the same, ‘cause the same sort of people, it's just an age, isn't it, really?” However, other research suggests that similar age and interests are important (Gerritzen, Orrell and McDermott, 2024; Stamou *et al.*, 2024). It was a higher priority for participants in this study that peers could relate to and understand their stage of life or career. Examples highlighting the lack of emphasis on similar age included the children a participant was working with, and older people that joined what had previously been a group for those of a younger age.

Though the *Literature Review* highlighted the value of social media for those with young-onset dementia, this was not reflected in the participant experiences in this study. Three participants told me about using social media: Darcy told me about using an app on her phone to organise taxis, Beth used You Tube to help with tasks, and Fiona used Facebook to message friends and family. Mention of technology or social media was otherwise limited to online meetings, which the *Literature Review* also identified were important (Gerritzen, McDermott and Orrell, 2023; Gerritzen,

Orrell and McDermott, 2024). To date, research related to social media use and living with dementia has focused on predominantly male participants (Talbot *et al.*, 2020a; Kohl *et al.*, 2024b). Future research exploring any difference in how men and women use social media may enhance understanding of how important this is to the gendered career experiences of those with young-onset dementia.

Professionals offered a form of peer support, such as the link workers and specialist nurse for participants from Scotland. However, participants also shared examples of how professionals had been barriers to career continuance; appointments and follow-up that participants didn't feel any benefit from, not feeling heard or having questions answered, and a lack of understanding about how participants' lives were being impacted by their symptoms. Stamou *et al.* (2020)'s survey found a significant lack of support for those diagnosed with young-onset dementia, whilst Nygard *et al.* (2023, p. 13) found that others (including professionals) were "indispensable to support the agency of the person with dementia". The findings from *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career Development* therefore highlight the concern that those with young-onset dementia need support from professionals that they may not be getting.

Prior career experience is also a relevant consideration for healthcare professionals, particularly during diagnosis and in the period following diagnosis. This links to person-centred approaches, the intersecting collection of needs someone living with dementia has, including the need to be occupied or involved in the management of healthcare and support (Kitwood, 1997). For example, Beth felt her diagnosis had been delayed because of her ability to articulate herself. She felt professionals hadn't considered how her professional background had enhanced her communication skills and therefore hadn't appreciated how this and other aspects of her life were affected. In the context of increasing pressure on the NHS and related services, a simple way that healthcare professionals can support those being diagnosed or living with dementia is to consider the patient or client's career. The more professionals know about their patients or clients as individuals, the more likely they are to be able to meet their needs (Kitwood, 1997), and consideration of career may be an accessible and relatively simple way to achieve this.

Aspö *et al.* (2024) focused on transitions when living with young-onset dementia and highlighted the importance of professionals being aware of the complexity of transitions. Understanding how career and experience of dementia are connected may help professionals to attune to transitions. Participants in *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career Development* described not being understood or supported by healthcare professionals, and similar experiences have been described elsewhere (Gerritzen, McDermott and Orrell, 2023; Smeets *et al.*, 2024). Specialist training has been

recommended, for example Stamou *et al.* (2024, p. 2257) recommended that “professionals need to receive specialist training to develop a nuanced understanding of [young-onset dementia]”. Some participants in *Young-Onset Dementia and Women’s Career Development* felt a disconnect with healthcare professionals, they did not feel supported through the diagnosis process or subsequent monitoring of their condition. This contrasted with support from link workers and a specialist nurse in Scotland. By asking understanding and caring about individual’s careers (their *life and work*) as well as physical or cognitive symptoms, healthcare professionals can gain insight that may support the diagnostic process and target interventions to maximise benefits for that person. This would not only ensure that individuals to feel listened to and respected, but facilitate a genuinely person-centred approach that better meets needs and avoids assumptions related to diagnosis.

6.4 Disruption to the Lifecycle (Planning Ahead and Personal and Family Roles)

The third section of the *Literature Review* explored areas of career related to the lifecycle, such as personal and family roles that are part of career and how dementia affected plans for the future. Participant experiences in this study suggest that, concerning, additional support may be needed through the diagnosis process (for example, from a spouse); support that not every woman with dementia symptoms has. Three participants were supported at interview by their husbands. Each husband articulated how they had needed to actively intervene and advocate for their wives to ensure they received a diagnosis. This suggests a potential vulnerability for women navigating the diagnosis process alone. Such support should not be necessary, but some participant experiences here suggest that it is. Recent research from Canada found that family members felt navigating the information and support available was “time consuming, stressful, exhausting, overwhelming and frustrating” (Novek and Menec, 2023, p. 188). This has concerning implications for those without family support, who may need to navigate sources of information and support alone.

Those living with young-onset dementia have career needs related to their roles in the family and home, and women’s careers often have a relational dynamic (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005). Beth and Darcy both discussed in detail how they managed tasks related to homemaking, such as undertaking cooking and cleaning. Both also told me they were not living with partners. Homemaking also arose in Bea’s interview, when her supporter reminded her about activities related to managing their home. As women generally undertake the greater proportion of unpaid work in the home (Baxter, Campbell and Lee, 2023), how a dementia diagnosis affects or changes this has important career implications. It is known that the management of daily routines and chores is connected with

identity (Robinson, Giorgi and Ekman, 2012), and is important for women (Wiersma, Harvey and Caffery, 2022), and future research could explore the meaning of being a 'homemaker' (Super, 1980) as a career role and gendered identity for those living with young-onset dementia. Those living with young-onset dementia need to balance differing needs, and those relating to the family and home were important facets of continuing careers for participants in *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career Development*.

Kinney, Kart and Reddecliff (2011) described how career trajectories are disrupted because of dementia, and this study has found that this disruption also includes career roles. The need to accommodate change and facilitate adjustments was not limited to employment but also applicable to voluntary and less formal roles, including personal roles. Fiona and Darcy had both experienced difficulty with how family members had treated them because of dementia, and Penny and Fay had friends who had disconnected from them. This underlines the importance of peer support and being able to share with others who accept and understand the diagnosis. Roach, Drummond and Keady (2016) found that meaningful activity supported the continuation of family roles, and findings from this study support this. For example, Darcy was able to continue looking after her grandchildren with additional support. Penny and her husband, who had worked together years previously, now enjoyed various types of exercise together. Though most participants in this study were not in employment roles, the alternative roles that enabled them to continue using and contributing their skills were a way of ensuring what Roach, Drummond and Keady (2016, p. 31) described as "biographical continuance". Though they lived with the loss of their employment roles, they were able to mitigate wider loss through finding alternatives that supported their other important career identities.

A key finding from *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career Development* is that career-related feelings and needs change and evolve. Responses and reactions to career changes were not fixed or static but constructed and reconstructed as participants continued their careers and their perspectives on career events changed over time. This finding is similar to that of Nygard *et al.* (2023), where a participant's positive feelings about her employment became more negative over time; and Kohl *et al.* (2024a), who found that feelings about disclosing diagnosis also changed over time. Participants in *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career development* recognised that dementia was a devastating and awful diagnosis, but expressed how feelings and needs had changed for them since they were diagnosed. Factors that had influenced changed feelings included the influence of time and other people. Changed feelings and perspectives were even "in the moment" (Willig, 2017, p. 220) of the interview. For example, during my interview with Beth she told me "I will look at it different now you've said what you've said" when we discussed her use of You Tube.

As interviews took place online participants were in their homes, and interviews included appearances and interjections from various pets (a cat, dogs and birds). Fay described getting her dog as a significant time in her career post-diagnosis, because he needed her to feed and walk him. Animal companions provided not only acceptance, but they needed participants. As Tabitha's supporter stated, "to be needed is a very important human need", and this need continues when living with a diagnosis. Though this can be challenging to achieve with other people, animals continued to need looking after by their owners living with dementia. Research has shown how canine companionship helped people to maintain mental well-being during the pandemic (for example, because dogs were oblivious to what Covid-19 was and continued being the same when many aspects of human life were significantly changed) (Peel, 2024). The pets of participants in *Young-Onset Dementia and Women's Career Development* supported wellbeing whilst living with a diagnosis, they needed their owners and did not judge them. Smeets *et al.* (2024, p. 1122) interviewed employees with dementia and their relatives. A participant in their study said of their relative with dementia: "there [at work], she could take care of people, and yes, she missed that a lot", and participants in this study similarly shared how caring for their animals was a way they could continue caring as part of career.

6.4.1 Original Contribution to Knowledge: Findings

This thesis has made an original contribution to the field of dementia research. This is the first empirical study to explore career development for women living with young-onset dementia. It brings together knowledge from previous research related to different aspects of career, such as paid employment, with new and insightful findings that directly challenge stigma related to a dementia diagnosis. It evidences how women living with young-onset dementia do have continuing careers; and that their careers include change, challenge and a community of others who offer positive support.

Currently, research focused on women who are living with young-onset dementia is scarce. This study therefore offers important understanding into gendered experiences of *life and work* when living with young-onset dementia. Though women's careers are often characterised by multiple transitions (Bimrose, McMahon and Watson, 2013) and interruptions (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005), this study has found that developing dementia exacerbates this and results in careers that continue but are not continuous. The finding that career-related feelings and needs change and evolve connect the stages of career impacted by dementia with those before, for example the need to change and evolve roles when becoming a mum or carer. The support of peers for career continuance needed to be understood flexibly and included other women and (male) partners, as

well as others sharing a diagnosis (and also not) and animal companions. The influence of career on support provision may be particularly important to consider from a gendered perspective, for example because women may have had varying roles throughout their careers and different ‘arenas’ of career such as home, community and workplaces (with again may vary due to roles, with women more likely than men, for example, to have roles in caring professions).

6.5 Methodological Approach

Aspects related to the methodological and theoretical approach of this study will now be reflected upon. As discussed in the *Background* chapter, defining career for this study was complex, and I explain how this complexity was beneficial to the study. Connected with defining career was the decision to use the Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) as part of the study’s methodological approach, and I evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of this decision. I also discuss the focus on women’s experiences offered through this study and how I innovatively used reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) in a ‘methodish’ way (Braun and Clarke, 2022a) as both an analytical and methodological approach. Following this, I reflect on some practical aspects of the study relating to the participant inclusion criteria and consent, and the interview approach I adopted.

6.5.1 The Meaning of ‘Career’

I found that career, as a word, was somewhat problematic during recruitment and data gathering. Participants strongly associated career with paid employment (Barnes, Bassot and Chant, 2010) and often expressed confusion about what career meant to them. An example of this arose when Bea and I began our interview:

Rachel: “*Did you bring an object to represent your career today?*”

Bea: “*My career?*”

Supporter: “*Less to do with career and more to do with your life.*” (Bea, supporter and Rachel)

I did clarify, through the *Participant Information Sheet* (Appendix Six) and *Object Instructions* (Appendix Two), as well as through the study introduction on the JDR database, that career in the context of this study meant *life and work*. However, this definition jarred against a general understanding of career as something with employment or professional connotations:

“...that was one of the questions I was going to ask you. When we use the word career, in this research, you made it very clear, it makes it different because some people choose a career as a mother...” (Clare)

Clare said that I had made the meaning clear, however she also had questions about what career meant. On reflection, including ‘career’ in the title of the study may have alienated or confused potential participants who did not feel they had a professional ‘career’. As there is no alternative word, reference in the study to *life and work* rather than or alongside career may have helped to clarify the meaning. However, an insight gained for future research is that the strong connection between career and paid employment may need reconceptualising in the context of young-onset dementia. Furthermore, as career development theory has been male-dominated (Patton and McMahon, 2006b) women may feel alienated from the concept of career, particularly if they have chosen “a career as a mother” or prioritised other personal roles alongside (or as alternatives to) paid work roles. As our interview continued, Clare asked “do you retire from your career?”, explaining that “I believe life is a career [laughter]. Living is a career, do you know what I mean?” affirming an understanding of career as *life and work* rather than only paid employment.

6.5.2 The Life-Career Rainbow

Super’s Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) was used to understand career in respect of life stages and life roles. The flexibility and relative simplicity of this approach helped to reduce the abstract nature of career. It was also inclusive of aspects of career that other approaches were not, such as the influence of gender and disability, and experiences that did not include paid employment. The rainbow also had limitations, such as not reflecting modern career trajectories. I was also uncomfortable with the rainbow ending with the ‘decline’ stage, especially in the context of dementia research where such a depiction of career and language could be interpreted to perpetuate stigma about dementia being a hopeless condition (Pritchard and Bartlett, 2024).

As I find visualisation and imagery helpful to support my thinking and analytical process, I found the rainbow a useful channel through which I could interpret the data. For example, when Penny and her supporter told me about the “grey, dark picture of dementia” they had seen in a magazine I was able to contrast this with the rainbow with its varied colours and roles, and relate this to Penny’s experiences as she told me about the ways her career was continuing while living with dementia. I also found the Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) supported my understanding of career as inclusive of different roles and life stages. This enriched data gathering, because I was able to explore

participants' experiences of paid work as well as other roles and activities that were important to their careers.

The Kaleidoscope Model (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005) also provided a perspective that was not reliant on paid employment. They proposed the Kaleidoscope as a metaphor to explore the contextual and relational aspects of women's careers, having found through their research that women's careers had a relational dynamic which distinguished women's careers from men's. Such a relational dynamic was evident through the participant data in this study, as the participants told me about the other people who had been important and influenced their careers. In the Kaleidoscope the importance of lifespan is understood through three key areas of career for women: authenticity, balance and challenge (ABC) (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005). In early career the predominant or primary focus is on challenge, then balance in mid-career and authenticity in late career (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005). As the colours and patterns in a kaleidoscope change as it is twisted, they suggested that women's career focus changes over time or at particular transition points, for example after serious illness (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005). This supported understanding of participants' careers not being continuous, as dementia precipitated a changed pattern that was substantially different to the one before. The *void of dementia* could be understood as the shift between one pattern and the next, a period that is part of career but not an ongoing pattern or trajectory.

The Kaleidoscope (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005) highlighted the importance of context for women throughout their careers in a way that the Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) did not, however both depict patterned rather than linear trajectories of career. Such patterns are particularly salient in midlife (Mainiero and Gibson, 2017), the life stage most applicable to young-onset dementia. The Kaleidoscope and the Life-Career Rainbow both conceptualise career in the context of the lifespan, and the Kaleidoscope adds the flexibility to consider how gender and context can influence and change the more linear aspects of the Life-Career Rainbow. Therefore, a greater emphasis on the Kaleidoscope alongside the rainbow may have added some theoretical breadth during the design phase of the study. However, the Life-Career Rainbow was utilised as a basis for understanding career flexibly rather than as a rigid perspective, therefore limitations were negated. Future research could explore career using The Kaleidoscope (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005) to further understand its applicability in the context of young-onset dementia.

6.5.3 Gendered Perspective

This study has focused on women's experiences and voices, offering a needed gendered perspective to dementia research (Bartlett *et al.*, 2018; Sandberg, 2018). Further research exploring men's experiences of living with young-onset dementia in the context of career could provide further insight into how gendered perspectives may differ or align. As women are not a homogenous group, it is also important that future research builds on this study to further explore career experiences and how different aspects of women's identities and circumstances impact their careers when living with young-onset dementia.

This study adds to the understanding of the significant and enduring barriers that women face in their career development (Fouad *et al.*, 2023). Historically, the focus of career development approaches has generally been on early life stages, for example the way girls are socialised in childhood (for example, Gottfredson (1981)), or transitions between early education and initial employment. More recently, there has been more focus on later life stages and the importance of managing career transitions (Brown and Cushway, 2022). This study has contributed to the career development field by offering understanding of how young-onset dementia can be understood as a transition point of women's careers rather than an ending. Further research is needed from a careers perspective to support those with young-onset dementia, such as increasing understanding of how to manage the transition of diagnosis and how paid employment can be facilitated in workplaces.

6.5.4 Reflexive Thematic Analysis

In this study I adopted RTA with a 'methodish' approach (Braun and Clarke, 2022a), meaning that RTA was used not only as a method of analysis but also as a methodological approach to the study. A key dynamic of using RTA in this way was understanding the role of the researcher as an integral part of the research process. Rather than attempting to 'bracket' or marginalise my involvement in data gathering and analysis, I have been an integral element of it. Just as using a different analysis method would have resulted in a different account of the data (Carter and Little, 2007), so a different researcher would have generated different findings. Braun and Clark, who developed RTA, have made clear that the approach is often not applied well (Braun and Clarke, 2024a) and have suggested that greater transparency when reporting RTA studies is necessary. Whilst not aiming for replicability of findings, the process has been detailed to enhance transparency of the analysis process, promote rigour, and enable other researchers to replicate and adapt the process that I have undertaken here in other contexts.

This study has also evidenced how RTA is a “flexible, useful research approach” (Kilty *et al.*, 2023) for research exploring the experiences of those living with young-onset dementia. Researcher reflexivity is important for qualitative dementia-related research, for example to ensure that communication and research design meet the needs of those living with dementia (Webb *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, due to the variable and unpredictable nature of dementia symptoms, researchers need an approach that is flexible and adaptable (Campbell, Dowlen and Fleetwood-Smith, 2023).

6.5.4.1 Creativity in Analysis

RTA not only enables researchers to have the flexibility they require for the needs of those with young-onset dementia, but also be flexible with how they bring themselves into the analysis process. For example, during analysis I was able to follow the six phases outlined by Braun and Clarke (2022a), but did so in ways that complimented my visual way of thinking and creative ability to explore the data. Braun and Clarke (2022a) have emphasised how engaging critically with the data may not necessarily be text-based, and how familiarisation needs to be personal for the researcher and not necessarily make sense to others. In *Thematic Analysis: A Practical Guide* (Braun and Clarke, 2022a) they provide examples of ‘doodles’ and poetry as familiarisation techniques. I not only used these techniques, but also other creative approaches such as clay modelling and crochet.

The examples of creativity discussed in the *Methods* chapter present an original contribution to understanding how quality RTA can utilise creativity to produce a rich and nuanced analysis. For example, the crochet poster (Figure 4 in the *Methods* chapter) that I created during the familiarisation stage of analysis enabled me to better remember and retain the data from each interview, because crochet meant I could interact with the data through the yarn and hook and present it visually. Utilising my sense of touch (Zino *et al.*, 2021) in this way, as well as writing reflective notes and repeated listening to the interviews, established the depth of data familiarisation from which the findings of this study were generated. I was able, through RTA, to explore and embrace different and varied ways of interacting with and connecting with the data; generating an excellent and in-depth analysis.

Figure 11: Crochet Reflection

Figure 11 (to the left) is an example of the crochet reflections that were created for each interview. I noted the reasoning behind my choice of yarn, colour and style for each reflection. This was an early way I generated meaning from the data and recorded my ‘gut’ responses (Brown, 2019). Each reflection was sewn onto the crochet poster (Figure 4 in the *Methods* chapter) to represent the data set collectively in a way not possible with writing. For example, the eyes could take in the complete data set rather than need to focus on individual words in sequence. Since creation, the crochet poster is something I have seen daily as I have undertaken the stages of analysis, unlike notes or transcripts which must be intentionally engaged with. It

has evidenced that the “complexities, interaction, and creativity that reflexive [thematic analysis] offers is remarkable” (Trainor and Bundon, 2021, p. 705), utilising a form of interacting with the data not previously practised within dementia research. Traditional text-based scientific posters may not best reflect the creative, unique and reflexive approaches that researchers use with RTA, and “linear, textual outputs [do] not fully do justice to the research or the participants” (Brown, 2019, p. 39). The crochet poster was therefore not only an innovative way I engaged with the data during analysis, but also a way of disseminating the research that aligned with the qualitative, reflexive and creative approach of the study.

6.5.5 Participant Inclusion Criteria

During the recruitment phase of the study, I identified the need to be flexible with the participant inclusion criteria related to age. When the study was promoted through Join Dementia Research (JDR) there were some participants who expressed interest, but I was unclear when communicating about the age criteria and this caused confusion, which may have discouraged some eligible potential participants from participating. Having greater clarity from the outset of recruitment would have likely prevented this, however I was able to quickly adopt a more flexible approach towards the age criteria and prevent further confusion arising.

On reflection, this issue arose because of conflict I had as a researcher between wanting to protect the integrity of data by ensuring participants had young-onset dementia, and not wanting to exclude participants who may have had young-onset dementia but weren’t formally diagnosed before the

age of 65. This also reflected a form of ‘positivist creep’ (Braun and Clarke, 2022a; Braun and Clarke, 2024a), where I had projected my own understanding of the importance of age into the criteria based on the biomedical definition; when in actuality life stage was more fitting with the approach of the study. Whilst I had intended to promote the importance of a participant’s identification with a young-onset diagnosis (even if this hadn’t been formally recorded), this was challenging in practice; especially when using an online database such as JDR where information about a potential participant’s diagnosis was not always complete or up-to-date. This challenge is not isolated to this study but is connected with the tension of an established biomedical definition that is specific to the age of 65. This age is no longer reflective of retirement or ‘old age’, and aging with a *young-onset* diagnosis is not reflected in NHS recording (Carter *et al.*, 2022).

6.5.6 Participant Consent

Electronic consent forms using Word had seemed the most appropriate way to obtain participant consent, given that interviews were to take place online. Not only was this a practical consideration, but returning the consent form by email was an additional confirmation that the participant understood and was able to engage with the consent process. However, several participants had difficulty with the electronic consent form. I understood this difficulty arose from different devices being used to download and display the form, such as tablets and mobiles, and the consent boxes on the side not being visible to, or modifiable by, participants.

To address this issue, I adapted the process for participants who experienced difficulty with the form. I read the consent statements aloud to obtain verbal consent, with subsequent email confirmation to formally record consent. Further adaptation included a printed consent form for the participant who was not interviewed online. No concerns with capacity to consent were identified because of difficulty with the consent forms; participants had been able to read the form and explain why they had not been able to return it. A flexible approach was therefore important to be inclusive of individual participant needs, and flexibility with obtaining consent has been highlighted as a particular requirement for online interviews (Phenwan, Sixsmith and McSwiggan, 2023). A secure online consent form via a webpage or embedded into an email could have avoided format issues.

6.5.7 Participant Diversity

Women in this study were all recruited through gatekeepers, which meant that they all received support in some form or were involved with dementia-related research. The career experiences represented in this study are therefore reflective of those able and willing to engage with

gatekeepers, and the voices of those less able or willing to do so are not. However, participation in research must be voluntary and therefore an unavoidable inherent bias arises through the sample of those volunteering (Robinson, 2014). Different types of gatekeeping organisations were contacted to support recruitment to help ensure as wide a range of potential participants as practically possible. Using JDR facilitated the recruitment of participants who had not been able to find support local to them, enabling the study to include the perspectives of those who had local support and those that did not. However, as only about half of those diagnosed with young-onset dementia in Scotland receive the post-diagnostic support they are entitled to (Public Health Scotland, 2024), it could be argued that those engaged with JDR have been able to do so because of support (such as receiving information about JDR from those they receive support from).

In this study, gatekeepers were understood to be people and organisations that sought to protect those known to them (Kay, 2019). Whilst JDR has been considered an alternative to recruitment through gatekeepers elsewhere (Phenwan, Sixsmith and McSwiggan, 2023), in this study JDR was considered a gatekeeper because participants were able to raise questions or concerns with JDR if any arose. Participants were also able to decline participation by contacting JDR or indicating this via the JDR portal rather than myself directly as the researcher. JDR also requires participants to be actively engaged to participate in research that may be of interest to them (for example, by expressing interest in a study). However, JDR is not an organisation that delivers support or services to those living with young-onset dementia, and therefore is a different form of gatekeeper to those that do, such as Alzheimer Scotland.

It is also important that future gendered research is inclusive of non-binary gender identities rather than reliant on simplistic biological definitions of men and women. Future research could further explore gendered experiences alongside other aspects of identity. To negate any subtle bias or assumptions about what was important to career, participants were not asked about other aspects of their identity in this study (such as details of ethnicity or family background). Whilst this was a strength of the approach, a different recruitment strategy may have widened the diversity of the participant group. For example, identifying and specifically targeting support groups for those with young-onset dementia from various ethnic backgrounds or for those with LGBTQI+ identities.

6.5.8 Interview Approach

There were no significant technological issues that disrupted interviews, such as internet outage, however there were some glitches (such as freezing or camera positioning). Such glitches did not seem to cause concern for participants, and were used as an opportunity to develop rapport (such as

joking about technology not co-operating). One potential participant preferred to have an interview at an Alzheimer Scotland centre, but we were unable to arrange a date convenient for the supporter, participant and myself. Another participant also preferred to be interviewed at an Alzheimer Scotland centre and the interview was arranged with her supporter, following the regular dementia café she attended.

Flexibility was a key strength of the interview approach. For example, I was able to accommodate timing that was best for participants. Participants were able to participate and in their own private space (Seitz, 2015) and without the need to travel. Whilst facilitating interviews in participants homes is good practice in dementia research (Cridland *et al.*, 2016a), one limitation of the online approach was not being able to ensure the participants were in a private and confidential space (Cridland *et al.*, 2016a). Whilst I was not able verify the suitability of the environment participants chose for their interviews, I respected their choice and no concerns with privacy were evident.

As Phenwan, Sixsmith and McSwiggan (2023) have noted, when facilitating interviews online the researcher and participant are in the same virtual space but not the same physical space.

Advantages of occupying the same physical space include sharing the sensory experience of the interview, and being able to see the whole body of the participant (and the participant being able to see the whole body of the researcher). This can be important for reading and responding to body language. However, a key advantage of the virtual space is that it is less intrusive for the participant, with no need to prepare for or have concern about a researcher visiting. It is also acknowledged that it is important for participants to feel comfortable and safe, and for some individuals being in the same physical space may be important but for others the virtual space may feel more comfortable. As rapport is especially important for participants living with dementia (Cridland *et al.*, 2016a), having the preliminary meeting with participants helped to ensure they were comfortable and could develop rapport with me in the virtual space.

Furthermore, the subject of research can mean that home isn't the most appropriate interview space (Cridland *et al.*, 2016a), and it could be argued that home may not be the most appropriate interview space to discuss career. Being at home for interviews may have influenced the data gathering because of being in a personal environment rather than a professional one. However, as only one participant was in paid employment it would not have been possible to facilitate interviews in other places, such as workplaces (and this would also have raised additional ethical concerns, such as access to a confidential space). This study was also undertaken at a time following the pandemic, which is an important context. Not only did meeting virtually become necessary for many during lockdowns, but since the pandemic more people are working from home and older workers are

more likely than younger workers to have hybrid or home working arrangements (Office for National Statistics, 2023). Therefore, the distinction between personal and professional environments is changing and homes are important career spaces.

Telephone and online interviews have been undertaken in dementia research due to necessity arising from the pandemic (Phenwan, Sixsmith and McSwiggan, 2023; Aspö *et al.*, 2024; Kohl *et al.*, 2024a), or because of a related research focus such as social media use (Talbot, Roe and Brunner, 2024). This study has evidenced that online interviews are an effective and accessible method of data gathering for people living with young-onset dementia. A key limitation of online interviews is the potential exclusion of those less comfortable using the internet or without access to technology (Phenwan, Sixsmith and McSwiggan, 2023). A flexible approach, such as offering an offline alternative, can minimise this limitation. Phenwan, Sixsmith and McSwiggan (2023) used telephone interviews as an alternative to online interviews. However, online interviews enable the researcher and participant to see one another's facial expressions and upper body language, which is an important facet of interview communication (Seitz, 2015).

Interviews in this study took the form of "guided conversation[s]" (Dicicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006, p. 315), with consistency in the opening and closing questions (the *Interview Schedule* can be found in Appendix Seven). This strategy, alongside the use of object elicitation, was adopted so that participants were able to discuss those aspects of career that they felt were important, rather than introduce potential bias by asking specific career-related questions. Whilst a strength of this approach was the avoidance of such bias, some participants may have found this less structured style more difficult to engage with, for example because of a lack of visual aid or "single faceted" questions (Cridland *et al.*, 2016b, p. 1). However, the form of interview allowed me to adjust flexibly in accordance with participant needs, such as providing more prompts if this was helpful.

To negate concerns that those supporting participants may answer on their behalf, I created a separate information sheet and consent form for participant supporters (Appendix Eight and Appendix Nine). I had also included a reminder in the *Interview Schedule* (Appendix Seven) that questions needed to be answered by participants whenever possible. Three participants were supported at interview, each by their husband. With each of these interviews, I found that the flow of the interview became a discussion that involved the supporters, and this supported participants to answer and engage. Participants seemed comfortable with interviews having a triad form, for example they looked at their supporters and responded to their input. Whilst I hadn't anticipated supporters having as active a role in the interviews, this helped participants to feel comfortable and was therefore a strength of this study. For example, during Penny's interview, her supporter

apologised for “talking too much”. I replied that “the priority [is] that you guys are comfortable”. Penny then explained that she started to struggle with finding words, and her supporter was “very good” at helping her with this. Penny was asserting the importance not only of his presence, but also how the triad interview dynamic supported her ability to participate.

However, whilst participant comfort is the priority concern, a supporter’s presence does have influence on the interview. For example, Penny’s supporter told her she was “missing a chunk” during our interview, advising her that “you’ve explained to Rachel about, about the work you were doing. You’ve not really explained how that came to an end”, which prompted Penny to discuss this further. Whilst Penny appeared comfortable discussing how her paid work had ended, she may not have done so were it not for her supporter reminding her. It is also acknowledged that there may have been aspects of career that those supported at interview didn’t want to talk about, or talked about differently, with their supporter present.

6.5.8.1 Object Elicitation

The use of object elicitation was a strength of this study. All participants engaged with this aspect of the interviews and did so in a variety of ways, as did the participants in Willig (2017). Using objects to begin interviews achieved the objective of ensuring that participants could direct and pace discussion (Edwards and l’Anson, 2020). All our discussions began and flowed from initial conversations about the object. Willig (2017, p. 211)’s research with participants who were living with advanced cancer used object elicitation to facilitate “participants’ reflections on the quality and texture of their lived experience”. She found that using objects enabled her participants to focus on what was presently important to them, rather than focus on their terminal diagnosis, and in this study objects enabled participants to focus on an aspect of career of their choice rather than their dementia diagnosis. Willig (2017) also found that the meaning of objects could be influenced through the interview process, for example through discussion between the participant and the researcher. This was the case with some participants in this study, for example during Clare’s interview I told her I imagined that the ‘tree of life’ she was referring to was a strong oak tree. I asked what it was that made her tree this way. She agreed, saying “it is an oak tree that I think about” and then explained about how roots and community were important, adding that “I haven’t thought this out”, indicating how the meaning of objects could be influenced by the interview. Objects also facilitated a form of reflexivity, providing a mechanism through which participants and I could understand the meaning of their choice together.

Whilst being able to ‘think it out’ with participants was a strength of using object elicitation, as Willig (2017) has highlighted, a potential limitation of object elicitation is to focus on the objects

themselves rather than the participants' connection with the objects. This was avoided in this study because the objects themselves were not analysed, though they did support the familiarisation stage of data analysis (for example, influencing the design of crochet reflections). The flexible and adaptable approach to object elicitation also helped to negate the potential limitation of too much focus during interviews on the objects, rather than moving on to other areas of discussion (Willig, 2017). For example, whilst Clare and Ruth used their objects as a theme to discuss their career experiences during the interview, participants such as Penny, Tabitha and Fiona discussed their objects only briefly as we started. Using object elicitation also enhanced rigour within the study by ensuring relevance (Finlay, 2021), as participants were able to represent their careers their way through their choice of object. Objects were not only useful as a way of starting interviews, but also allowed participants to structure what they wanted to share and discuss. Objects also encouraged the participants to talk right from the start of the interview (Dicicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006), and most seemed to enjoy the opportunity to share and tell me about their objects.

Using object elicitation may therefore be a useful technique for ensuring that interviews are enjoyable for participants. Objects facilitate an element of creativity into the traditional interview format without alienating potential participants for whom 'creative' activities (such as artwork or poetry) may not appeal. An implicit respect for participant autonomy and choice was part of the process of object elicitation, as participants were free to choose their object. Most participants found it helpful to discuss the object choice during our introductory meeting, for example seeking reassurance that what they were thinking of was appropriate or asking me further questions about what to choose. Therefore, whilst the object instructions (Appendix Two) were useful, as a less familiar interview method, researchers using a similar approach in the future should ensure that participants are able to discuss their choice in advance to minimise any stress or uncertainty as they prepare for the interview.

Whilst object elicitation has been used in health-related research (Willig, 2017), this study adds an original contribution by extending the method to those living with young-onset dementia. Use of objects in dementia-related research has previously been limited to a focus on art therapy (Byers, 2011), and was also used to explore a connection between museum objects and wellbeing (Camic, Hulbert and Kimmel, 2019). Lee and Bartlett (2021) used a form of object elicitation by asking participants (who were living in a care home) about the objects in their rooms. Clothing has been used to explore identity for women living with dementia (Buse and Twigg, 2014; Buse and Twigg, 2015a; Buse and Twigg, 2015b) and clothing design (Iltanen and Topo, 2015). I used object elicitation in this study in a unique way, connecting the experience of young-onset dementia and career. The meaning of the objects was interpreted by participants, who were able to choose whatever they

wanted to represent their careers. Therefore, the objects had an abstract relationship to the subject of the research, evidencing further potential of object elicitation as a method in dementia research. This builds on previous research such as that of Edwards and l'Anson (2020, p. 47), who asked pharmacy students participating in their research to choose three artefacts to represent "what learning as a pharmacy student meant to them".

A further insight into the use of object elicitation gained through this study was that using this approach online did not seem to negate its advantages. Whilst I was not able to engage with objects using all my senses (Woodward, 2020), participants were able to do so. They were able to describe objects to me and, more importantly in the context of this study, why they had chosen them and what the objects meant to them. The objects helped to facilitate discussion about career in a way that simply asking questions from an interview schedule would not have encouraged. One participant had forgotten to choose an object, but was able to decide and elaborate on their choice without the object itself. Another chose a non-physical object. Therefore, even when participants were not holding or showing me an object, thinking and sharing about it elicited rich and insightful data.

6.5.9 Original Contribution to Knowledge: Methodological Approach

This study has made an original contribution to knowledge through the development of methodological approaches. The use of online interviews and object elicitation here has evidenced how these methods can be effectively and successfully utilised with research participants who are living with dementia. Areas of learning have been highlighted above for future research using either (or both) of these approaches.

The way RTA has been adopted in this study has also made a significant contribution to furthering and enhancing how it can be used. I adopted it not only as a method of analysis but as part of the methodological approach. In addition, I have integrated creative analytical approaches alongside text-based and more traditional techniques. Whilst there are some examples of creative approaches using a form of thematic analysis, none have used crochet to enrich the process as I have. This study therefore serves as an example of how crochet can be used to support and deepen understanding of data through the analysis phases. I have also used other creative channels; including drawing, clay modelling and poetry to think about and reflect on the data through *doing* as well as reading and listening. As a researcher, I have embraced not only my role in the research process but also the visual and metaphorical ways that I understand the world.

6.6 Summary of Recommendations

The recommendations arising from this study are focused on the areas of research, career guidance and policy:

6.6.1 Recommendations for Research

This exploratory study has been the first to explore career with women living with young-onset dementia, and used reflexive thematic analysis and creative approaches in a unique way to support the research process.

- Further research focusing on men living with young-onset dementia and their career experiences would support understanding of how women's career needs may align or differ with those of men.
- Further research is needed to explore how women with differing roles experience career while living with young-onset dementia, for example to better understand the intersectional needs and experiences of women (for example, women who live alone and women who are LGBTQI+ or identify as non-binary).
- As the *void of dementia* was identified as a significant part of participants' careers, further research exploring the transition of diagnosis and leaving paid employment could help ensure those receiving a diagnosis while working are better supported.
- The participants in this study had differing dementia diagnoses and their careers were impacted in different ways by their symptoms. Further research detailing how careers are impacted by specific types of dementia could help address the support needs related to specific diagnoses or symptoms.

6.6.1.1 Recommendations for Methodology

- Researchers using RTA should not only 'listen to their guts' (Brown, 2019) but be gutsy in how they engage and interpret the data. By embracing individual ways of thinking, including being creative, self-expression and artistic play, researchers can ensure that their approach to RTA aligns with their needs and can therefore produce a richer and deeper analysis than they would relying solely on text-based forms of reflection and analysis.
- Object elicitation can be used effectively with participants who are living with young-onset dementia, and is recommended as a way to offer participants control over the interview process. As a less familiar research method, additional time should be factored in to meet

with participants to discuss the approach if they have not experienced this before, to provide reassurance or further instructions.

- Online interviews can be used effectively with participants who are living with young-onset dementia. Advantages include negating the need to travel, being able to see the participant (which is not possible with a telephone interview), and offering participants flexibility over the interview scheduling. Online interviews are therefore recommended when appropriate for the participants and the research design, with additional time factored in to ensure participants are comfortable using the software required for the interview.

6.6.2 Recommendations for Career Guidance Professionals

Consideration of personhood in dementia care is important for meeting individual needs (Kitwood and Bredin, 1992; Kitwood, 1997; Scottish Government, 2023), and career guidance also seeks to be person-centred (Skills Development Scotland, 2023). Recommendations for career guidance therefore consider how a person-centred approach can be realised for those living with young-onset dementia:

- This study has defined career as *life and work*, though found that for some participants the concept of 'career' was not understood in this way and was potentially alienating. It is therefore recommended that practitioners and service delivery managers consider emphasis on a broad meaning of career in communications (if this is not currently the case), to ensure relevance to those who may not consider themselves to have a 'career' and therefore be less inclined to seek or engage with career guidance.
- This study focused on life roles and stages for women, using Super (1980)'s Life-Career Rainbow as a way of understanding career. Theoretical approaches that emphasise the importance of paid work, or are not inclusive of differing gendered experiences or those of disabled people, are likely to be limiting when supporting women living with young-onset dementia. It is recommended that practitioners utilise contemporary and inclusive theory that is sensitive to experiences such as living with a dementia diagnosis, and consider how approaches such as the Kaleidoscope Model (Mainiero and Sullivan, 2005) can apply to or be adapted for women living with young-onset dementia.
- Participants' feelings and needs changed and evolved as they continued their careers whilst living with dementia, so it is recommended that practitioners consider not only the individual's life stage but also how dementia may be impacting that life stage. For example,

participants often found the period following diagnosis emotionally traumatic and difficult. Practitioners can support individuals to move into more positive career stages through person-centred approaches that recognise how important peers can be to those living with a dementia diagnosis.

- Though young-onset is defined as dementia diagnosed before the age of 65, participants in this study indicated that career stage was more important and appropriate for their needs than their age. This is especially relevant because dementia-specific support can often be designed for older people, who are at a different career stage. It is recommended that whilst age may be a consideration, for example for eligibility for dementia-related or other forms of support, age should not be a definitive factor in the delivery of guidance.

6.6.3 Recommendations for Policy

This study adds to the growing body of research about young-onset dementia, challenging assumptions and stigma related to dementia being a condition of older age and evidencing that people living with dementia continue to fulfil their ‘citizen’ life role (Super, 1980). The findings from this study are therefore relevant for a range of policy contexts. Of particular relevance is the delivery plan for Scotland’s Dementia Strategy (Scottish Government, 2024). There are several recommendations which connect with the plan and could therefore support successful delivery of the strategy:

- The plan recognises the diversity of the workforce that support people living with dementia (Scottish Government, 2024). However, currently career guidance professionals are not recognised as part of this workforce. It is recommended that those delivering career guidance are included in plans for supporting the dementia workforce. This will help to ensure realisation of the aim to provide post-diagnostic support that is “person-centred and trauma-informed, based on what people want and need” (Scottish Government, 2023, p. 41). As workforce plans have a focus on the skills and training needed to meet the needs of those living with dementia (Scottish Government, 2024), it is important that those working in career guidance have access to the skills and training available.
- This study has highlighted how careers continue when living with a diagnosis, and the delivery plan specifies the need to ensure that employers are aware of dementia and how this may affect their employees (Scottish Government, 2024). The delivery plan commits to the creation and delivery of a programme to support employers and raise awareness, and it is recommended that insights from this study, such as how career-related feelings and needs related to dementia change and evolve, are included as part of this programme.

- The plan recognises the importance of post diagnostic support and peer support for those living with a diagnosis, but also acknowledges that there are gaps in this support and quality of practice (Scottish Government, 2024). This includes the gap between entitlement to support and receiving the support (Public Health Scotland, 2024). It is recommended that career is considered as part of a model of best practice, so that organisations responsible for support understand the importance of career life roles and stages when designing their services. Career needs to be considered holistically to enable continuance, rather than limited only to those who have paid employment or need employment-related support.

6.7 Conclusion

This study, *“Living is a Career, Do You Know What I Mean?”: Young-Onset Dementia and Women’s Career Development*, has explored **how women living with young-onset dementia experience life roles in the context of career**. I used reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) to analyse data from interviews with 12 women living with dementia. Interviews took place online and object elicitation was used to start each interview.

The research objectives were to:

- Explore how a diagnosis of young-onset dementia impacts life role identities and life stages for women
- Identify enablers and disablers of career role continuance for women living with young-onset dementia
- Explore the meaning of artefacts to career and career identities for women living with young-onset dementia.

As an initial step in addressing these objectives, the literature review addressed the question of what people living with young-onset dementia do in the context of career. The literature focused on paid work and non-paid work and activities. The Life-Career Rainbow (Super, 1980) added further insight by considering career in the context of the lifecycle and life roles and stages. As women’s careers develop differently from men’s (Mainiero and Gibson, 2017) and gendered experiences of dementia are under-researched (Sandberg, 2018), the decision was made to focus on women’s experiences and how dementia impacts their life role identities and life stages. As highlighted through two of the four key findings, participants in this study had careers that were continuing but not continuous, and their feelings and needs related to career were subject to evolution and change. Life role as an employee was impacted by dementia through changes to and loss of paid work, and

roles were gained through dementia advocacy and shared activities. Life roles and stages were not static because of a young-onset dementia diagnosis.

Enablers and disablers of career continuance were addressed through two further key findings: careers influence support provision and peers support career continuance. Being able to access support that reflected familiar career experiences was an important enabler of career continuance, as was being able to connect and share with peers in a variety of contexts and forms. Disablers of career continuance were primarily other people. Examples included not having needs met by dementia-related professionals and having to untangle negative *knots of messages*, such as stigma and misunderstandings about dementia.

The meaning of career artefacts was explored with object elicitation. Participants in this study used objects in a variety of ways to tell their career stories, for example through the use of metaphor or to focus on a career achievements. Women living with young-onset dementia are not homogenous but “women are very, many faceted, multitasked, complicated people” (Clare) and their career experiences and object choices reflect this diversity. Some participants chose objects relating to the past (such as a childhood book), others to the present (such as an academic report). Some chose objects related to professional roles (such as a flipchart and marker pens), others to more personal roles (such as a framed photograph). Some objects were focused on practical needs (such as mobile phone), others related more to feelings (such as a pocket watch/ locket). The meaning of career artefacts to women living with young-onset dementia therefore supports a definition of career as *life and work*, because all participants were able to articulate why they chose their objects and how these related to various aspects of their careers.

This study has evidenced that women living with young-onset dementia not only continue their careers after diagnosis, but continue to enjoy and grow through their career experiences. Having a deeper understanding of the career-related experiences of women with young-onset dementia will inform the development of needed and necessary targeted support. This study will help to ensure that this support focuses on enabling career continuance after diagnosis, so that those living with young-onset dementia can continue to make a meaningful contribution to society and maintain their individual wellbeing.

7. References

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8. Appendices

8.2 Appendix Two: Participant Object Instructions

Choosing an object to bring to interview

For our interview I will ask you to bring an object that represents your life and work. We will start the interview by discussing your object. It could relate to your paid work, voluntary work, or a role you have in your family or community. It can be anything you like! It just needs to be important to your life and work. Please choose something easy for you to find, hold and bring along. You can also draw a picture of an object if that is easier for you.

Using objects (also known as artefacts) in interviews may be new to you. Using objects can help us to think and explain things in different ways, this is why the interviews will begin with the object you have chosen.

Here are a few ideas from my own life and work, but you may choose something completely different to any of these! It is a very individual choice.

This photo of me as a child with my pet mouse Honey signifies the importance of pets throughout my life. It was also printed in Bunty magazine, which I loved reading!

When I was 17 years old, I became ill with ME (Myalgic Encephalomyelitis). This walking stick is an object that represents my experience of chronic illness and how this has impacted my life.

This necklace is my favourite item of jewellery. It shows how faith is an important part of my life. The larger cross was given to me by my grandmother before she died and it reminds me of her.

8.3 Appendix Three: Methodological Perspectives

8.4 Appendix Four: 3D Collage

8.5 Appendix Five: Ethical Approval Letter

11/09/2023 (Dr Gordie Mackay, ethics co-chair)

Dear Rachel Allen,

Your application 21551: An exploration of how women living with young-onset dementia in Scotland experience life roles in the context of career, submission 16837, has been approved by the Health and Life Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Title	Comment
Title of Study	Thanks for resubmitting the ethical application with amendments based on the reviewers comments. This is an interesting study and worthy of exploration. Good luck with your study.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Gary Boyd

8.6 Appendix Six: Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet V. FINAL

Young-Onset Dementia and Career Development

[Ethical approval granted: ref 21551]

My name is Rachel Allen. I am a PhD student at the ASCPP (Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice) at UWS (University of the West of Scotland).

You are receiving this participant information sheet because you may be interested in participating in my PhD research project. These pages provide more details about the project. A video with the details of this sheet is also available on You Tube (<https://youtu.be/zYziCfDJ83Y> or you can find via the *@researcher_rach* channel).

What is the project about?

My research aim is to explore how women living with young-onset dementia in Scotland experience life and work in the context of career. The word 'career' often relates to paid work or employment. However, in this project the understanding of career is not just about paid work but also different roles we may have throughout our lives.

Why is the project important?

We know that women often have different life and work experiences compared with men, and that having young-onset dementia impacts identity and paid work. This project will widen our understanding of the specific impact for women, for paid work but also other roles that are part of our lives.

Why have I been invited to take part?

You have been invited to take part because you are a woman, living in Scotland, living with young-onset dementia (the symptoms of dementia started before you were 65 years old).

Do I have to take part?

No, participation is entirely voluntary. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be asked to keep this information sheet and sign a consent form. If you decide to participate and then later change your mind, you will be able to withdraw at any time until two weeks after your interview. This means I will delete your personal information and data (including any data from our interview). You will not need to give a reason if you decide to withdraw.

What are the benefits of taking part?

You will not directly benefit from participating in this project. However, I hope the findings from this project will benefit others living with young-onset dementia by sharing what is learned from the research. Participating also offers an opportunity to share about your life experiences.

What are the disadvantages of taking part?

There are no direct disadvantages of taking part. However, participation will involve you voluntarily giving your time. Everyone has individual needs, so if you are concerned about potential disadvantages that may affect you, please do discuss these with me.

What does taking part involve?

If you decide to participate, we will arrange an initial discussion online, using Microsoft Teams. This gives you an opportunity to meet me, ask questions, and ensure you are comfortable with using Teams software. We will discuss the consent form (recording your formal agreement to participate) and I will email this to you for completion, if you have not already completed this. You will be invited to participate in an interview that will last approximately one hour. You are welcome to have a relative or friend with you during the interview (they will also need to sign a consent form). The interview will be online, using Teams. You will be asked to bring an object to the interview that represents your life and work. Our interview will start by discussing this.

I would like to record our interview (both what is on the screen and the audio) and will ask for your permission to do this before the interview begins.

Confidentiality

To take part, I will need to record your full name and contact details. This information will be stored in accordance with UK GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) and university guidelines. I will only use your information to contact you about the study. It will not be used for any other purpose

and only myself and Dr. Louise Ritchie will be able to access it. When the research is published you will be referred to by a pseudonym (a name that is not your real name). This helps to ensure your contribution is anonymous. A privacy notice for the project is available on request.

What happens after my interview?

I will send you an email to thank you for your participation. Your interview will be transcribed (what was said is put in writing), so I can read it. You can still decide to withdraw from the project until two weeks after your interview date. After this time, I will begin to analyse the information from your interview and other interviews from the project. You can choose to receive updates about how the project is progressing if you would like these.

When will the project finish?

I will write about the project in my thesis, which I will submit to the university for my PhD qualification. I hope this will be sometime in late 2024. As well as the thesis, I hope to share the learning from this project by writing articles for academic journals and creating an accessible summary in written and video form. You can opt-in to receive updates when available.

~

If you have any questions at all or would like to discuss the project further, please get in touch. My research is supervised by Dr. Louise Ritchie, and you are also welcome to contact her with any questions or complaints. Our email addresses are below:

Rachel Allen [redacted]

Dr. Louise Ritchie [redacted]

-Thank you for reading this participant information sheet-

8.7 Appendix Seven: Interview Schedule

Draft Interview Schedule V.4

Introduction

- Greet participant
- Check that camera, microphone, screen, etc are working for both interviewer and participant.
- Ask participant for their permission to begin recording.
- Ask participant if anyone supporting them at the interview today. If yes, greet supporter and thank them for coming. Remind both that questions will be addressed to participant and participant is to answer questions whenever possible.
- Let participant know silence is fine if they need time to consider their response. They are welcome to take as many breaks as they need to. Ask participant if they would like to agree a signal or other indication to take a break.
- Remind participant of the consent statements that they have agreed to via email.
- Check that participant is still willing to be part of the study and be interviewed, and remind participant they can withdraw at any time without giving a reason until 14 days after the interview (date will be specified).
- Ask participant to confirm their name and age.

Interview

- Ask participant if they have chosen an object. If participant confirms this, ask if they have brought it and show to the camera or post a photo in the chat. If participant has not chosen an object, discuss why and proceed (for example, if participant has forgotten they may want to reschedule the interview).
- Q1: Please tell me about [object].
 - Prompts if required: Why did you choose [object]?
 - Can you describe [object]?
 - Can you tell me more about that part of your life?
 - What does [object] mean to you?
 - How would you feel if you lost [object]?
 - Where do you keep [object]?

- Further questions are dependent on ‘flow’ of interview (for example, discussion about the object might naturally move onto addressing questions below); these ‘prompt questions’ are to be used if necessary to move on from the object, or maintain interview focus:
 - PQ1: How would you describe your current life stage?
 - PQ2: What activities are important to you?
 - PQ3: Has dementia changed your career?
 - PQ4: If someone asks you “what do you do?”, how do you answer?
 - PQ5: I would describe myself as a student as this role in my life is most important to me right now. How would you describe your current life roles?

These additional prompts can be used if appropriate to facilitate flow of the interview (Tense and definition of ‘that’ to be flexible depending on topic being discussed, such as a particular job, role, event, life stage, etc):

- Why did that come to an end?
- Did anything help you to continue that?
- Can you tell me more about how that started?
- Can you tell me more about how that ended?
- This study is focused on women’s experiences, do you think that’s different for men?
- Do you have any support to do that?
- How did you manage that transition?
- How did that impact your career?
- Why is that important to you?
- These questions are to be asked at the end of the interview:
 - Q2: Are there any highlights from your life and work you would like to share?
 - Q3: Is there anything else we haven’t discussed you would like to add?

Post-Interview

- Inform participant that we are now ending the interview.
- Check that participant still gives consent to participate now that the interview has finished.
- Ask how participant is feeling, and put details for Alzheimer Scotland helpline into chat (or relate verbally if appropriate).
- Thank the participant for their time and advise you will stop recording and end the Teams call.
- Positive chit-chat to end well.

- Email participant to thank them for their participation, include the Alzheimer Scotland helpline info and reminder that when published they will be referred to by a pseudonym. Ask participant to 'opt in' by response for further communication about study progress and publication.

8.8 Appendix Eight: Supporter Information Sheet

Supporter Information Sheet

Young-Onset Dementia and Career Development

[Ethical approval granted: ref 21551]

My name is Rachel Allen. I am a PhD student at the ASCPP (Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice) at UWS (University of the West of Scotland).

As part of my PhD project, I am interviewing women living with young-onset dementia online, using Teams. Those participating are welcome to have someone with them for support during the interview. You are receiving this supporter information sheet to explain more about offering support during the interview. This sheet should be read alongside the participant information sheet.

A video with the details of this sheet is also available on You Tube (<https://youtu.be/zYziCfDJ83Y> or you can find via the @researcher_rach channel).

What is a 'supporter'?

A supporter is someone who is invited by the participant to be with them during the interview.

What does being a supporter involve?

During the interview, the participant will talk to me (the researcher) and answer questions. The participant may feel more comfortable having someone they know nearby during the interview for reassurance. While the participant is talking and answering, they may look to you for help with finding a word or offering a reminder. As a supporter, you will not answer any questions or participate in the interview on behalf of the participant.

Interviews are taking place online using Microsoft Teams. Your support may be required with using the technology (such as joining the meeting and positioning the camera), if the participant requests this.

The interviews will be audio and video recorded. You will be asked to sign a consent form as you may be recorded (for example, if you are sitting next to the participant or speak during the interview).

Do I have to offer support?

No. If for any reason you are unable to support the participant, please let them know.

If you agree to offer support and later change your mind, please let the person you are supporting know about your decision as soon as possible. You can withdraw your consent as a supporter at any time until the interview with the participant has concluded. After the interview you will be unable to withdraw your consent because the recording may have included you and will be used for analysis. Participants agree to a separate consent process and are able to withdraw up to two weeks after the interview date.

Confidentiality

To record your consent as a supporter, I will need to record your full name and contact details. This information will be stored in accordance with UK GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) and university guidelines. Only myself and Dr. Louise Ritchie (my supervisor) will be able to access it. You will not be contacted directly about this project. Communication will only be sent to the participant in accordance with their preferences.

When the research is published participants will be referred to by a pseudonym (a name that is not their real name). It may be the case that you will be referred to as a supporter using a pseudonym. For example, if you spoke during the interview and what you said is included in the interview transcript, which is then quoted in a publication. A privacy notice for the project is available on request.

What happens after the interview?

The participant will be sent an email thanking them for their participation, and thanking you for offering your support during the interview.

~

If you have any questions at all or would like to discuss further, please get in touch. You are also welcome to contact Dr. Louise Ritchie, my supervisor, with any questions or complaints. Our email addresses are below:

Rachel Allen ([REDACTED])

Dr. Louise Ritchie ([REDACTED])

-Thank you for reading this supporter information sheet-

8.9 Appendix Nine: Supporter Consent Form

Young Onset Dementia and Career Development

[Ethical approval granted: ref 21551]

Participant Consent Form (Supporter)

Thank you for agreeing to support someone living with young onset dementia at their interview. Please read the statements below and initial the corresponding box to indicate your agreement with each statement:

	Initial
I confirm that I have read and understand the full participant information sheet (V. FINAL) for the above research project.	
I have had the opportunity to consider the information, discuss with the researcher, and have had any questions answered satisfactorily.	
I am happy for the interview to take place on Microsoft Teams and for the interview to be audio and video recorded and transcribed; and for word for word quotations to be used in reports and attributed to a pseudonym.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time until the interview with the person I am supporting has concluded. If I decide to withdraw, I understand that this only applies to my role as a supporter and not the person I am supporting.	
I agree to take part in the above project.	

Name of participant (supporter):

Date:

Signature (please type your name):

Name of researcher: Rachel Allen

Date:

Signature:

Please email this completed consent form [REDACTED] from the same email address it was sent to. Thank you.

8.10 Appendix Ten: Summary of Study

Young-Onset Dementia and Career Development

[Ethical approval granted: ref 21551]

My name is Rachel Allen. I am a PhD student at the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice at UWS (University of the West of Scotland).

My PhD research project aims to explore how women living with young-onset dementia in Scotland experience life and work in the context of career.

'Career' in this project includes paid work and family, community, volunteering and other roles and activities.

Participants need to be women, living with young onset dementia, aged between 50-70 years.

Participation involves one online interview (using Teams). You will be asked to bring an object to the interview that represents your life and work.

This is a brief introduction to the project. Further details can be found in the participant information sheet.

My email address is [REDACTED]

Please do contact me with any questions. You can also contact my Supervisor, Dr. Louise Ritchie [REDACTED]

8.11 Appendix Eleven: Participant Consent Form

Young Onset Dementia and Career Development

[Ethical approval granted: ref 21551]

Participant Consent Form

Please read the statements below and initial the corresponding box to indicate your agreement with each statement:

	Initial
I confirm that I have read and understand the full participant information sheet (V.FINAL) for the above research project.	
I have had the opportunity to consider the information, discuss with the researcher, and have had any questions answered satisfactorily.	
I am happy for my interview to take place on Microsoft Teams and for the interview to be audio and video recorded and transcribed; and for word for word quotations to be used in reports and attributed to a pseudonym.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time (until two weeks after the date of the interview) without giving a reason.	
I am happy for a photograph of the object I select for interview to be used in reports attributed to a pseudonym.	
I agree to take part in the above project.	

Name of participant:

Date:

Signature (please type your name):

Name of researcher: Rachel Allen

Date:

Signature:

Please email this completed consent form to [REDACTED] from the same email address it was sent to. Thank you.

8.12 Appendix Twelve: Participant Privacy Notice

Participant Privacy Notice

Young-Onset Dementia and Career Development Study

The University is committed to looking after any information that you make available to us. We aim to be clear about what we will do with your data. This privacy notice explains when and why we collect personal information about you and how we will use this information including the ways we might share this with others. It also explains how we keep your information secure as well as the rights you have in relation to the information we hold about you.

The headings below set out the main information we need to give to you. If you have any questions, or would prefer this privacy notice in a different format, please contact Rachel Allen, PhD student, by email (rachel.allen@uws.ac.uk). You can also contact her Supervisor Dr. Louise Ritchie by email (louise.ritchie@uws.ac.uk). You can also contact the University directly by email (dataprotection@uws.ac.uk).

This privacy notice has been updated from the University's full privacy notice. This may be updated during the study, and you can check the full privacy notice on the university's website:

<https://www.uws.ac.uk/about-our-website/privacy/>

Who are we?

The University of the West of Scotland (referred to in this Privacy Notice as the "University", "we", "our" or "us") is the Data Controller under the data protection legislation. This privacy Notice sets out how we process the personal data we collect about you (referred to in this Privacy Notice as "you" or "your").

What type of information do we collect about you?

We will collect a variety of information about you. For example:-

- Your name
- Your email address and phone number
- Your age and date of birth

In some cases we may also hold sensitive personal information about you such as:-

- Information about your health (such as your dementia diagnosis)

- Information about your political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, and sexual orientation should this form part of the interview data. You will not be asked about these aspects of sensitive personal information but you may choose to discuss these during the interview if they are relevant and you feel comfortable doing so.

If we are processing sensitive personal information about you then we will make sure that we will have in place additional safeguards when using that data.

What are the sources of the information we hold about you?

We may collect information about you in a number of ways. For example, we may be provided with your contact information from an organisation we have contacted about the study. The organisation will only provide your information to us with your consent. If you agree to participate in the study, we will ask you to confirm your name, contact details and age to ensure you meet the eligibility criteria for the study. You may choose to tell us about your health (such as dementia diagnosis) during interview.

How will we use your information?

We will use the information we hold about you to interview you as part of the Young-Onset Dementia and Career Development study. The interviews will be transcribed and analysed. After your interview, you will be asked if you would like to receive updates as the study progresses. If you later change your mind about this, you can contact Rachel, Louise or the University (using the email addresses on page one) and let us know.

Why do we need to process your personal data?

We may process your personal data for a number of reasons.

Article 6 states that we must have a lawful reason for processing your data. The relevant condition for this study is:

1. the data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes

If special category data is being processed then a condition under Article 9 must also be met. For this study the condition is:

1. The data subject has given their explicit consent to the processing;

How long will we keep your information for?

We will only keep the information we hold about you until the study is completed. This is currently expected to be March 2025, though this may change. We will therefore hold your personal information for a maximum of 2 years.

Data from interviews, such as transcripts, will be kept for 10 years, in accordance with our procedure. Transcripts will be anonymised. This means that any part of the transcript that may identify you, such as mention of a name or specific place, will be changed or removed so that you cannot be identified.

Who has access to your information and who will we share your information with?

This study is being undertaken by Rachel Allen, supervised by Dr. Louise Ritchie. Both Rachel and Louise will have access to your information. No-one else will have access to your information, unless an exceptional situation arises. Should such a situation arise, Professor Debbie Tolson may also have access to the information. Debbie is part of Rachel's supervisory team and Director of the Alzheimer Scotland Centre for Policy and Practice.

Any publications arising from this research will be anonymised using pseudonyms. For example, a quotation from your interview might be used in a publication but this would be attributed to a pseudonym and not your real name.

We will not share your information with anyone outwith the University. The only exception to this would be if Rachel and Louise had a serious concern for your safety or wellbeing and legal advice would be taken before sharing your information with anyone for safeguarding purposes.

What choices do you have in relation to your information?

Under the legislation you have certain rights in relation to the information we hold about you:

- To obtain access to, and copies of personal data we hold about you;
- To require us to stop processing your personal data if the processing is causing you damage or distress;
- To require us to stop sending you marketing communications;
- To require us to correct any personal data we hold about you that is incorrect;
- To require us to erase your personal data;
- To require us to restrict our data processing activities;
- To withdraw your consent to our data processing activities (without affecting the lawfulness of our processing before you withdrew your consent);
- To receive the personal data that we hold about you, in a reasonable format specified by you, including for the purpose of you transmitting that personal data to another controller;
- To object, on grounds relating to your particular situation, to any of our particular processing activities where you feel this has a disproportionate impact on your rights.

Many of the rights above are not absolute so there may be times when you make a request to us and we are unable to meet it in full but if this is the case we will explain to you fully why we have not been able to do what you have asked. You should also be aware that where our processing of your information relies on your consent and you then decide to withdraw that consent then we may not be able to provide all or some aspects of our services to you, such as providing updates about the study.

You can withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason, until two weeks after your interview date. After this time, your interview data may have been transcribed and analysis started. We will delete or update your personal data (your name, contact details and age) and contact preferences at any time at your request.

More detailed information about the rights you have any how you can make a request can be found online: <https://www.uws.ac.uk/about-uws/compliance/information-records-management/data-protection/>

How can you access and update your information?

We want to make sure that the information we hold about you is always accurate and up-to-date. We can only do this if you let us know about any changes to the information we hold about you. You can do this by emailing Rachel Allen (Rachel.allen@uws.ac.uk) or Dr. Louise Ritchie (louise.ritchie@uws.ac.uk).

How will we keep your information safe?

All personal information we hold about you is held on our secure servers. If we hold paper records about you then we make sure that staff are trained about how they should handle this information and make sure it is stored securely.

You can find out further information below.

- Firewall

A firewall is a network security device that monitors incoming and outgoing network traffic and decides whether to allow or block specific traffic based on a defined set of security rules.

Rules are designed to provide a balance between strong security and allowing staff and students appropriate access to teach and study.

- Patch Management

Patch management is a strategy for managing security fixes or upgrades for software applications and technologies. A patch management plan helps the organisation handle these changes efficiently and in a controlled and fully tested manner. We patch our devices and systems as part of a 30 day rolling process. Critical security patches are installed as required.

- Access Control

Access control is a security technique that can be used to regulate who or what can view or use resources in a computing environment.

Access to files and folders and connections to computer networks is based on user credentials, login and password.

- Event/Network Monitoring

The UWS network is constantly monitored for anomalous behaviour which would be associated with cyber-attacks. Event monitoring tools help us to monitor details of activity on the network and allow us to highlight areas of concern for further investigation. Identifying anomalies quickly is vital to securing the confidentiality, integrity and availability of data on our network.

- Anti-Virus

Anti-Virus protection is installed on all endpoint devices and updated at least daily with the latest vendor updates.

Antivirus software is designed to prevent, detect and remove malware infections on individual computing devices, networks and IT systems.

Our antivirus software programs include real-time threat detection and protection to guard against potential vulnerabilities as they happen, as well as system scans that monitor device and system files looking for possible risks.

Data will also be stored on an external hard drive. This external hard drive is password protected and stored in a secure 'lock box' in the event that it needs to be transported.

Does the University carry out any automated decision making using my information?

The University does not carry out any automated decision making based on the information you provide to us.

Will we transfer your information outside of the EEA?

No, your information will not be transferred outside of the EEA.

Who is the University's Data Protection Officer?

The Head of Legal Services is the UWS Data Protection Officer. If you have any concerns about how we handle your personal data then you can contact the Data Protection Officer directly by e-mail dataprotection@uws.ac.uk or by post at Data Protection Officer, University of the West of Scotland, Legal Services, High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE

How can I complain about your use of my information?

If you remain unhappy then you have a right to complain to the Information Commissioners Office:

Information Commissioner's Office

Wycliffe House

Water Lane

Wilmslow

Cheshire

SK9 5AF

e-mail:casework@ico.org.uk and telephone 0303 123 1113

8.13 Appendix Thirteen: Ethics Application Extract (Mitigation of Psychological Risk)

It is unlikely that this study will cause either physical or psychological distress. As interviews will take place via Teams, participants can choose a physical space they feel comfortable in (such as their home) and will have opportunity to take breaks to minimise physical discomfort (for example, needing a screen break or to avoid sitting for too long). Those living with young-onset dementia may have had upsetting experiences negotiating the onset of symptoms and diagnosis while in employment, for example, and consequences such as experiencing significant change. The interview schedule has been developed in sensitivity to the emotive nature of experiences participants may have had related to their careers. Participants will be able to choose the aspects of career they want to discuss during the interview and therefore choose what is appropriate for them. Use of an object to begin the interview offers an element of control to the participant and enables myself as the interviewer to develop the interview respectful of the participant's pace and direction.

My supervisory team, along with colleagues from ASCPP, are very experienced and have excellent skills related to interviewing people living with dementia, and they are able to support me to ensure I interview participants sensitively and respect their needs. For example, I have undertaken a mock interview with the ASCPP Depute Director and incorporated her feedback by including a question about career highlights to end the interview, to ensure that interviews end positively. I have also engaged a critical friend, who is living with young onset dementia, and asked them to review the participant information sheet and object instructions. I asked the critical friend if they felt the interview could be upsetting for participants. Their advice was that "there is always a fear that someone can upset themselves, it's about managing the interview not allowing someone to go to the depths of their mind where they really don't want to be". I have therefore considered how to manage the interview to ensure I avoid participants going 'to the depths of their mind' in negative ways. The critical friend and I discussed how choosing an object had given them control about what aspects of their life were shared. Choosing an object they are comfortable with is a way that participants can avoid a discussion that would take them to emotional places where they don't want to be. Should a participant become upset during an interview, I will offer them a break. I will respect that participants with young-onset dementia, just as other research participants without dementia, have the right to be upset and share their experiences and emotions. If the participant does not

agree to a break, or the interview resumes following a break and the participant continues to be upset, and wants to continue the interview I will acknowledge the upset the participant is communicating, thank them for sharing this with me, and move the interview on through prompting (using an earlier conversation thread or a prompt unrelated to the area that has been upsetting). I will also regularly debrief with my supervisors following interviews about how any emotional interview experiences were handled and how I as a researcher have been affected by any emotion from participants.

Those living with young-onset dementia are considered a marginalised group and may not have had opportunity to share their experiences or stories. Offering such an opportunity through interviews can be empowering and offer affirmation to participants that their experiences are important and worthy of knowing. Whilst doing so may be emotional and possibly upsetting, the interview is structured to enable participants choice about the subjects and topics covered and therefore the potential for the interview to be distressing is minimised.

Participants will be recruited through Alzheimer Scotland and therefore have a point of contact outwith the University should they have any questions or concerns. At the end of each interview, when recording has stopped, I will ask participants how they are feeling and ensure they have time to talk through any emotions that may have arisen during the interview. In case the first point of contact at Alzheimer Scotland is not available, participants will also be provided with the Alzheimer Scotland telephone helpline (0808 808 3000) and email address (helpline@alzscot.org) in the participant information sheet and post-interview email. Helpline calls are answered by trained volunteers, many of whom have experience of caring for someone with dementia in a personal or professional capacity. The helpline can provide details of further support available and send information out free of charge.

- End of Thesis -

